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**Report on mixtures and implementation strategy
in Europe - Assessment of chemical mixtures
under consideration of current and future
regulatory requirements and scientific
approaches.**

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EUROMIX DELIVERABLE 9.1

*Report on mixtures and implementation strategy in Europe -
Assessment of chemical mixtures under consideration of current and
future regulatory requirements and scientific approaches.*

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Abstract

The aim of Task 9.1 “mixtures and implementation strategy in Europe” is to prepare an overview on how mixture testing and cumulative risk assessment are addressed in current regulatory toxicology and how it should be addressed ideally in the future. This report gives an overview on the regulatory processes and requirements for risk assessment of chemical mixtures, identifies gaps in the European legislation and summarises potential approaches for the health risk assessment of chemical mixtures. In addition, the legal acts of Australia, Brasil, Canada, Japan, Korea and USA are analysed with regard to their legal requirements for the risk assessment of chemical mixtures and their implementation. The analyses revealed that, the consideration of combined effects is legally binding in Australia, Canada, EU and USA, whereby the EU has to improve the regulations to avoid loopholes that make it possible to avoid the consideration of synergistic and cumulative effects. Furthermore, there is a general lack of common terminology, accepted methods, clear guidance and harmonised methods for cumulative risk assessment.

Apart from this, available methods and approaches for the hazard and risk assessment of mixtures were analysed in order to provide a structured overview. In total, eleven approaches from ten different organisations were identified from literature and previous reports. While some of the approaches reviewed are meant to be general frameworks, others were developed with a specific exposure source or group of chemicals in mind. The approaches show many similarities in their structures and applied principles, in general a tiered approach is recommended. Further, there is a general agreement to use dose addition as the default assumption when estimating risks of chemical mixtures. The hazard index approach is often used for the component-based evaluation of mixtures.

The report aims to build the basis for the development of an approach for human risk assessment of mixtures and outlines challenges and recommendations for improvement of cumulative risk assessment. The outcome of the report will be discussed in the EuroMix (European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures) stakeholder conference in May 2017, with the intention to revise the report in the light of the comments and advices. In addition, specific results of the EuroMix project, such as the new developed hazard and exposure models of the EuroMix model toolbox, will be considered in the revised version, especially for drafting recommendations and guidance for risk managers. The final report will give an overview on the on-going discussions regarding legal requirements, current implementation, will propose potential approaches for the assessment of chemical mixtures and will emphasise the need for quality control of mixture assessment in general.

1. Introduction

Because the number of chemical uses in industry, agriculture and daily life has increased substantially in the last decades, a paradigm shift in the risk assessment of chemicals is underway, leaving behind the traditional individual substance approach (Solecki et al, 2014). Over 100.000 chemical substances are on the market in Europe and may enter the environment (Schwarzenbach et al., 2006). As a consequence, humans and ecosystems are exposed to large numbers of various chemicals from different sources and via different routes. A holistic study of 4000 European freshwater monitoring sites showed that 42 % sites were likely to be chronically affected by organic pollutants and that pesticides were the major contributors to the chemical risk (Malaj et al., 2014). Also large-scale biomonitoring studies of the U.S. and German population found various chemicals in human urine and blood samples (Becker et al., 2002; Becker et al., 2003; Woodruff et al., 2011; CDC, 2015). This shows that the general public is exposed to multiple chemicals by different routes such as inhalation, food consumption or dermal absorption. Even though the exposure of humans is usually in the range of negligible doses (Birnbaum, 2012), it has been shown, for instance, that low doses of estrogenic compounds, at levels that individually do not induce effects, can cause observable effects in combination (Brian et al., 2005; Rajapakse et al. 2002). As the exposure to intentional, generated or coincidental mixtures is rather the rule than the exception, adverse effects from combined exposure to relevant different chemicals should be considered in an appropriate risk assessment of chemical substances, to ensure human and environmental health.

Within the European Union (EU), the placing of chemical substances and products at the market is highly regulated in order to ensure a high level of protection for human, animal and environmental health.¹ Several European regulations such as the EU Regulation on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (EC No. 1272/2008), the Regulation on plant protection products (EC No. 1107/2009) and biocides (EC No. 528/2012) as well as the Regulation on maximum residue levels of pesticides (EC No. 396/2005) recognise the potential occurrence of combined effects from exposure to multiple chemicals and require taking cumulative and synergistic effects into account. However, the risk of chemical substances and products is assessed based on the specific uses and applications and therefore mostly addresses the exposure to single substances or products by one exposure route only. A more extensive assessment is required, as the exposure to “mixtures” could be either from the same chemical by multiple routes (aggregate) or by multiple chemicals by single route or multiple routes (cumulative).

Currently, potential higher doses due to the exposure via several exposure routes and potential interactions between substances reaching the same target site are usually not considered. Thus, it is important to take realistic exposures scenarios to multiple substances into account and to develop methodologies considering cumulative and synergistic effects for mixtures with known composition, e.g. personal care products, food additives and pesticides as well as mixtures with unknown composition. The implementation of cumulative aspects in regulatory decisions is highly demanded and promoted by EU parliament, EU commission, European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and national authorities (Stein et al, 2014).

¹ Non comprehensive list of EU legislation regulating chemical substances and products: registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals (Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006), classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008), plant protection products (Regulation (EU) No. 1107/2009), biocidal products (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012), medicinal products for human use (Directive 2001/83/EC), veterinary medicinal products (Directive 2001/82/EC), cosmetic products (Regulation (EC) No. 1223/2009), food additives (Regulation (EC) No. 1333/2008) and additives for use in animal nutrition (Regulation (EC) No. 1831/2003).

Furthermore, mixture risk assessment is applied differently in the EU Member States, as no common approach has been proposed by the European legislation yet, with the exception of a guidance document for biocidal products (ECHA, 2015). Existing approaches in the EU also differ from them applied in US or other countries outside of Europe. Although, guidance documents from the EU, other countries (e.g. USA, Canada) and international organisations, such as the World Health Organisation (WHO), International Programme on Chemical Safety (IPCS) and the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) were published, often the lack of agreed and sufficiently specific and applicable technical guidance is the major obstacle for a consistent and adequate implementation of mixture risk assessment (Solecki et al., 2014).

However, with regard to the mutual acceptance of both pesticides and other chemical substances within the EU and the international trade there is need for the implementation of a better harmonised approach for the risk assessment of chemical mixtures at the European and at the international level. The process of harmonisation should be based on an improved testing strategy for toxicological testing, exposure assessment and risk characterisation.

This report gives an overview how mixture testing and cumulative risk assessment are addressed in current regulatory toxicology and outlines challenges and recommendations for improvement of cumulative risk assessment. The outcome of the report will be discussed in the EuroMix (European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures) stakeholder conference in May 2017, with the intention to revise the report in the light of the comments and advices. In addition, specific results of the EuroMix project, such as the new developed hazard and exposure models of the EuroMix model toolbox, will be considered in the revised version, especially with regard to recommendations and guidance for risk managers.

As a follow up of this report, it is proposed to summarise the outcome of the stakeholder workshop in an annex to this report after the meeting. Furthermore, it is intended to publish the main findings of the report and the conference in a position paper, focussing on 1) the current and on-going discussion regarding experimentally verified, tiered strategy for the risk assessment of mixtures of multiple chemicals (derived from multiple sources across different life stages), 2) the need for quality control, implementation strategies and international harmonisation, 3) the acceptance of the new mechanism-based strategy, the bioassay platform, the openly accessible web-based model toolbox, and 4) a clear guidance on a tiered hazard and exposure test and risk assessment strategy to support the global discussion of risk assessment policies for mixtures.

1.1. Background and goal of the report

The increasing occurrence and awareness of the exposure to mixtures in daily life and the need to overcome the chemical-by-chemical assessment approach of the existing legislation, led to a prioritisation of policy and research addressing combination effects of chemicals at the European level. For instance, assessing the health risk for consumers of multiple residues on feed has been an issue for national authorities, thus, appropriate methods and implementation have been discussed at second forum on consumer protections held by the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) (BfR, 2005). Based on the requirement of the Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005 on maximum residue levels (MRL) *“to carry out further work to develop a methodology to take into account cumulative and synergistic effects of pesticides”* the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) held a scientific colloquium with the aim to continue the debate on scientific approaches, methods and available data for human risk assessment of pesticidal mixtures in November 2006 (EFSA, 2007). In

2008, the Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues (PPR) published an opinion report based on the outcome of the scientific colloquium in Parma and an international workshop on aggregate/cumulative risk assessment organised by the WHO (WHO, 2009). The PPR panel came to the conclusion that exposure to multiple pesticide exposures need to be addressed and recommended a tiered approach for cumulative risk assessment and a global scientific cooperation for further harmonisation of procedures also beyond pesticides (EFSA, 2008). In 2009, the Council of the European union stressed “that further action in the field of chemicals policy, research and assessment methods to address combination effects of chemicals is required” and invited to assess how the existing Community legislation addresses risks from exposure to multiple chemicals from different sources and pathways (Council of European Union, 2009). In response, the Scientific Committees on Health and Environmental Risks (SCHER), Emerging and Newly Identified Health Risks (SCENIHR) and Consumer Safety (SCCS) published a scientific opinion concluding that chemical mixtures might have joint adverse effects on organisms and recognised that potential combined effects are commonly not considered in the present risk assessment, which might be due to a lack of exposure information and appropriate data sets (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). In the following, a number of reviews and reports have been published, analysing the European Regulation concerning their requirements for the risk assessment of chemical mixtures (e.g. Kortenkamp et al., 2009; JRC, 2014) as well as available methods for a cumulative risk assessment (e.g. EFSA, 2013a; JRC, 2015). These reports provide an excellent overview on the current regulation within the EU referring to mixtures as well as available methods for cumulative risk assessment.

This report was prepared within the framework of EuroMix founded by the Horizon 2020 program of the European Commission. With the intention to take important steps towards a harmonised risk assessment approach for chemical mixtures this report aims:

- a) to summarise and review the outcome of available reports on EU regulation and identify potential gaps in the current European legislation for all relevant chemical substances;
- b) to analyse additional existing regulations of countries outside of Europe, such as Australia, Brasil, Canada, Japan, Korea and USA, and reveal differences in regard to mixture risk assessment compared to Europe;
- c) to gather existing approaches for risk assessment of mixtures in and outside of Europe;
- d) to outline the challenges of cumulative risk assessment and give recommendation with regard to the development of an harmonised approach

This report is currently based mainly on successive literature reviews. First of all, the current regulations of the EU, selected non-European countries and commenting literature were critically reviewed. Then existing methods and approaches for the assessment of combined effects were gathered and summarised. As mentioned above, it is intended to revise the report in a later stage, in order to consider specific results of the EuroMix project and the outcome of the discussion at the stakeholder conference on the implementation of test strategies for chemical mixtures in Europe, aiming to define the first steps towards a harmonisation.

1.2. Structure of the report

The first chapter of the report launches into the topic of chemical mixtures and gives a general background on the importance of cumulative risk assessment. The second chapter introduces terms and gives an overview on general concepts and approaches for the assessment of chemical mixtures. Chapter three summarises how mixture testing and cumulative risk assessment are addressed in current regulatory toxicology and identifies gaps in the European regulation. Furthermore, current regulations of selected non-European countries were analysed. In the fourth chapter, a structured overview on available methods and approaches for the hazard and risk assessment of mixtures is presented. The analyses were conducted to provide the basis for the development of a common approach for human risk assessment of mixtures. Chapter four partly presents the outcome of Milestone 8.1 “Review of current models of health risk assessment of mixtures”. Finally, we outline challenges and recommendations for the next steps towards a harmonised risk assessment of mixtures.

2. General terminology and approaches for assessing chemical mixtures

In the field of chemical mixtures, definitions and terminology vary greatly in the different specialised area where they are applied (e.g. regulatory area, scientific context, toxicology or ecotoxicology) but also between Europe and other nations such as USA and Canada. The lack of a common terminology was identified as a major barrier to develop a common understanding of the exposure to multiple chemicals, at the WHO/IPCS workshop in 2007 (WHO, 2009). As no harmonised terminology exists, it was recommended to precisely describe the terms referring to exposure and effects of mixtures to avoid confusion (WHO, 2009). This report relies in the on terms and definitions of WHO/IPCS workshop (WHO, 2009) and EFSA documents (EFSA, 2013a, EFSA, 2013b).

2.1. Mixture types

Mixture stands for the “combined exposure to multiple chemicals” (EFSA, 2013a). A commonly used definition, describes mixtures as “any combination of two or more chemicals, regardless of source and spatial temporal proximity, that may jointly contribute to actual or potential effects in a receptor population” (ATSDR, 2014). In general, it is distinguished between “**simple mixtures**”, containing a small number of known and quantified chemicals (≤ 10) and “**complex mixtures**” which are qualitatively or quantitatively not fully characterised, containing many chemicals (≥ 10). Furthermore, “**similar mixtures**” refer to mixtures containing the same chemicals in slightly different proportions or share most but not all chemicals in similar proportions (ATSDR, 2014). It is assumed that the fate, transport and effect of similar mixtures are comparable, which enables for instance a simplified approach for the classification of substantially similar mixtures (EC No. 1272/2008). In general, three different types of mixtures are distinguished:

- Intentional mixtures are products which are intentionally manufactured by combining different substances. Thus, all the components are known (e.g. formulation used as PPP, biocides or cosmetics),
- Generated mixtures are by-products of processes such as drinking water disinfection or cigarette smoking,
- Coincidental mixtures comprise unrelated chemicals from different sources, which potentially reach the same receptor (organisms, ecosystems, populations) by their presence or migration in the same medium (e.g. chemical residues in drinking water, groundwater or freshwater) (ATSDR, 2014; JRC, 2014). Thus, the composition is coincidental and not known.

2.2. Key terms and concepts of mixture assessment

The term “**mixture assessment**” refers to the risk assessment of mixtures, considering products that contain more one substance or substances that might occur together, due to a joint emission or common exposure routes. “**Mixture effect**”, “**joint effect**” and “**mixture toxicity**” are used synonymously and refer to the biological response and thus to the potential adverse effects caused by mixtures after simultaneous or sequential exposure. Mixture may be hazardous due to interactions or due to additivity of the chemical components. Most of the concepts developed for the hazard/risk assessment of mixtures are based on the mode of action of the chemical components of a mixture. In the framework of WHO, EFSA and IPCS “**mode of action**” (MoA) is often defined as a

“biologically plausible sequence of key events leading to an observed effect supported by robust experimental observations and experimental data” (Boobis et al., 2009; EFSA, 2013a). It describes the biochemical events that cause an observable effect and contrasts with the “**mechanism of action**” which implies the detailed understanding of the effect development on the molecular level (WHO, 2009). The adverse outcome pathway (AOP) is a framework which is conceptually similar approach to a mode of action (Meek et al., 2014). It is defined as “*a sequence of events from the exposure of an individual or population to a chemical substance through a final adverse (toxic) effect at the individual level (from a human health perspective) or population level (from an environmental perspective)*” (EFSA, 2014). An AOP organises existing knowledge of the effect progression, starting from the initial point of chemical-biological interaction within the organism (molecular initiating event; MIE), continuing with intermediate measurable biological changes (key events; KE), which are connected via key event relationship (KER), finishing with an adverse outcome (AO) of regulatory concern (OECD, 2013; EFSA, 2014, Villeneuve et al., 2014).

Chemicals that occur simultaneously might cause a “**combined toxicity**”, defined as the “response of a biological system to several chemicals, either after simultaneous or sequential exposure” (EFSA, 2013b). Chemical substances can act differently in mixtures, for this reason a distinction is made between dose addition, response addition or interaction. “**Concentration addition**” assumes that all components of a mixture have a similar MoA (EFSA, 2013a), target the same target cell and behave as if they were a simple dilution of each other. Thus, the effects of exposure to a mixture of chemicals with the same MoA are predicted by summing the potency-corrected effects of each component (EFSA 2013a, EFSA, 2013b). For chemicals that act independently by different MoAs, the combination effect can be calculated from the individual responses of the components of a mixture, referred to as “**independent action**” (EFSA 2013a, EFSA, 2013b). “**Interactions**” are joint actions between chemicals causing a combined effect of a mixture that is different from additivity, based on the dose-response relationships of the individual components (ATSDR, 2014). In this context, one differentiates between combined effects being greater than predicted on the basis of additivity (**synergism**), or less than estimated for additivity of the components (**antagonism**) (EFSA, 2013a).

For the cumulative risk assessment different sources of emission pathways and routes of exposure are taken into consideration. Therefore, different **exposure scenarios**, defining situations of a potential exposure including sources, exposed population, timeframe and activities, are considered. Here, information on the way the agent takes from the source to the target (**exposure pathway**) and the course the agent enters a target after contact (**exposure route**) is taken into account (Zartarian, et al., 2005). In human risk assessment, a distinction is made between the exposure of operator, worker, bystander and resident for instance.

The general term “**combined exposure**”, refers to the exposure to one or more chemical substances from different sources, pathways and routes (Bunke et al., 2014). According to the guidance document of the ECHA (2015) three different exposure scenarios can be classified:

- i. combined exposure to multiple substances by one source of release(s) and/or use(s),
- ii. combined exposure to multiple substances by different sources of release(s) and/or use(s),
- iii. aggregated exposure to single substances from different sources of release(s) and/or use(s).

In this context, the WHO/IPCS workshop recommended to avoid the ambiguous term “**cumulative exposure**”, comprising both the combined exposure to multiple chemicals by single and multiple sources or routes (WHO, 2009). Instead, it was proposed to precisely refer to exposure to “**multiple chemicals by multiple routes**”, or to “**multiple chemicals by a single route**” (WHO, 2009).

“**Aggregate exposure**” is shortly described as “single chemical, all routes”, which implies the exposure to the same chemical substance from different sources, multiple pathways and/or routes (Meek et al., 2011). Likewise, the “**aggregated risk**” is the risk of a single chemical considering multiple routes of exposure, whereas “**cumulative risk**” is the risk exerted by multiple chemicals (sometimes restricted to chemicals with the same MoA) considering aggregated exposure and therefore multiple routes of exposure (WHO, 2009). Groß et al. (2011) gave a comprehensive summary of terms and definitions in the context of cumulative exposure and risk assessment and outlined clear differences in some definitions. Table A1 of the Annex shows the overview of terms given by Groß et al., (2011), extended by definitions given by EFSA as well as legal directives and regulations.

2.3. General approaches for assessing mixture toxicology

There are two principal approaches for the hazard and risk assessment of chemical mixtures: testing the mixture in its entirety termed ‘whole mixture approach’ or the prediction of the mixture toxicity based on the composition of the mixture, taking into account the toxicities of all constituents, called ‘component based approach’.

The **whole mixture approach** provides measured data and thus experimental evidence on the effect of the entire mixture. It is regularly applied for the assessment of environmental mixtures such as effluents of wastewater as well as the classification of formulated products (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008). However, the application is usually restricted to acute and thus short-term toxicity, as long-term tests provide, due to the different fate and kinetics of the components, only limited knowledge on the potential chronic effects on humans or the environment (Backhaus et al., 2010). The whole mixture approach is not applicable for prospective risk assessment, as the mixture has to be available for direct testing, and is therefore no general solution. Furthermore, from an economic, ethical and practical point of view it is not feasible to test all combinations of chemicals (Backhaus et al., 2010).

The **component based approaches** enable the prediction of combined effects, based on effect data for the known or assumed components of the mixture. They can be applied for prospective risk assessment, as there is no need to systematically test different mixture ratios and mixture concentrations (Kortenkamp et al., 2009). These approaches refer to the three types of actions for the combined exposure of chemicals: i) concentration addition and ii) independent action, assuming that components of the mixture do not interact at the biological target site and therefore do not influence each other’s toxicity, and iii) interaction assuming joint actions of components.

Concentration addition also referred to as dose addition, similar action or similar joint action, applies for similarly acting chemicals (JRC, 2014) and was introduced by Loewe et al. (1926). The approach is based on general pharmacological knowledge and receptor based thinking, assuming that components of a mixture that interact with the same target site of an organism, increase the total dose at the target site, leading to increasing effects of mixtures (Altenburger et al., 2013). Thus, it is assumed that effects of the different components can be simply added, after they have been scaled for their potencies. According to the literature reviewed by Kortenkamp et al. (2009), concentration addition is a reliable model to estimate combined effects of strictly identical components with similar mechanism of action or mixtures with components having a baseline-toxicity (Kortenkamp et al., 2009).

Independent action was firstly introduced by Bliss (1939), and is also known as response addition, effect addition, simple independent action, dissimilar action or independent joint action (JRC, 2014). The concept assumes that chemicals with a different MoA (dissimilar action), affect the same endpoint due to different target sites (tissues, cells or molecular receptors) (Backhaus and Faust, 2013). Therefore, the toxic action of each component is independent and does not influence the others. Independent action is a probabilistic approach that calculates the joint probability of statistically independent events, based on the effect that each component would cause in a single treatment at a concentration found in the mixture (Backhaus and Faust, 2013). The model is restricted to mixtures containing dissimilarly acting compounds, where concentration response curves of all components are known.

Independent action as well as concentration addition, assume that the components of a mixture do not influence the uptake, distribution or metabolism of each other (Backhaus and Faust, 2013). Both concepts simplify the biological response, which allows establishing general guidelines, but might not represent the biological reality (Backhaus and Faust, 2013). In most cases mixtures consist of similar and dissimilar acting components, whereas both concepts assume a well-defined mixture of either similar or dissimilar acting components. Nevertheless, independent action and concentration addition have been proposed as default approaches in regulatory risk assessment (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). In comparison to the independent action approach, concentration addition is more conservative with a lower risk of underestimating the mixture toxicity, data requirements are easier to fulfil and empirical studies revealed that synergistic effects higher than the assumption of concentration addition are rather exceptions (Altenburger et al., 2013). Therefore, concentration addition is often discussed as a general default assumption for the hazard estimation of mixtures, irrespective of similar or dissimilar MoAs of the components (Backhaus et al., 2004; Kortenkamp et al., 2009).

Interactions of mixture components can lead to deviations of the estimation made by concentration addition or independent action. These can cause more toxic, synergistic effects or less toxic, antagonistic effects. Deviations from the concentration addition or independent action might appear as a result of:

- i. toxicokinetic interactions during the uptake, distribution, metabolism or elimination of the chemicals (e.g. components of a mixture modify the absorption of the other or compete for an active transport),
- ii. toxicodynamic interactions during the effect development (interference of the biological responses on receptors, target cell or organ), or
- iii. metabolic interactions, one component leads to a changed metabolism of the other (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012).

However, no models are available to estimate the biological response of components which interact and therefore influence the toxicity of each other (Altenburger, et al., 2013).

3. Legal basis regarding chemical mixtures

Two extensive reviews of the EU regulation regarding the requirements of the risk assessment of chemical mixtures have been conducted with the intention to assess if EU regulation accounts for potential effects of combined exposures to multiple chemicals (Kortenkamp et al., 2009; JRC, 2014). The recently published JRC report (JRC, 2014) analysis regulations for intentional mixtures, applying for industrial chemicals regulated under REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals; Regulation (EC) No. 1907/2006), the classification labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP; Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008), plant protection products (Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009), biocidal products (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012), medicinal products for human use (Directive 2001/83/EC), veterinary medicinal products (Directive 2001/82/EC), cosmetic products (Regulation (EC) No. 1223/2009), food additives (Regulation (EC) No. 1333/2008) and additives for use in animal nutrition (Regulation (EC) No. 1831/2003). Additionally, regulations referring to unintentional mixtures such as contaminants in food (Regulation No. 315/93/EEC), water contaminants (Directive 2006/60/EC, Directive 2006/118/EC, Directive 98/83/EC) or waste production (Directive 2008/98/EC) have been reviewed by JRC (2014).

The present report aims to identify potential gaps regarding chemical mixtures in the current European legislation. The study focusses on industrial chemicals regulated under REACH and CLP, intentional mixtures of plant protection products, biocidal products and their active substances, as well as human and veterinary pharmaceuticals, cosmetic products and food and feed additives (section 3.1). An overview of all reviewed regulations relating to intentional mixture is given in Table 1. The risk assessment of unintentional mixtures is more challenging, as the occurrence of these mixtures is often coincidental and components are not known. Therefore, it is difficult to set regulatory requirements. As a result, legislations dealing with unintentional mixtures (contaminants in food, water contaminants, soil quality, ambient air quality, waste production) either do not address mixture toxicity and cumulative exposure or requirements are not specific (JRC, 2014). As we aim to develop an approach to implement the legislative requirements for mixtures, less regulated unintentional mixtures are beyond the scope of this study. However, an overview of the regulations referring to unintended mixtures is provided in Table 2, based on the valuable work done by JRC (JRC, 2014).

Furthermore, regulations on chemical substances and products from selected non-European countries have been analysed. Section 3.2 gives an overview of the legal frameworks of Australia, Brasil, Canada, Japan, Korea and USA and refers to their requirements and approaches to assess the toxicity of chemical mixtures.

Table 1: Overview of the chemical and mixture assessment requirements for intentional mixtures in the European regulation, based on JRC (2014).

Regulation / Directive	Chemical monitoring and analysis	Encouraging alternative methods to animal testing	Chemical risk assessment		Mixture assessment		Pro-spective RA	Retro-spective RA
			Human health	Environmental health	Human health	Environmental health		
EC No. 1107/2009 on plant protection products (PPPs)	No (Environment)/ Yes (Residues)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes – WM approach (for formulation)		Yes	No
EU No. 283/2013 on data requirements for active subst.								
EU No. 284/2013 on data requirements for PPPs								
EU No. 528/2012 on biocidal products	No (Environment)/ Yes (Residues)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes – WM approach, plus risk assessment if the biocidal product is intended to be used in combination with other biocidal product.		Yes	No
Directive 2001/83/EC on medicinal prod. for human use	No	Not specified	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Directive 2001/82/EC on veterinary medicinal products	No Environment)/ Yes (Residues in foodstuff)	Not specified	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
EC No. 1223/2009 on cosmetic prod.	No	Yes	Yes	Through REACH	Yes	No	Yes	No
EC No. 1272/2008 on CLP	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
EC No. 1907/2006 on REACH	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
EC No. 1333/2008 2008 on food additives	Yes (intake)	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No
EC No. 1831/2003 on additives for use in animal nutrition	Yes (residue)	No	Yes	Yes	Additive with multiple components: consideration is given for the cumulative effects or WM assessment. No consideration for mixture assessment from different sources		Yes	No
EC No. 429/2008 on assessment of feed additives								

Table 2: Overview of the chemical and mixture assessment requirements for generated or coincidental mixtures in the European regulation, based on JRC (2014).

Regulation / Directive	Chemical monitoring and analysis	Encouraging alternative methods to animal testing	Chemical risk assessment		Mixture assessment		Pro-spective RA	Retro-spective RA
			Human health	Environmental health	Human health	Environmental health		
Directive 2011/92/EC on EIA - environmental impact assessment	No	No testing	Yes	Yes	Should be addressed		Yes	No
Directive 2010/75/EC on IPPC - Integrated pollution prevention and control	Yes	No testing	No	No	No	No	No	No
Directive 2008/98/EC on waste and waste streams	No, but refers to other legislation, e.g. REACH, IPPC	No	Refers to CLP	Refers to CLP	No		No	No
Directive 98/83/EC on Water Framework Directive (WFD)	Yes	No testing	Yes	Yes	Mentioned in Guidance, but not addressed in detail		No	Yes
Directive 2006/118/EC on groundwater	Yes, with reference to WFD	No	No RA, but contained additional threshold value for pesticides and nitrates	No	No	No	No	No
Directive 2013/39/EU on EQS - environmental quality standards	Yes	Yes	No	No RA, but QS are derived from ERA studies	No	Yes	No	No
Directive 2008/56/EC on marine strategy	Yes	No testing	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
Directive 98/83/EC on drinking water	Yes	No testing	No RA, but parametric values should be based on a RA method	No	No	No	No	No
COM(2006) 231 & COM(2006) 232 final – COD 2006/0086 thematic strategy for soil protection	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes

Regulation / Directive	Chemical monitoring and analysis	Encouraging alternative methods to animal testing	Chemical risk assessment		Mixture assessment		Pro-spective RA	Retro-spective RA
			Human health	Environmental health	Human health	Environmental health		
Directive 2008/50/EC on ambient air quality	Yes	No testing	Yes	Partly	No	No	No	Yes
EC No. 1935/2004 food contact material	Yes	Not specified	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No
Regulation 315/93/EEC on food contaminants	Yes (food)	Not specified	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No
Directive 2002/32/EC on feed contaminants	Yes (food)	Not specified	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
EC No. 396/2005 on MRLs - maximum residue levels	Yes	Not specified	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Directive 98/24/EC on protection of the health of workers	Yes	Not specified	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Directive 2009/48/EC on toys	Yes	No testing	No RA but threshold value and refers to CLP	No	Refers to CLP	No	Yes	No

3.1. Considerations of chemical mixtures in European legislation

In the following section, legislations on industrial chemicals regulated under REACH and CLP and legislations on intentional mixtures of plant protection products, biocidal products and their active substances, as well as human and veterinary pharmaceuticals, cosmetic products and food and feed additives are outlined. All regulations have been analysed with the aim to assess if and in which way mixture toxicity is taking into consideration for the hazard, risk or safety assessments of the chemical substances or products. All reviewed regulations refer to intentional mixtures with known composition.

3.1.1. General legislations

3.1.1.1. REACH

In the EU the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) is regulated by the Regulation EC No. 1907/2006, which entered into force in 2007. REACH aims “[...] to ensure a high level of protection of human health and the environment, including the promotion of alternative methods for assessment of hazards of substances, as well as the free circulation of substances on the internal market while enhancing competitiveness and innovation” (Article 1). All substances imported or produced in quantities of more than one ton per year must be registered to the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). Thus, REACH not only applies to chemical substances used in industrial or agricultural processes, but also to substances used in day-to-day lives. The companies producing or importing these chemical substances have to assess and manage the risks posed by them and provide appropriate safety information for the users. The ECHA evaluates all registrations dossiers of the companies and the EU Member States evaluate selected substances with concerns for human health or the environment. The evaluation may result in the authorisation of the substances or, if risks are unmanageable, in restriction processes leading to a limitation in the use or even a ban. The chemical safety assessment within REACH is crucial to ensure that all risks are identified and under control.

Under REACH, the terms “mixture”, “preparation” and “solution” are used synonymously. Mixtures are composed of two or more substances, whereas a chemical substance is defined as a chemical element and its compounds including additives for its stability and impurities. Here, also Multi-Constituent Substances (MCS) resulting from a chemical reaction in which several constituents are included at more than 10 %, chemicals containing up to 20% arbitrary by-products (JRC, 2014) and “[...] UVCB substances (substances of unknown or variable composition, complex reaction products or biological materials) may be registered as a single substance [...] provided that the hazardous properties do not differ significantly and warrant the same classification”. By definition these mixtures are treated as one chemical substance. As REACH is based on a single substance approach, all obligations are related to substances and no requirements and guidance for the hazard and risk assessment of mixtures is provided (Kortenkamp et al., 2009).

Within the chemical safety assessment of REACH, Derived No-effect-Levels (DNEL) for the human health assessment have to be estimated. The DNEL shall be established for each route of exposure and for the exposure from all routes combined, if more than one route is likely to occur (Annex 1; 1.4.1). Thus, REACH requires that all relevant exposure routes are investigated for each individual substance. For the exposure assessment “[...] each relevant route of human exposure (inhalation, oral, dermal and combined through all relevant routes and sources of exposure) shall be addressed. Such estimations shall take account of spatial and temporal variations in the exposure pattern [...]”

(Annex 1, paragraph 5.2.4). The ECHA guidance document on information requirements and chemical safety assessment stipulates for the risk characterisation for human health, that exposure scenarios such as if “[...] *the same person is potentially exposed to the same substance [...] via different routes [...] or from different products [...], these concomitant exposures should be assessed in the exposure estimation*” (ECHA, 2012a). For substances with consumer use the applicant is supposed to assess the combined exposure for the general public exposed both via the food and via consumer products. In contrast, the guidance document on consumer estimation clearly states that the applicant is “not obliged to carry out a risk characterisation related to uses of the substance not covered in his own registration (ECHA, 2012b)”. If the same substance occurs in different consumer products that could be expected to be used jointly it is advised to calculate the combined exposure jointly. Then, “[...] *the contribution of each route to the total risk due to exposure should be summed [...] separately for each time scale (acute and long-term)*” (ECHA, 2012b)”.

Under REACH each company or consortia of companies are required to register and ensure the safe production and use of chemical substances. However, it is doubtful whether individual registrants have information beyond their own tonnage and use. The registrants are advised to check whether the foreseeable uses of their customers are covered by the exposure scenarios of the substance (CEFIC, 2016). However, they generally do not have the knowledge in which mixture and for what purpose the substance registered by him is used by downstream formulators (JRC, 2014). Thus, the prerequisite for the consideration of the total exposure and the overall risk exerted by the chemical substances may not be given, even though it may occur, that due to several uses of different registrants or formulators the risk will sum up and may cause adverse effects. The “Practical Guide on Exposure Assessment and Communication in the Supply Chains” clearly shows that REACH does not require a cumulative risk assessment and that nearly all REACH requirements are related to the substance itself or substances as part of a mixture, but not to mixtures (CEFIC, 2010). Furthermore, the actors in the supply chain are not obliged to develop an exposure scenario for the mixture (JRC, 2014). Recently the guidance was updated, implementing a methodology for the generation of safe use information of mixtures, considering hazardous substances above certain concentration criteria. However, no final agreement on the assessment of interactions in mixtures exists. Thus, the evaluation of mixtures relies on expert judgement, “[...] *as the effects of a multitude of possible combinations of substances in a mixture cannot be anticipated*” (CEFIC, 2016). Only the Authorities have access to the relevant information on aggregated exposure of the same substance marketed by different registrants and by different uses, but they have no obligations for the assessment of the combined exposure exists for them (Tørsløv et al. 2011). Thus, it is not regulated how cumulative and aggregated exposures from substances of different registrants are to be assessed, in order to ensure human and environmental health.

3.1.1.2. CLP

Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 on the classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures entered into force on the 20 January 2009. It amended and repealed the Directives on the classification, packaging and labelling of dangerous substances (Directive 67/548/EEC) and dangerous preparations (Directive 1999/45/EC). The CLP regulation aligns the classification system of the EU to the Globally Harmonised System (GHS) introduced by the United Nations to simplify global trade. It applies for all substances and mixtures, except for medicinal products, veterinary medicinal products, cosmetics, medical devices, food and feed stuff. It aims to ensure “*a high level of protection of human health and the environment as well as the free movement of chemical substances, mixtures*”

and articles”, within the EU (Article 1; Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008). Therefore, the CLP regulation ensures that potential hazards caused by chemical mixtures or substances are clearly communicated to users and consumers through standard statements and pictograms on labels. For the classification of substances and mixtures, hazardous properties such as physical hazards, hazards to human health, the environment or the ozone layer, requiring a classification need to be identified. Also, information on the *“potential occurrence of synergistic or antagonistic effects among the substances in mixture”* has to be taken into account for classification (Article 12, Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008). The member state or the supplier collects available data, evaluates physical, toxicological and ecotoxicological hazards and proposes the hazard class or classes in which the substance or mixture shall be classified. This proposal is evaluated by the ECHA Risk Assessment committee in a scientific opinion, which is used by the Commission to finally decide on the classification and labelling.

The CLP Regulation provides clear criteria for the classification of substances but also for mixtures. Health and environmental hazard classes are defined depending on the effect of the substance on the organism or the environment, the hazard category reflects the severity of the effect. The classification principles for health and environmental hazards can be found in Annex I of Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008, an overview is given in Table 3 and Table 4 of this document. The classification of a substance or a mixture is based on available scientific data. The supplier is not obliged to produce new data for the classification. In case, experimental data on the whole mixture is available, the mixture should be classified based on that. If there is data from similar mixtures with comparable concentrations of components available the *“bridging principles”* are applied (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008, Annex 1, 1.1.3). However, mixtures are often classified based on the available information of the components. If amounts of classified components are known the summation method is used, if components are not classified but toxicity data is available the concertation addition method is applied. The component-based classification has to be applied if components of a mixture are classified as *“carcinogenic, germ cell mutagenic or reproductive toxic substances, or where the biodegradation or bioaccumulation properties in the hazard class hazardous to the aquatic environment are evaluated”* (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008, Recital 22). Table 3 and Table 4 summarise hazard classes and classification approaches based on health and environmental criteria according to Kortenkamp et al. 2009.

The classification of mixtures is handled differently among human health hazard and aquatic environmental hazard. For human health specific and generic concentration limits and generic cut-off values are applied. Generic concentration limits imply that from a certain threshold on the presence of a substance in a mixture or an impurity within a substance is hazardous, which leads to a classification of the substance or the mixture (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008, Article 10), whereas a specific concentration limit is set, when scientific data reveals that the substance is hazardous even below the generic concentration limit. Thus, specific concertation limits have priority over generic concentration limits. Generic cut-off values require a classification of the mixture if a classified component of the mixture is present in proportions higher than 0.1% (acute toxic category 1-3) or 1% (acute toxic category 4, skin corrosion or eye irritation) (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008, Annex 1, Table 1.1)

Table 3: Health hazard classes and hazard categories according to Regulation (EU) No. 1272/2008 and mixture classification approaches as summarized in Kortenkamp et al. (2009).

Hazard classes based on health criteria	Hazard category		Whole mixture tests	Bridging principles	Concentration addition	Summation method/conc. limits	Application order
	Summarised Annex 1, Reg. (EC) No. 1272/2008		Based on Kortenkamp et al., 2009				
Acute toxic	Category 1	Categories are defined based on acute toxicity estimates (ATE) for oral, dermal, gases, vapours, dusts and mists. Category 1 represents the highest acute toxicity, category 4 the lowest. See Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	WM-BP-SM-CA
	Category 2						
	Category 3						
	Category 4						
Skin corrosion /irritation	Category 1A	Exposure ≤ 3 min, observations ≤ 1 hour	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	WM-BP-CA-SM
	Category 1B	Exposure > 3 min to ≤ 1 hour, observations ≤ 14 days					
	Category 1C	Exposure > 1 hour to ≤ 4 hours, observations ≤ 14 days					
Eye damage / eye irritation	Category 1	Irreversible effects on the eye	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	WM-BP-CA-SM
	Category 2	Irritating to eyes					
Respiratory or skin sensitisation	Category 1	Evidence in human or positive results from animal tests for respiratory hypersensitivity	Yes	Yes		Yes	WM-BP-SM
Germ cell mutagenicity	Category 1A	positive evidence from human epidemiological studies	Yes	Yes		Yes	SM-(WM-BP)
	Category 1B	Positive results from in vivo germ or somatic cell studies					
	Category 2	Concern for human due to somatic cell mutagenicity or genotoxicity					
Carcinogenicity	Category 1A	known to have carcinogenic potential for humans	Yes	Yes		Yes	SM-(WM-BP)
	Category 1B	presumed to have carcinogenic potential for humans					
	Category 2	Suspected human carcinogens					

Hazard classes based on health criteria	Hazard category		Whole mixture tests	Bridging principles	Concentration addition	Summation method/conc. limits	Application order
	Summarised Annex 1, Reg. (EC) No. 1272/2008		Based on Kortenkamp et al., 2009				
Reproductive toxicity	Category 1A	Known human reproductive toxicant	Yes	Yes		Yes	SM-(WM-BP)
	Category 1B	Presumed human reproductive toxicant					
	Category 2	Suspected human reproductive toxicant					
Specific target organ toxicity - single exposure	Category 1	Substances that have produced or are presumed to produce significant toxicity in humans	Yes	Yes	Yes		WM-BP-SM
	Category 2	Substances that can be presumed to have the potential to be harmful to human health					
	Category 3	Transient target organ effects					
Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure	Category 1	Substances that have produced or can be presumed to produce significant toxicity in humans following repeated exposure.	Yes	Yes	Yes		WM-BP-SM
	Category 2	Substances that can be presumed to be harmful to human health					
Aspiration hazard	Category 1	Substances known or regarded to cause human aspiration toxicity hazards	Yes	Yes		Yes	WM-BP-SM

CA: concentration addition, WM: Data from whole mixture tests; BP: application of bridging principles; SM: summation method or concentration limits for already classified ingredients.

Table 4: Environmental hazard classes and hazard categories according to Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 and mixture classification approaches as summarised in Kortenkamp et al. (2009).

Hazard classes based on environmental criteria	Hazard category		Whole mixture tests	Bridging principles	Concentration addition	Summation method/conc. limits	Application order
	Summarised Annex 1, Reg. (EC) No. 1272/2008		Based on Kortenkamp et al., 2009				
Aquatic hazard - Acute toxic	Category 1	LC ₅₀ for fish, EC ₅₀ for crustacea and/or ErC ₅₀ for algae ≤ 1mg/L	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	WM-BP-SM-CA
Aquatic hazard - Chronic toxic	Category 1	LC ₅₀ fish, EC ₅₀ crustacea and/or ErC ₅₀ algae ≤ 1mg/L and substance is not readily biodegradable and/or BCF ≥ 500				Yes	SM
	Category 2	LC ₅₀ fish, EC ₅₀ crustacea and/or ErC ₅₀ algae 1 to ≤ 10 mg/L and substance is not readily biodegradable and/or BCF ≥ 500, unless NOECs are > 1 mg/L					
	Category 3	LC ₅₀ fish, EC ₅₀ crustacea and/or ErC ₅₀ algae >10 to ≤ 100 mg/L and substance is not readily biodegradable and/or BCF ≥ 500, unless NOECs are > 1 mg/L					
	Category 4	Safety net classification – data does not allow classification, but there are nevertheless concerns					

CA: concentration addition, WM: Data from whole mixture tests; BP: application of bridging principles; SM: summation method or concentration limits for already classified ingredients.

For substances which have been classified as hazardous for aquatic environment (acute or chronic category 1, respectively), substance specific multiplying factors (M-factors) instead of specific concentration limits shall be applied. The M-factor is applied to the concentration of the classified substance (hazardous to the aquatic ecosystem), in the following the classification of the mixture is based on the summation method (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008, Article 2.34). Cut off criteria are also defined for aquatic hazards and lead to classifications of the mixture if a classified component has content of more than 0,1% (acute or chronic category 1), or 1% (chronic category 2-4) (Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008, Annex 1, Table 1.1).

In summary, the classification of mixtures is often based on summation methods, but also uses the more conservative concentration addition approach, which is in line with scientific findings (see 2.3; Backhaus et al., 2004; Kortenkamp et al., 2009). The CLP regulation is one of the few regulations within the EU providing guidance how to assess the hazard of chemical mixtures. Depending on the available data and on the properties of the components of a mixture, four methods are provided: whole mixture approach, bridging principles, summation method, and concentration addition (JRC, 2014). According to Kortenkamp et al. (2009), the classification in dependence of the relative amount of already classified components (summation method) reveals, in some cases, a risk for an underestimation of the total toxicity of the mixture, which could be avoided by a change of generic concentration limits. Furthermore, only the whole mixture approach reflects potential interactions of components of a mixture. The summation method and the concentration addition approach are simplified approaches which allow a rapid classification, but cannot account for potential synergistic or antagonistic effects. Thus, the CLP Regulation requires to take known synergistic or antagonistic into account, but does not give guidance how this should be done.

3.1.2. Plant protection products

Plant protection products (PPPs) are currently regulated by Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009 of the European Commission, which lays down rules on the evaluation, authorisation and placing PPPs on the market to ensure a high level of protection of human, animal health and the environment. This regulation allows a harmonised and efficient authorisation of PPPs within the EU and replaced the previous Council Directive 91/414/EEC in December 2009.

PPPs are formulated products (intentional mixtures), which are intended to (i) protect plants or plant products against all harmful organisms, (ii) influence the life processes of plants (such as the regulation of their growth except of nutrients), (iii) preserve plant products, or (iv) destroy undesired plants or parts of plants. They are designed to protect crops, desirable or useful plants and are primarily used in agriculture, but also in private gardens. PPPs are usually mixtures containing one or several active substances with a general or a specific action against harmful organisms. They may also contain additional components such as 'safeners' to reduce phytotoxic effects on plants to be protected, 'synergists' showing no or weak activity but leading to an enhanced activity to the active substance of the PPP, 'adjuvants' to increase the efficiency of an PPP or substances which are neither active substances nor safeners or synergists called 'co-formulants'.

Within the EU, PPPs are authorised in a two tier procedure: In the first stage, the safety of each active substance used within a PPP is evaluated in a peer review program between Member states and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), which leads to an approval or non-approval at the European level by the European Commission. In a second stage, the Member States of the EU evaluate and authorise the PPP at the national level with mutual recognition in zones with

comparable agricultural conditions. In this procedure, data requirements for the approval of substances and the authorisation of PPPs are laid down by two different Regulations, Regulation (EU) No. 283/2013 for active substances and Regulation (EU) No. 284/2013 for the formulated plant protection product. These data build the basis for the extensive risk assessment with regard to human, animal and environmental health in course of the authorisation of PPPs.

Concerning mixture risk assessment Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009 requests that PPPs and their residues “[...] shall have no immediate or delayed harmful effect on human health, including that of vulnerable groups, or animal health, directly or through drinking water [...], food, feed or air, or consequences in the workplace or through other indirect effects, taking into account known cumulative and synergistic effects where the scientific methods accepted by the Authority to assess such effects are available”. The report of JRC (2014) correctly assessed that it is not clarified if this statement also refers to the environmental health, as this is not mentioned explicitly. Furthermore, for the authorisation of PPPs interactions between active substances, safeners, synergists and co-formulants shall be taken into account (Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009, Article 29). This regulation therefore clearly requires taking interactions within the formulated product as well as direct and indirect cumulative and synergistic effects through different exposure pathways into account. However, it is also indicated that accepted scientific methods for the assessment of these effects have to be available, which is rarely the case. Thus, no general framework on how to assess and account for mixtures and potential interactions of PPPs exists.

With regard to the approval of active substances Regulation (EU) No. 283/2013 defines the data requirements for active substances in accordance with Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009. In order to approve the active substance and put them on the market or use them in PPPs, the applicant has to provide a dataset on the (i) identity of the active substance, (ii) physical and chemical properties of the active substance, (iii) further information in on the active substance, (iv) analytical methods, (v) toxicological and metabolism studies, (vi) residues in or on treated products, food and feed, (vii) fate and behavior in the environment, (viii) ecotoxicological studies, (ix) literature data (peer reviewed open literature on the active substance), and (x) a proposal for the classification and labelling based on Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008. Regulation (EU) No. 283/2013 requires accounting for “[...] any possible cumulative exposure due to different uses of the same substance [...]” for the proposal of toxicological reference values and maximum residue values if the active substance is simultaneously used as biocide or in veterinary medicine. Furthermore, sufficient information should be given on the active substance, safeners, synergist and other components as well as on other PPPs containing the active substance to permit “[...] a cumulative risk assessment deriving from exposure to more than one active substance [...]” for consumer exposures and “to permit an estimation of the exposure to operators, workers, residents and bystanders [...]”, where relevant. Thus, supplementary studies on mixture effects shall be conducted on the active substance, where necessary (Regulation (EU) No. 283/2013, 5.8.2 (f)). In conclusion, already for the approval of active substances the cumulative exposure to more than one active substance and cumulative exposures considering “[...] residues arising from sources other than current plant protection uses of active substances [...]” shall be taken into account, if this is considered as relevant. However, no criteria are defined at which concentrations other residues are considered as relevant, supporting the presumption that it is subject to expert knowledge.

Regulation (EU) No. 284/2013 is the counterpart to Regulation (EU) No. 283/2013 and sets the data requirements for PPPs. Thus, the required data set is similar to those for active substances (see

above) but considers the formulated product. However, additional information on technical properties of PPPs, data on application and efficacy is required, but toxicological studies focus on acute tests with the formulated product only. In this respect, JRC (2014) has expressed concerns because formulated products often include additional components which increase bioavailability and toxicity of the active substances, which is not assessed for chronic effects. To evaluate foreseeable risks any information on harmful effects of the PPP on human and animal health or unacceptable effects on the environment “[...] shall be included as well as known and expected cumulative and synergistic effects”. Cumulative and synergistic effects of combined exposures have to be taken into account when the PPP “[...] product label includes requirements for use of the plant protection product with other plant protection products or with adjuvants as a tank mix [...]”. Thus, sufficient information should be given on the PPP to permit “[...] a cumulative risk assessment deriving from exposure to more than one active substance [...]” for acute and chronic exposure of consumer, operators, workers, residents and bystanders, where relevant. Therefore, information on the exposure extent to the active substances as well as on toxicologically relevant compounds in the PPP is required. The evaluation shall be based on suitable calculation models considering the different exposure scenarios of operators, workers, residents and bystanders as well as the proposed conditions of use and agricultural practices. Also for formulated PPPs risks from combined exposures shall be taken into account, if they are expected and if they are intended to be applied with other PPPs or adjuvants or if combined effects are expected or known. However, no guidance on the implementation is provided.

Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009 is also linked to the Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005, on maximum residue levels (MRLs) of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin. This Regulation concerns the public health and establishes MRLs by taking data on toxicology, food consumption and residues on food or feed into account. The MRL is the highest tolerable level of pesticide residues on food or feed and is a limit set at the EU level. The setting of MRLs for plants and plant products are, among others, a requirement for the authorisation of PPPs (Regulation (EC) No. 1107/2009; Article 29). Many activities regarding combined exposures and potential combined effects of substances or products refer to the requirements of Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005. This is because Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005 clearly states the importance “[...] to carry out further work to develop a methodology to take into account cumulative and synergistic effects” (Recital 6). It further stipulates to account for “[...] pesticide residues arising from sources other than current plant protection uses of active substances, and their known cumulative and synergistic effects, if appropriate methods are available” (Article 14). Thus, the MRL Regulation explicitly requires taking mixture toxicity into account. In addition, Article 36 requires preparing and developing legislation and technical guidelines on pesticide residues for the assessment of aggregated, cumulative and synergistic effects. This is a very important statement as in many legislative requirements of various regulations the consideration of potential combined effects is requested, however, only under the prerequisite that appropriate methods are available.

In the following, EFSA intensified efforts to develop methods and organised, among other actions, a Scientific Colloquium on cumulative risk assessment of pesticides to human health (EFSA, 2006) and published a scientific opinion on new approaches to assess cumulative and synergistic risks from pesticides to human (EFSA, 2008). In 2009 EFSA published a guidance document for the risk assessment of birds and mammals, proposing a stepwise approach for the combined effect assessment. This approach considers mixtures of active substances and toxic co-formulants but does,

due to the lack of data for these organisms, not consider the toxicity of the formulated product (EFSA, 2009). However, such a guideline is missing for the risk assessment of humans.

It can be concluded that the reviewed regulations concerning PPPs stipulate to consider potential combined effects caused by components of formulated products or by combined exposures of substances or products. Thus, cumulative and synergistic effects have to be considered within the risk assessment of the authorisation process. However, this is often restricted by statements like “if appropriate methods are available”, or “where relevant” or “known and expected cumulative and synergistic effects” shall be considered. Thus, the bottleneck is the lack of available and accepted scientific methods, concrete guidelines how to assess and evaluate effect from mixtures and the knowledge which mixtures are hazardous and therefore relevant for a combine risk assessment. There is a need to (i) develop appropriate methods for the assessment of combined effects, (ii) to agree on these methods at least at the European level, (iii) systematically collect and process knowledge on combined effects, and (iv) develop guidelines for risk assessors in order to account for potential combined effects.

3.1.3. Biocidal products

Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council regulates the making available on the market and use of biocidal products. This regulation allows a harmonised authorisation of biocides within the EU and aims to protect human, animal and environmental health. It replaced the previous Directive 98/8/EC in September 2013.

Biocides are applied to protect humans, animals, materials or articles against harmful organisms like pests or bacteria. Thus, biocidal products are substances or mixtures containing active substances or micro-organisms intending to destroy, deter, render harmless, prevent action of or exert a controlling effect on any harmful organism by any means other than physical or mechanical action. As for PPPs, biocidal products are usually mixtures of substances, applied as formulated products containing beside active substances also co-formulants, diluents, carrier materials and stabilisers.

Biocides are authorised in a two-step procedure. Firstly, active substances have to be approved, before they can be used within a biocidal product. These substances are evaluated in a peer review procedure of the Member States and the ECHA. This leads to an approval and the implementation in a positive list or non-approval by the European Commission. In a second step, the Member States of the EU evaluate and authorise the biocidal product at the national level with the possibility of mutual recognition. In the new Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012, a union authorisation valid for all Member States for products with similar conditions of use in all Member States can be granted. This comprehensive regulation also defines the data requirements for active substances (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012, Annex II) and biocidal products (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012, Annex III), which built the basis for the risk assessment in order to safeguard human, animal and environmental health.

Also for the authorisation of biocidal products cumulative and synergistic effects shall be taken into account (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012, Article 19.2). In the data requirements of biocidal products a combined risk assessment is required for “*biocidal products that are intended to be authorized for use with other biocidal products, the risks to human health, animal health and the environment arising from the use of these product combinations shall be assessed*” (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012, Annex III, 8.5.4). For ecotoxicological studies, testing of the biocidal product may be necessary if synergistic effects are expected (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012, Annex III, 9.1). Comparable to the PPP authorisation process, biocidal product are mainly evaluated on effect data of the components

present in the formulated product and whole mixture studies are conducted for acute tests, only (JRC, 2014). In Annex VI on common principles for the evaluation of biocidal products a risk assessment “[...] associated with the relevant individual components of the biocidal product, taking into account any cumulative and synergistic effect” is required to ensure a high level of protection of human, animal and environmental health (3). Thus, “[...] the possibility of cumulative or synergistic effects shall also be taken into account” and “[...] further guidance on the scientific definitions and methodologies for the assessment of cumulative and synergistic effects” shall be developed and provided by Agencies in collaboration with the Commission, Member States and interested parties (Article 15). This part further summarises, that the overall risk of the biocidal product itself shall be assessed, also taking into account cumulative and synergistic effects (Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012, Article 53, Article 54).

Thus, Regulation (EU) No. 528/2012 explicitly requires accounting for cumulative and synergistic effects and even stipulates collaboration between Agencies, Member States and the European Commission to develop and provide guidance. As for PPP, it lacks a general approach for the risk assessment of mixture, even though a legal mandate for the implementation of a combined risk assessment exists. However, the ECHA published several guidance documents on the biocides legislation. The guidance on the biocidal products regulation concerning the risk assessment of human health provides a tiered approach to account for risks exerted by multiple substances within a single biocidal product (ECHA, 2015), which is a first important step. However, so far it is not clear when combined exposure to multiple chemicals needs to be performed for biocidal active substances (ECHA, 2015).

3.1.4. Medicinal products for human use

Pharmaceuticals are highly regulated by several legislative acts, to place medicinal products for human use on the European market a marketing authorisation is required. Directive 2001/83/EC is currently regulating the marketing of medical products for humans and aims to reduce the discrepancies between national provisions of the Member States in order to enable the trade of medicinal products within the EU. Despite regulating the production, distributions and use of medicinal products Directive 2001/83/EC also aims to safeguard public health by setting criteria on quality, safety and efficacy.

The benefit of medicinal products is often dose dependent, low doses might have no beneficial effects whereas too high doses might cause severe adverse reactions. Furthermore, un-intended adverse side effects are often inevitably and have to be accepted. Therefore, the *“harmfulness and therapeutic efficacy can only be examined in relation to each other and have only a relative significance depending on the progress of scientific knowledge and the use for which the medicinal product is intended”* (Recital 7). Thus, for authorisation of marketing the applicant must provide documents that *“demonstrate that potential risks are outweighed by the therapeutic efficacy of the product”* (Recital 7). As a result the marketing authorisation is based on a risk-benefit approach, which is by definition *“an evaluation of the positive therapeutic effects of the medicinal product in relation to the risks [...] to the quality, safety or efficacy of the medicinal product as regards patients' health or public health”* as well as *“any risk of undesirable effects on the environment”* (Article 1, 28). According to Article 26, the marketing authorisation shall be refused if *“(a) the risk-benefit balance is not considered to be favourable; or (b) its therapeutic efficacy is insufficiently substantiated by the applicant; or (c) its qualitative and quantitative composition is not as declared”*.

The Directive 2001/83/EC differentiates between the human risk to patients and to public health, but also considers undesirable effects to the environment. Toxicity studies are based on the active substance, the combination of all included active substances or the final product and comprise tests on single-dose toxicity, repeat-dose toxicity, genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, reproductive and developmental toxicity as well as local tolerance studies (Annex 1, Part 1, 4.2.3). With regard to human health, therapeutic uses and potential undesirable pharmaco-dynamic effects of the active substances are tested, and interactions of combined active substances or different medicinal products are determined (Annex 1, Part 1, 4.2.1). Human toxicity is assessed as a whole and assessment studies on intended and unintended interactions of substances: 1) within one medical product, 2) with substances of other medicinal products, and 3) with alcohol, tobacco and other food are taken into account (JRC, 2014).

The impact on the environment shall be assessed on a case-by case basis and specific arrangements can be applied to reduce the impact (Article 8, 3ca). The European Medicine Agency (EMA) provides a guideline for the environmental risk assessment of medicinal products for human use (EMA, 2006). Even though medical products for human use are typically intended mixtures of different substances which are excreted and end up in ecosystems, neither the Directive 2001/83/EC nor the guidance documents (EMA, 2016) have specific requirements regarding the assessment of mixture toxicology.

3.1.5. Veterinary medicinal products

The Directive 2001/82/EC on veterinary medicinal products has been developed in parallel to Directive 2001/83/EC on medical products for humans, therefore, both directives share common approaches and text passages. The marketing of veterinary medicinal products has to be authorised and is, due to its potential relevance for food production, of high interest. The application of veterinary medicinal products may influence the quality of food with regard to residues in food and feed resulting in potential adverse effects on humans, non-target organisms or the environment.

For this purpose, Directive 2001/82/EC rules the production and distribution of veterinary medicinal products, with the aim to safeguard public health (Recital 2). Just as for medicinal products for humans the *“harmfulness and therapeutic efficacy can be examined only in relation to one another”* and it has to be demonstrated *“that potential hazards are outweighed by the benefits due to efficacy”* otherwise the application is rejected (Recital 11). Thus, the marketing authorisation is based on a risk-benefit approach. For authorisation of veterinary medical products quality, safety and efficacy criteria are set and risks towards animal health, human health and undesirable effect on the environment are considered (Title I, Article 1.19). The requirements for safety and residue tests, pre-clinical and clinical trials and efficacy tests for veterinary medicinal products are laid down in Annex I to the Directive. Toxicity and ecotoxicity studies have to be conducted for the product, its active substances and relevant metabolites, clarifying the potential toxicity i) under the proposed use in animals (target animal), ii) to man due to residues of the veterinary medicinal product in foodstuff, iii) to human beings due to a direct contact while administration to the animal, and iv) to the environment as a result of the application to target animals (Annex 1, Title 1, Part 3, Chapter 1). A marketing authorisation for veterinary medicinal products intended for food producing species is only granted, if the active substance or substances they contain are listed in Regulation (EC) No. 470/2009 on residue limits of pharmacologically active substances in foodstuffs of animal origin (Kortenkamp et al., 2009).

Interactions with other medicinal products or feed additives have to be considered in the clinical try (Annex 1, Title 1, Part 4, Chapter III), but play a minor role compared to the assessments conducted for medicinal products intended for human use (Kortenkamp, et al., 2009). In contrast, for veterinary medicinal products clear requirements for the assessment of risks towards the environment are set (Annex 1, Title 1, Part 3, Chapter 1, Section 6). In a first obligatory phase the exposure of the environment shall be assessed under the consideration of target animal species, use pattern, administration method, possible excretion of the product its active substances and relevant metabolites as well as disposal of unused products. The second phase, shall investigate the fate and effects of the products on particular ecosystems, considering physical/chemical, pharmacological and toxicological properties. However, the assessment of mixture toxicity due to the simultaneous occurrence of residues from different veterinary medicinal products, pharmaceutical or pesticides is not established by legislation.

In summary, veterinary medicinal products are typically mixtures and their risks towards target animals, humans and the environment are considered as a whole. Interactions with other veterinary medicinal products are only considered within the target animal, but not for the joint occurrence of different residues in the environment.

3.1.6. Cosmetic products

Cosmetics are currently regulated under Regulation (EC) No. 1223/2009 of the EU, which replaced the previous Directive 76/768/EEC and was fully applicable from July 2013. The Regulation (EC) No. 1223/2009 sets harmonised rules for cosmetic products for the internal European market and aims to ensure a high level of human health protection (Recital 4). The regulation explicitly relates to cosmetics and not to biocidal or medical products and does not include products which need to be inhaled, injected or implemented in the body. Since 2013 the legislation prohibits animal testing of finished cosmetic products (Recital 41) and promotes the use of alternative methods, by prohibiting the marketing of cosmetics containing ingredients which *“have been the subject of animal testing using a method other than an alternative method”* (Article 18).

As cosmetic products are typically intended mixtures, the term mixture is here defined in the same meaning as the term preparation and refers to a mixture or solution of at least two substances. In contrast to plant protection products and biocidal products, cosmetic products are intended to be in contact with parts of the human body (epidermis, hair, nail, lips, teeth, membranes...) for aesthetical reasons such as good appearance and body odour. Therefore, substances classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic or toxic for reproduction (category 1A, 1B and 2, based on Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008) are prohibited in cosmetic products (Recital 32). In case the Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS) evaluated the use of category 2 substances in cosmetics as safe they may be used (SCCS, 2016). As thousands of cosmetic products are on the market, including only a limited number of substances, the safety of cosmetic products is based on the safety of the ingredients, which reduces unnecessary testing (SCCS, 2016).

The safety assessment for cosmetic products has to be conducted under the assumption of normal and reasonable use (Article 3) and ensures that *“the intended use of the cosmetic product and the systematic exposure to the individual ingredients in a final formulation are taken into account”* (Article 10). For a reasonable safety assessment, a weight-of evidence approach shall be used for the review of existing data. Furthermore, the safety report for the cosmetic products shall be kept up to date, also implementing data generated subsequent to the placing on the market.

The safety assessment itself is described in Annex I Part 8 of Regulation (EC) No. 1223/2009, guidance is given by “The SCCS notes of guidance for the testing of cosmetic ingredients and their safety evaluation” (SCCS, 2016). The assessment requires to consider “all significant routes of absorption”, systemic effects and bases the risk characterisation on the margin of safety (MoS) calculated from no observed adverse effect levels (NOAEL) and systemic exposure doses (SED) (SCCS, 2016). The regulation requests to particularly consider “any possible impacts on the toxicological profile due to” particle sizes, impurities and interaction of substance. However, it is presumably referred to interactions of substances within one cosmetic product and not to substances included in different products, which might be used simultaneously. In general, Regulation (EC) No. 1223/2009 deals with cosmetic products as a whole and not with specific substances (Kortenkamp et al., 2009). Thus, potential cumulative and synergistic effects are not mentioned and the consideration of mixture effects is not explicitly required. Indications of potential co-exposure to several cosmetic products are rare and no guidance on how to assess and account for interactions of substances exists.

3.1.7. Food law

General principles and requirements for food law and food safety are regulated under Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002. This Regulation “provides the basis for the assurance of a high level of protection of human health and consumers' interest [...], whilst ensuring the effective functioning of the internal market”. It further defines “common principles and responsibilities [...] in matters of food and feed safety” and legally establishes the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the responsible agency for evaluating risks associated with the food chain. According to article 14 of Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002, unsafe food shall not be placed on the market, requiring, amongst others, to determine whether probable cumulative toxic effects might be injurious to health. No further explanation for the implementation of this requirement is provided. Several legislations in the field of food and feed refer to the general principles of the food law, thus, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 provides the legal basis for many specific legislations.

3.1.8. Food additives

Regulation (EC) No. 1333/2008 on food additives replaced the previous Directive 89/107/EEC and entered into force on 20 January 2009. This regulation shall harmonise the use of food additives, which are substances that are not normally consumed but are added for technological purpose (e.g. for preservation). Food enzymes and food flavours are not included under the Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 and are regulated in individual legislations (Regulation (EC) No. 1332/2008; Regulation (EC) No. 1334/2008).

The legislation on food additives aims at “ensuring a high level of protection of human health and a high level of consumer protection [...], taking into account, where appropriate, the protection of the environment” (Article 1). Food additives may be approved for the use in food, if i) they does not “pose a safety concern to the health of the consumer”, ii) there is a technological need for the use, iii) “its use does not mislead the consumer”, and iv) “where relevant, other legitimate factors, including environmental factors” are met (Article 6). Food additives shall not pose a safety concern to consumer health, thus, for approval of food additives a safety assessment has to be conducted by EFSA. The safety assessment of food additives are based on acceptable daily intake (ADI) values, which are permitted use levels, considered to be safe if not exceeded (Kortenkamp et al., 2009). If necessary, maximum use levels are defined in Annex II (Community list of food additives approved for use in foods and conditions of use) or Annex III (Community list of food additives approved for

use in food additives, food enzymes and food flavourings, and their conditions of use) of Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008.

With regard to the assessment of mixture toxicity, the new legislation on food additives (Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008) has taken a step back rather than forward. The previous Directive 89/107/EEC clearly required to assess the possible harmful effects of a food additive or derivatives, by stating that *“any cumulative, synergistic or potentiating effect of its use”* shall be taken into account. In Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 no requirements for evaluating mixture toxicity or potential interactions of substances used as food additives are laid down. The safe use of food additives shall be ensured by establishing maximum use levels, taking account *“any acceptable daily intake, [...], established for the food additive and the probable daily intake of it from all sources”*. This implies to take potential intake of food additives from other sources into account. Thus, the safety assessment of food additives is based on the assumption that scientifically determined ADI values ensure a safe use, the assessment of mixture toxicity is not legally required but also not excluded (Kortenkamp, et al. 2009)

3.1.9. Additives for use in animal nutrition

Regulation (EC) No. 1831/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council regulates the procedure for authorising the placing on the market and use of feed additives. This regulation shall enable an effective functioning of the internal market whilst ensuring *“a high level of protection of human health, animal health and welfare, environment and users' and consumers' interests in relation to feed additives”* (Article 1). Before the application of feed additives within the EU, a harmonised scientific assessment of the safety has to be conducted by EFSA (Recital 14). Feed additives shall favourably affect the characteristics of feed, animal products and shall satisfy nutritional needs of animals. In case of adverse effects on animal health, human health or the environment or if feed additives are presented in a misleading manner to the consumer or user, an authorisation shall be refused (Article 5). For an authorisation, EFSA shall propose a MRL in the relevant food stuff, if this is necessary for the protection of consumers. As feed additives might be also mixtures of components, the Regulation (EC) No. 1831/2003 should *“cover mixtures of additives sold to the end-user, and the marketing and use of those mixtures should comply with the conditions laid down in the authorisation of each single additive”* (Recital 9). However, Regulation (EC) No. 1831/2003 does not set specific requirements to take potential hazards or risk from mixture toxicity due to simultaneous exposures of different feed additives or other chemical substances into account. No criteria for the safety assessment of feed additives are set. The implementation of Regulation (EC) No. 1831/2003 is laid down in Regulation (EC) No. 429/2008, setting rules for the applications, assessment and authorisation of feed additives. Also, requirements for studies concerning the safety of use for target species, users/workers and the environment as well as residue studies and studies concerning the efficacy of the additive are defined here (Annex III). For additives with multiple components, Regulation (EC) No. 429/2008 requires a separate assessment of each component for consumer safety and the consideration of the cumulative effect. Alternatively, the complete mixture shall be assessed (Annex II). Also here, no further guidance on the implementation of cumulative effect assessments is given. The general European food law (Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002) may apply, requiring the consideration of probable cumulative toxic effects in food safety assessment (Article 14, 4b). However, according to Kortenkamp et al., (2009) this cannot be interpreted as mandatory requirement in the feed additive Regulation.

In conclusion, the assessment of mixture toxicity for feed additives is not specifically required, however, adverse effects to animal and human health as well as the environment are not permitted.

3.1.10. Gaps in European Regulation

The reviewed European regulations dealing with the authorisation and classification of chemicals and the authorisation of plant protection, biocidal, medicinal and cosmetic products as well as additives for food and feed are mainly substance or product oriented. They usually consider single substances or intentional mixtures with known compositions. However, due to contaminations or simultaneous or sequential exposure to chemical substances or products unintentional mixtures may occur. These are hard to assess as their components are usually not known, composition might be complex, non-target screening is expensive and time consuming and thus data is lacking. Furthermore, hazard and risk of chemicals and pesticides is assessed based on their intentional uses for each regulatory sector separately, without taking other uses regulated in other sectors into account. There is no general framework for a systematic, comprehensive and integrated assessment of chemicals and mixture effects, which considers different routes of exposure and different product types (EC, 2012). Thus, chemicals and intentional mixtures are regulated isolated in the different regulatory sectors and no requirement for un-intentional or “coincidental” mixtures exists. Evan et al., (2016) showed that humans are co-exposed to chemicals regulated in different legislations and referred to studies revealing mixture effects of chemicals being regulated in different legislations. Thus, the chemical-by-chemical risk assessment within one legal sector cannot fully assess the risk of chemical substances, as risk profiles are overlapping (Evan et al., 2016). According to Bunke et al. (2014), a horizontal framework legislation might be required to overcome the product and sector related hazard and risk assessment and improve risk managing procedures. However, it is questionable whether a horizontal framework is scientifically, regulatory and politically feasible, as an overall risk assessment requires a sound data basis, a comprehensive knowledge on potential uses and exposure paths of chemical products and an all-encompassing assessment approach, which does not yet exist. It is especially of importance that all the regulations dealing with chemicals and pesticides are established to ensure a high level of protection for human, animal and environmental health. In order to achieve this objective, different exposure paths have to be considered and the total exposure and mixture effects have to be assessed. In consequence of Regulation (EC) No. 396/2009, the EU coordinates a multiannual pesticide control programme with the aim to provide data on pesticide residues in food available for European consumers (EFSA, 2015a). Therefore, the Member States, Iceland and Norway are required to collect and analyse samples of selected food products and pesticides and are obliged to provide the data to EFSA. EFSA summarises the results in the annual report on pesticide residues in food. Additionally, Member States set up national control programmes, usually focussing on product groups which are expected to exceed legal limits (EFSA, 2013d). This information builds the basis for future monitoring activities and provides important data for exposure and risk assessments, also with regard to most common multiple residues from different products. First informatics approaches have been developed, using public available data on prevalence and distribution of selected chemicals to help prioritising chemical combinations for further testing (Gabb and Blake, 2016). Such approaches are of special interest as it is impractical to test all possible combinations of chemicals human might be exposed to. Also, large-scale population studies on blood and urine samples such as the German Environmental Survey (GerES), or the National Report on Human Exposure to Environmental Chemicals (NHANES) provide important information on realistic chemical exposures of the human population (Becker et al., 2002; Becker et al., 2003; Woodruff et al., 2011;

CDC, 2015). The monitoring data of these large-scale studies is important information for chemical risk assessment, however, it needs to be processed and summarised in well organised public available databases to support science and decision making of risk assessors and risk managers.

In summary, most reviewed regulations, except of the more substance oriented REACH Regulation, stipulate to consider mixture toxicity or cumulative and synergistic effects. For the classification and labelling of chemicals (CLP), the authorisation of plant protection and biocidal products as well as for food (general food law) the assessment of mixture toxicity is explicitly required and legally binding. However, mixture toxicity is not specifically addressed in the regulations of food and feed additives, veterinary medicinal products and cosmetics. The CLP Regulation is one of the few regulations providing guidance on how the hazard of mixtures shall be assessed, also without the necessity of additional animal testing. However, it does not consider exposure information, which would be required for a complete risk assessment. A guidance document for a risk assessment accounting for mixture toxicity only exists for biocidal products (ECHA, 2015).

Most of the reviewed regulations assess the hazard and risk of intentional mixtures as if they were present in isolation (Kortenkamp et al., 2009), solely for human medicine interactions with other medicinal products and food are taken into account. In regulations in which assessment of mixture toxicity is required, restrictions are made by statements like “if appropriate methods are available”, “where relevant” or “known and expected cumulative and synergistic effects” shall be considered. Therefore, a clear mandate to proof if substances in a mixture have interactions, leading to combined effects, is lacking. As a result, it is highly dependent on expert knowledge and the public availability of toxicity data if the combined toxicity of a mixture is considered or not. The MRL Regulation (Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005) clearly requires developing new methodologies to be able to account for cumulative and synergistic effects, which would be the first step to enable a sound risk assessment of mixtures. Due to the lack of available methods for the assessment of mixture effects, concrete guidelines how to evaluate effects from mixtures are missing. Also, existing knowledge on combined effects of hazardous mixtures, being relevant for a combined risk assessment, is not systematically documented, which would simplify the research of regulators and risk managers. A clear legal mandate to take mixture toxicity into account in all regulatory sectors dealing with chemicals is needed to improve the risk assessment of mixtures and ensure human health and protect the environment (Kortenkamp et al., 2009).

3.2. Considerations of chemical mixtures of non- EU countries

The main goal of the project is to develop a common approach for the risk assessment of mixtures and take important steps towards a harmonised approach for the risk assessment of mixtures. In order to get a comprehensive overview on procedures for risk assessment of chemicals it is important to consider legislative requirements and approaches of countries apart from Europe.

The aim of this section is to provide an overview on how non-EU countries conduct risk assessment of chemical substances also with regard to the assessment of mixture toxicity. Therefore, six countries with presumably different regulatory approaches of the risk assessment have been selected and representatives of national agencies or researchers, being familiar with the current legislation and their implementation, have been asked to support this report. For each country, a general overview on the risk assessment of chemical substances and products is given also with regard to potential requirements on the risk assessment of mixture effects.

The following sections are based on the public available information in English and the information given by cooperating partners. For Brasil, Korea and Japan information was limited and therefore the sections might not cover all regulatory processes of these countries.

3.2.1. Australia

Chemicals in Australia are grouped into three broad categories: i) industrial chemicals, ii) agricultural and veterinary chemicals and, iii) therapeutic goods for human health. Industrial chemicals are regulated by National Industrial Chemicals Notification and Assessment Scheme (NICNAS). Both human health and agricultural and veterinary chemicals are regulated by distinct authorities, the Therapeutics Goods Administration (TGA) and Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority (APVMA) respectively. Both authorities take a risk based approach to evaluation that includes consideration of each products formulation against the criteria of human health. The APVMA also considers product formulations for animal and environmental safety.

Industrial Chemicals:

NICNAS aids in the protection of the Australian people and the environment by assessing potential risks to health and the environment associated with the importation, manufacture and use of chemicals and providing information to promote their safe use (Office of Parliamentary Counsel, 2015). The Industrial Chemicals Act 1989 regulates single ingredient chemicals, effectively raw materials for industrial processes or components of subsequent products. Substances and products used as pesticides, veterinary chemicals, medicine, food or food additives are outside the scope of NICNAS and are regulated under the “Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals Code Act 1994”, the “Therapeutic Goods Act 1989” and the “Food Standards Australia New Zealand Act 1991” (Office of Parliamentary Counsel, 2015).

Under the frame of NICNAS, the Australian Inventory of Chemical Substances (AICS) is maintained. The AICS is a database, containing all industrial chemicals in use in Australia. Chemicals that are not listed must be notified and assessed before manufacturing or importing. The data requirements depend on the introduced volumes and tests have to be conducted according to OECD guidelines, similar to the REACH approach in Europe (Hislop, 2014). For a new chemical the manufacturer or importer has to provide information on chemical identity, use and exposure details, physico-chemical properties, health and environmental effects data and additional data for some specific uses (NICNAS, 2016a). Since 2012, a classification in accordance with the GHS is required (NICNAS, 2016b). The risk assessment is conducted by the Australian authorities, occupational and public health is assessed by the Department of Health and the environmental health by the Department of the Environment. The risk assessment covers: i) hazard identification, ii) hazard assessment, incorporating the dose-response relationship, iii) exposure assessment, iv) risk characterisation, however, the degree of risk assessment varies depending on the type of new chemical notification (NICNAS, 2016c). As REACH, the Industrial Chemicals Act 1989 of Australia is substance oriented and does not require considering mixture effects. For industrial products containing several components individual substances are considered (ChemSafefetyPro, 2016).

Agricultural and veterinary chemicals

The “Agricultural and Veterinary Chemicals Code Act 1994” (Office of Parliamentary Counsel, 2016a) is the legal basis for registration and control of agricultural and veterinary chemicals. It requires the registration of agricultural and veterinary chemicals at the APVMA before being used or introduced

to Australia. Safety and efficacy of these products are evaluated to protect human, animal and environmental health (APVMA, 2016a). For the approval of “*new active constituents, registration of agricultural chemical products, variation of currently registered agricultural chemical products, or permits to use agricultural chemical products*” of the manufacturer or importer has to provide toxicological data, conducted in accordance with the OECD Guidelines (APVMA, 2016b). A comprehensive data set for the assessment of the toxicology of active constituents and the product is required, which also comprises the assessment of the toxicity of mixtures. The Australian laws clearly require that “*toxicity studies should be performed with the formulated product [...] to investigate the possibility of synergism or potentiation*” (APVMA, 2016b). This applies for products with two or more active constituents in a novel combination with no established hazard profile. A scientific argument has to be provided, if the data is lacking. It is required to clarify toxicological significance in additional tests, if synergism or potentiation is found (APVMA, 2016b). After evaluation agricultural and veterinary products are approved for specific purposes and uses.

Therapeutic goods

The “Therapeutic Goods Act 1989” sets out the legal requirements for the introduction and supply of therapeutic goods in Australia (Office of Parliamentary Counsel, 2016b). The TGA is the authority evaluating, by carefully considering benefits and risks, any product for which therapeutic claims are made. The TGA aims to protect and advance public health and identifies, assesses and evaluates the risks posed by therapeutic goods. For this purpose, risks are monitored and reviewed over time, in case risks are posed risk mitigation measures are applied (TGA, 2011). As all medicines carry a risk of causing adverse health effects, risks have to be compared to the evidenced benefits (TGA, 2016). Furthermore, potential interactions with other medicinal products or consumables (e.g. alcohol, tobacco, foodstuffs), which may affect the action of the product, have to be considered (Office of Parliamentary Counsel, 2016c).

Food Standards

The “Australia New Zealand Food Standards Act 1991” aims to “*ensure a high standard of public health protection throughout Australia and New Zealand*” by setting food standards for Australia and New Zealand (Office of Parliamentary Counsel, 2016d). The “Food Standards Australia New Zealand” (FSANZ) sets standards related to the composition, labelling, safe handling and primary production of food (FSANZ, 2009). Further, FSANZ conducts risk analysis, involving hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment and risk characterisation, to identify, assess and manage food-related risks (FSANZ, 2013). Food risks can result from microbiological, physical and chemical factors. Chemical risk factors include residues from agricultural or veterinary chemicals applied while primary production (FSANZ, 2009). The hazard characterisation focuses on the determination of a safe level of exposure and establishes “health-based guidance value” (HBGV), reflecting a safe exposure level, not leading to health risks. The HBGVs are based on traditional toxicity studies of single chemical compounds and are commonly established for food additives or agricultural and veterinary chemical residues and for contaminants (FSANZ, 2013). In this context, the assessment of mixture toxicity or the consideration of an aggregated or cumulative exposure is not mentioned and might not be conducted.

Summary

All agencies consider the synergistic effects of mixtures to a degree in their evaluations, most prominently in the APVMA and TGA. New chemical products considered by these agencies require

extensive human health studies to determine the actual effect of the mixtures use. For the APVMA this can include studies showing the levels of acute oral/dermal/inhalation toxicity, chronic effects, carcinogenicity, absorption and metabolism.

The TGA and APVMA also consider the combined effects of products, resulting in prohibitions on the use of one product with another primarily. The APVMA also considers the use of products in combination if it is recommended on the label. The label defines the circumstances of use the APVMA considers, use not in accordance with the label is prohibited. The APVMA considers the health and environmental effects of the two products when used in combination.

Chemical mixtures more generally within the environment are not expressly considered. Where specific instances for concern for a chemical are identified the APVMA, NICNAS or TGA have the ability to respond appropriately. Concerns may be identified through academic or community monitoring, international decisions or through ad hoc government monitoring. This is not specifically mixture based activity, but does seek to inform government action where synergistic properties are expected.

Australian food monitoring and residue limits (set through Food Standards regulation) are more structured but again are focussed on single chemical levels.

One of the factors that complicates chemical mixture regulation, either in tank (product to product) or in the environment more generally, is this responsibility for use (and consequence of use) is one of the Australian states and territories. This results in eight jurisdictions with differing approaches and scales of responsibility.

3.2.2. *Brasil*

According to Federal Decree 2657/1998, the term “chemical” refers to chemical elements, compounds, and mixtures thereof, whether natural or synthetic. Brasil has several regulatory schemes to regulate some specific applications and uses of chemicals, such as pesticides, disinfectants, food additives, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, etc. There are also specific regulations for biological and aquatic products, biochemicals (e.g. amino acids, enzymes, pheromones) and for products that are considered atypical (e.g. copper, sulphur, mineral and vegetal oils) (Hirata, 2006). All of them have less registration requirements than a regular chemical pesticide. Different Brazilian authorities are in charge of chemicals, depending on the relevant use of the chemicals:

1. Food, drugs and consumer products (cosmetics, health related products and sanitation products, cleaning products, pesticides, disinfectants) – Ministry of Health (ANVISA).
2. Fertilisers, herbicides, agriculture commodities, agriculture related products and veterinarian products – Ministry of Agriculture (MAPA).
3. Herbicides and chemicals not controlled by MAPA, mainly for forestry or timber products – Ministry of the Environment (IBAMA).
4. Chemicals used as raw-material (active ingredients) for the manufacturing of the products listed above shall follow specific rules of each one of the respective agencies. The Brazilian Association of Technical Ruling (ABNT) provides guidance for the technical rules on handling and uses of such chemicals, under the perspective of the Safety and Health Regulation and Environmental Rules (Barbosa, 2013).

Despite the existence of these regulations for specific uses, a large set of substances, particularly those used in industrial processes, are not covered by this laws. For this reason the Brazilian Ministry

of the Environment (IBAMA) has proposed a legislation that would establish an expansive chemical regulatory regime consisting of registration and reporting requirements, substance risk assessments, and risk management measures including potential restrictions on the production, import and use of substances (Kadas and Fraker, 2016). The proposed legislation will regulate “industrial chemical substance”, defined as “*a chemical element and its compounds, in a natural state or obtained through a manufacturing process, including any additive necessary to preserve its stability and any impurity that derives from the process used, but excluding any solvent that can be separated without affecting the substance’s stability or modifying its composition*” (IBAMA, 2016). Upon entry into force of the new act, all substances of commercial use will be covered, excluding substances which are governed by other regulations, such as:

- Radioactive chemical substances;
- Chemical substances in development or intended exclusively for research;
- Non-isolated reaction intermediaries, impurities, contaminants, and substances produced through unintentional reactions;
- Ores and their concentrates, and other rocks and minerals, except those that are chemically modified or that are composed of or contain substances classified as hazardous according to the GHS criteria;
- Metals and alloys in forms used for structural purposes;
- Active ingredients of pesticides; and
- Active ingredients of human and veterinary medicines (Kadas and Fraker, 2016).

In the course of introduction of this legislation, a National Registry of Industrial Chemical Substances to collect information about covered substances will be established. Manufactured or imported products with volumes exceeding one ton or more per year will have to be registered. Therefore, substance names and CAS (chemical abstracts service) numbers, volumes of annual production or import, substance uses, and any applicable GHS hazard classification have to be provided by the company (Kadas and Fraker, 2016). For particular substances potentially causing risks to the environment and human health, lower threshold quantities may be established. In general, all manufactured or imported chemical substances as well as intentional mixtures have to be registered. So far it is not clear if constituents of imported products being intentional mixtures, would count toward the quantities subject to registration (Kadas and Fraker, 2016). The proposed legislation distinguished between mixtures and “finished products”, whereby the distinction between these categories is unclear. For the risk assessment, an interagency “Technical Committee on the Evaluation of Industrial Chemical Substances” will be formed, selecting substances from the registry and evaluating their environmental and health risks. The selection of the substances will be based on the following factors:

- Persistence, bioaccumulation or toxicity to the environment;
- Carcinogenicity, mutagenicity or toxicity to reproduction;
- Characteristics of endocrine disruptors, based on scientific evidence;
- Relevant potential for human and environmental exposure;
- Appearance in alerts, international agreements or conventions to which Brasil is a signatory; and
- Scientific evidence of serious effects on health or the environment not listed above, but of equivalent concern (Kadas and Fraker, 2016).

The proposed legislation lacks details on the prioritisation of candidate substances for risk assessments and does not provide guidance on risk management decisions; however, it forces manufacturers and importers of substances under assessment to submit information, studies, and safety data sheets to support the risk assessment (Kadas and Fraker, 2016). The main impact of the proposed legislation will fall on the chemical industry, but it may also incentive other countries in Latin America to consider similar initiatives. No indications could be found that mixture toxicity is considered during risk assessment of chemical products.

Globally harmonised system of classification and labelling of chemicals

In Brasil, the Ministry of Development, Industrialisation and Foreign Trade (MDIC) is in charge to regulate the harmonisation labeling obligations for suppliers of chemical products used in work environments and make the GHS enforceable. Brazilian companies who export their products, mainly to Europe, comply with GHS (Barbosa, 2013). In general, GHS is required for substances since February 2011, for mixtures there is a transition period until June 1st, 2015 (CEFIC, 2014).

Regulation on agricultural chemicals

Pesticides and similar products are defined as *“products or agents of chemical, physical, biological nature intended to defend and protect stored processed agricultural outputs, pastures, native or planted forests, urban and industrial environments from attack by a variety of creatures”* (Fang, 2016). Substances classified as pesticides include defoliant, desiccant, growth stimulator and inhibitors. Component refers to the active ingredient, technical product (technical grade active ingredient), raw material, inert ingredient and additive used for the production of pesticide and similar products (Fang, 2016).

The Federal Law 7802/1989 on chemicals policy (pesticides law), regulates the research, experimentation, production, packaging, labeling, transportation, storage, marketing, commercial-advertising, utilisation, import, export, waste and package disposal, registration, classification, control of pesticide, components and similar products. It provides rules for: (i) manufacturing, import, distribution, labels, information on adverse consequences, handling and posology of chemicals for agribusinesses and forestry purposes; (ii) authorisation and permits; (iii) registration of products; (iv) prohibited hazardous active ingredients and chemicals, as well as (v) joint jurisdiction of Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of the Environment and Ministry of Health for the issuance of licenses, permits and registrations as well as for the inspection and control.

Pesticidal products are evaluated in a regular process. Therefore, a complete dossier of the technical product and its active ingredients, which are not registered in Brasil yet, is evaluated (Hirata, 2006). Pesticides can be also approved based on equivalency², hereby the registration is based on a reference product, whose registration was already granted after evaluation of the complete dossier. The Decree 4074/2002 provides the legal framework for pesticide registration and defines requirements for the registration based on equivalency, data requirements, laboratory practice for conducting data and acceptance of literature data for specific information (Hirata, 2006). According to the Decree 4.074/2002, the applicant shall simultaneously submit the application and attached dossiers to the Ministry of Agriculture, Health and Environment, respectively. The registration

² Equivalence means the determination of the similarity of the impurity and toxicological profile, as well as the physical and chemical properties, presented by supposedly similar technical material originating from different manufacturers, in order to assess whether they present similar levels of risk (WHO, 2016)

authorities of the different Ministries evaluate the efficacy, toxicological and environmental properties and decide on approval or non-approval of the registration. The pesticides risk assessment and hazard classification from the Ministry of Environment, for example, is based on parameters of bioaccumulation, persistence, transport, toxicity to different organisms, as well as on mutagenic, teratogenic and carcinogenic properties of the pesticide. Depending on these properties chemicals are classified in four categories: Class I - Product Highly Dangerous; Class II - Very Dangerous Product; Class III - Dangerous Product; Class IV - Product Slightly Dangerous (IBAMA, 1996). Pesticides might be re-evaluated, if health or environmental risks are revealed, if international organisations warn of new risks or if pesticides with a better safety or efficacy profile are available, which might lead to a replacement of existing pesticides (Fang, 2016). In these cases, the Brazilian authorities review the dossiers, under consideration of the approaches used by other institutions, and may cancel the registration of the pesticide under suspicion. A product registration can be canceled due to a negative result during periodic re-evaluation, violation of government imposed enterprise sanctions or breach of operating scope (Fang, 2016).

As the legislative system is considered outdated and incompatible with global best practices, a new pesticide law is drafted is currently considered by Brasil's Chamber of Deputies (Fang, 2016). It was proposed to establish new organisation, the National Technical Commission of Plant Protection to centralise authority. A new system of evaluation and registration similar to that implemented in the United States and Canada is expected to be implemented in Brasil (Fang, 2016). Despite all current efforts to establish new systems on pesticides evaluation, no further specifications on a concise risk assessment of mixtures are defined yet.

Conclusion

Brasil does not have a legislation setting and discipline procedures for the assessment and control management of chemical risks in a wide range, thus, it is known that substances are placed on the domestic market without any kind of monitoring or systematic control of the government. The whole process of the evaluation and registration of chemicals is currently under evaluation. New laws on industrial chemical substances and pesticidal products are drafted and might improve the assessment of chemicals and the implementation of laws in future. For the new regulations procedures and approaches of international organisations from US, Europe, Canada and China are evaluated, e.g. to establish a prioritisation program of high concern substances, potentially representing risk to human or environmental. This shows that these countries with a longer history of chemical regulation and comprehensive regulatory frameworks for chemical products must set an example. Currently, the assessment of mixture toxicity does not play a role in the evaluation and registration processes of chemical substances and mixtures.

3.2.3. Canada

Pesticides

In Canada, the Pest Management Regulatory Agency (PMRA)³ of Health Canada is responsible for pesticide regulation, under the Pest Control Products Act (PCPA, 2006) and Regulations made under this Act⁴.

³ <http://www.hc-sc.gc.ca/ahc-asc/branch-dirigen/pmra-arla/index-eng.php>

⁴ <http://laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/acts/p-9.01/>

In paragraph 7(7) to the Pest Control Products Act (PCPA, 2006), it is clearly stated that in the process of evaluating the human health risks of a pest control product and in determining whether these risks are acceptable, the Minister shall, *[...(b)...(i) among other relevant factors, consider available information on aggregate exposure to the pest control product, namely dietary exposure and exposure from other non-occupational sources, including drinking water and use in and around homes and schools, and cumulative effects of the pest control product and other pest control products that have a common mechanism of toxicity...]*. In assessing whether an acceptable risk is identified for decision making, particular emphasis is given on the different sensitivities of population sub-groups including pregnant women, infants, children, women and seniors.

In order to meet this legislative requirement, PMRA is harmonising with the approaches of the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA). In 2001, the PMRA published a Science Policy Notice (SPN, 2001), whereby the US EPA *Guidance for Identifying Pesticide Chemicals and Other Substances that have a Common Mechanism of Toxicity* (US EPA, 1999a – see Text Box 4) is adopted and it is proposed to follow US EPA Guidance on cumulative risk assessment (US EPA, 2002a) which was under development at the time. Details on the US EPA approach for pesticide cumulative risk assessment is presented in Section 3.2.6 to this report.

Environmental pollution

The Canadian Environmental Protection Act, 1999 (CEPA, 1999) (last amended on June 17, 2016 and current to September 18, 2016) aims at contributing to the sustainable development and therefore protection of human health and the environment through pollution prevention. A critical component of the CEPA was the compilation of a list of commercial substances already in use in Canada between January 1, 1984, and December 31, 1986, known as the Domestic Substances List (DSL). A Non-Domestic Substances List was also compiled including substances not on the DSL *“but believed to be in international commerce, though not in Canada, during the reference period”* (Meek and Armstrong, 2007). Description of the DSL and non-DSL is provided in Section 66 to the CEPA.

Substances on the DSL are categorised as Priority Substances Lists so that specific provisions may be applied on the basis of *“[...] greatest potential of exposure or (b) persistence, bioaccumulation and inherent toxicity to human health [...]”* (CEPA, subsection 73(1)). *“In order to determine whether a substance is toxic or capable of becoming toxic”,* screening level risk assessment shall be conducted (CEPA, Section 64).

The term ‘substance’ is defined by CEPA as *“any distinguishable kind of organic or inorganic matter, whether animate or inanimate, and includes [...] any mixture that is a combination of substances [...], and any complex mixtures of different molecules that are contained in effluents, emissions or wastes that result from any work, undertaking or activity”* (CEPA, Section 3(1)). In line with this definition, all substances including single chemicals but also complex mixtures formed naturally or as a result of chemical reactions, emissions and effluents and products of biotechnology and potential candidates for risk assessment under this legislation.

A substance is considered to be toxic under the CEPA if it is *“...entering or may enter the environment in a quantity or concentration or under conditions that:*

- a. have or may have an immediate or long-term harmful effect on the environment or its biological diversity;*
- b. constitute or may constitute a danger to the environment on which life depends; or*

- c. *constitute or may constitute a danger in Canada to human life or health.*" (CEPA, Section 3(1)).

There is no clear guidance produced by the respective Canadian Authorities (Canada's Department of the Environment and Department of Health) on how to address the CEPA mandate for assessing the impact of combined exposure to multiple chemicals. In 2007, Meek and Armstrong published the chapter *The Assessment and Management of Industrial Chemicals in Canada*, thereby introducing an approach for priority setting and/or assessing mixtures of chemicals included in the DSL on the basis of available data on exposure and toxicity and using simple (SimHaz) and complex (ComHaz) hazard and exposure (ComET) tools. In relation to potential exposure, all substances on the DSL are grouped into one of three categories, *i.e.*, those presenting "greatest", "intermediate" or "lowest" potential for exposure (GPE, IPE or LPE) (Figure 1).

In the Meek and Armstrong (2007) proposal it is recognised that most frequently, not all components in a mixture are known, exposure data are uncertain and the toxicological data are limited. Thus, the approach that can be used for mixture assessment will depend on whether data are available:

- for the mixture as a whole;
- only for components of mixture;
- for similar mixture(s).

Further, it is proposed to base screening health assessments on the analysis of a margin of exposure (MOE), where critical effect levels are compared to estimates of exposure taking into account confidence/uncertainties in the available exposure and toxicological databases and other relevant data (e.g. toxicokinetics, mode of action).

This approach has been considered further as the basis for the WHO/IPCS framework on combined exposures with relevance to human health risks (Meek et al., 2011). The objective of the WHO/IPCS framework is to perform a 'fit for purpose' assessment, so that the minimum amount of resources is invested to make a decision for a specific purpose. The magnitude of potential risks, the objective (e.g. priority setting or screening for additional focus or risk management), and the scope (e.g. local, national) of the assessment are considered for the initial problem formulation (Meek, 2013).

Figure 1: Tools-based approach for health-related components of DSL categorisation. GPE, IPE or LPE refers to "greatest", "intermediate" or "lowest" potential for exposure. (Meek & Armstrong, 2007)

Figure 2: Example of tiered exposure and hazard considerations: Mixture of Component based (Meek et al., 2011)

Further, Health Canada has developed guidance documents in order to provide training and advice to other Federal Departments on human health risks posed by federal contaminated sites under the Federal Contaminated Sites Action Plan (FCSAP⁵):

- The *Federal Contaminated Site Risk Assessment in Canada, Part I: Guidance on Human Health Preliminary Quantitative Risk Assessment (PQRA)* (Health Canada, 2010a).
- *Federal Contaminated Site Risk Assessment in Canada, Part V: Guidance on Human Health Detailed Quantitative Risk Assessment for Chemicals (DQRA_{Chem})* (Health Canada, 2010b).

Text Box 1.

The purpose of the *Federal Contaminated Site Risk Assessment in Canada, Part I: Guidance on Human Health Preliminary Quantitative Risk Assessment (PQRA)* (Health Canada, 2010a) is to “prescribe, to the degree possible, standard exposure pathways, receptor characteristics, toxicological reference values (TRV), and other parameters required to quantitatively and consistently assess the potential chemical exposures and human health risks at federal contaminated sites”. The only reference to mixture assessment is made in Section 2.7.3 of the Guidance, and it is restricted to the approach to be followed for the assessment of mixtures of carcinogenic polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH). A potency equivalence factor scheme is proposed where carcinogenic PAHs are adjusted to their carcinogenic potency relative to benzo[a]pyrene, and the potency equivalents are then summed.

The purpose of the *Federal Contaminated Site Risk Assessment in Canada, Part V: Guidance on Human Health Detailed Quantitative Risk Assessment for Chemicals (DQRA_{Chem})* (Health Canada, 2010b) is to provide a more accurate (realistic), defensible, and representative estimate of risks than that generated by a PQRA. With regard to mixture toxicity, the approach proposed in the *Supplemental Guidance for Conducting Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures* (US EPA, 2000) is adopted. Details on this approach are presented in Text Box 7. In addition to additive, synergistic/potentiative (greater than additive) and antagonistic (less than additive) effects, toxic equivalents are also considered where Toxicity Equivalent Factors (TEFs) are estimated for PCDDs/PCDFs (Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins/Polychlorinated dibenzofurans) and dioxin-like PCBs (polychlorinated biphenyls) relative to 2,3,7,8-tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin and for PAHs relative to benzo[a]pyrene.

For the estimation of risk from simultaneous exposure to multiple chemicals of potential concern the approaches proposed for single chemicals are followed:

a) Non-carcinogens

For substances presenting risks other than cancer, a hazard quotient (HQ) is estimated as the ratio of the estimated exposure to the reference value (e.g. Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI), Tolerable Air Concentration) as indicated in Equation 1 and Equation 2:

Equation 1 (Health Canada, 2010a,b)

$\text{Hazard Quotient} = \frac{\text{Estimated (on-site + background) Exposure } (\mu\text{g/kg bw/d})}{\text{Tolerable Daily Intake } (\mu\text{g/kg bw/d})}$

⁵ The FCSAP is a program of the Government of Canada “designed to ensure improved and continuing federal environmental stewardship as it relates to contaminated sites located on federally owned or operated properties”

OR, in case of airborne contaminants with a tolerable air concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)

Equation 2 (Health Canada, 2010a,b)

$$\text{Hazard Quotient} = \frac{\text{Air Concentration } (\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3) * \text{Fraction of time Exposed}}{\text{Tolerable Air Concentration } (\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3)}$$

The HQ is analogue to the terms exposure ratio and hazard ratio often encountered.

For single chemicals, HQs are estimated for each exposure route (oral, dermal, inhalation) where there are pathway specific TRVs. In case there is only one TRV (e.g. only oral TDI exists), exposures by multiple routes are summed and compared to this single TRV.

For simultaneous exposure to multiple chemicals, non-cancer HQs are assumed to be additive and summed for those substances determined by the risk assessor to have similar target organs/effects/mechanisms of action. For purposes of $\text{DQRA}_{\text{chem}}$, exposures associated with this total $\text{HQ} \leq 1.0$ will be deemed negligible. Risks for chemicals with unique target organs/effects/mechanisms of action should be shown individually (Health Canada, 2010b).

b) Carcinogens

For carcinogens with the same target organ and form of cancer, the risks are assumed to be additive and summed. The total cancer risk in such cases is deemed to be “essentially negligible” where the estimated total Incremental Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR⁶) is ≤ 1 in 100,000 (1×10^{-5}) (Health Canada, 2010b).

Additional guidance on mixture risk assessment may be provided by different Canadian States with the purpose to address local concerns as mandated by State Law.

Oregon’s Revised Cleanup Law (ORS 465.315(2)(a)⁷) proposes to conduct either a *deterministic* or a *probabilistic* risk assessment in order to [*demonstrate that acceptable risk levels have been achieved or will be achieved at a site and ensure protection of human health and the environment*]. In order to cover for this mandate the Oregon Department of Environmental Quality (DEQ) has produced relevant guidance documents (DEQ, 1998; DEQ, 2010) based primarily on US EPA guidance (see Section 3.2.6 Other Chemicals(a) to this report):

- The *Guidance for Use of Probabilistic Analysis in Human Health Risk Assessment* (DEQ, 1998) considers the hazard index (HI) approach by combining HQs from systemic toxicants with similar toxic endpoints in case of non-carcinogens or the cumulative ILCR during a life-time exposure in case of carcinogenic contaminant mixtures.
- The *Human Health Risk Assessment Guidance* (DEQ, 2010), adopts a deterministic risk assessment approach starting by determining the full nature and extent of contamination at cleanup sites in Oregon, including determination of contaminant type, their horizontal and vertical distribution, and their potential for movement. Contamination data obtained are used throughout the risk assessment. Human health risk assessment is again performed

⁶ The ILCR is derived as: $\text{ILCR} = \text{Exposure } (\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{d}) \times \text{Cancer Slope Factor } (\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}/\text{d})^{-1}$, or in the case of airborne contaminants with a unit risk value in $(\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3)^{-1}$:

$\text{ILCR} = \text{Air Concentration } (\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3) \times \text{Fraction of Time Exposed} \times \text{Cancer Unit Risk } (\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3)^{-1}$

⁷ <http://www.oregonlaws.org/ors/465.315>

considering the HI approach for non-carcinogenic mixtures and the excess lifetime cancer risk for carcinogenic contaminant mixtures.

The acceptable risk level following either the deterministic or the probabilistic approach, is defined among others,

- *“For multiple carcinogens and multiple exposure pathways, a cumulative lifetime excess cancer risk of less than or equal to one per one hundred thousand at the 90th percentile and less than or equal to one per ten thousand at the 95th percentile, each based upon the same distribution of cumulative lifetime excess cancer risks for an exposed individual” (Oregon Administrative Rule, OAR 340-122-115(3)(b)).*
- *“For noncarcinogens, a hazard index less than or equal to one at the 90th percentile, and less than or equal to ten at the 95th percentile, each based upon the same distribution of hazard index numbers for an exposed individual” (OAR 340-122-115(4)(b))].*

The Government of Alberta has published the *Guidance on Human Health Risk Assessment for Environmental Impact Assessment* (Alberta Health and Wellness, 2011) to provide general guidance for the completion of a human health risk assessment as part of an Environmental Impact Assessment mandated by the Environmental Protection Enhancement Act. In this guidance, the principle of additivity is adopted to address mixture toxicity. The exposure limits described by other regulatory Agencies (Health Canada, 2010b; US EPA, 2000) are referred to. These approaches are described in detail in Text Boxes 1 and 7.

Summary and Conclusion

In Canada, the Pest Management Regulatory Agency (PMRA) of Health Canada is responsible for pesticide regulation, under the Pest Control Products Act (PCPA, 2006) and Regulations made under this Act. In the PCPA, there is a clear mandate to consider aggregate exposure from diet and residential sources and cumulative effects of pest control and other products that have a common mechanism of toxicity in the process of human health risk assessment. In order to meet this legislative requirement, PMRA is harmonising with US EPA approaches. In 2001, the PMRA published a Science Policy Notice (SPN, 2001), whereby the US EPA *Guidance for Identifying Pesticide Chemicals and Other Substances that have a Common Mechanism of Toxicity* (US EPA, 1999a – see Text Box 4) is adopted and it is proposed to follow US EPA Guidance on cumulative risk assessment (US EPA, 2002a) which was under development at the time.

With regard to environmental pollutants, Health Canada has developed guidance documents (Health Canada, 2010a,b) in order to provide training and advice to other Federal Departments on human health risks posed by federal contaminated sites under the Federal Contaminated Sites Action Plan (FCSAP). Additional guidance on mixture risk assessment is provided by different Canadian States with the purpose to address local concerns as mandated by State Law (DEQ, 1998; DEQ, 2010; Alberta Environment, 2011). These guidance documents are based on the principles (dose addition, hazard index, hazard quotient) previously described by US EPA (2000).

3.2.4. Japan

In Japan, chemicals are regulated under the “Act on the Evaluation of Chemical Substances and Regulation of Their Manufacture, etc.” (Chemical Substances Control Law: CSCL), which forms the legal framework for the evaluation procedure required for import and manufacture of general industrial chemical substances and products. Similar to the chemical legislation in Europe, chemical substances or products with specific uses are subject to specific regulations: Food and food related substances are regulated in the “Food Sanitation Law”, agricultural chemicals in the “Agricultural Chemicals Regulation Act”, fertilisers in the “Fertilizer Regulation Act”, feed and feed additives in the “Act on Safety Assurance and Quality Improvement of Feeds” (METI, 2011) and pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and medical equipment in the “Pharmaceutical Affairs Law” currently replaced by the “Pharmaceutical and Medical Device Act” (Eisenhart, 2014)

At the world summit on sustainable development in 2002, Japan agreed that *“chemicals are used and produced in ways that lead to the minimization of significant adverse effects on human health and the environment, using transparent science-based risk assessment procedures and science-based risk management procedures, taking into account the precautionary approach”* by 2020 (MOE, 2016). In this context, the Japanese “Chemical Substance Control Act” was amended in 2009, introducing an efficient system which allows a stepwise risk assessment of chemicals (MOE, 2016). The following section gives an overview of the evaluation processes for chemical substances and products in the different regulatory sectors established in Japan.

General Law on chemical substances and products

The “chemical substance control law” aims *“to prevent environmental pollution caused by chemical substances that pose a risk of impairing human health and interfere with the inhabitation and growth of flora and fauna”* (METI, 2016a). Approximately, 28000 “existing” chemicals are currently imported or manufactured in Japan (METI, 2016a). For these chemical substances safety evaluations have been conducted by the Japanese government and regulatory measures have been set, if required. The evaluation of new industrial chemicals depends on their produced or imported volumes and is organised in tiers, thus, information for the risk assessment is collected stepwise. The CSCL has been recently reviewed and amended in order to ensure safety of the public and conformity with international rules and goals (METI, 2011). The following overview of the evaluation process is based on a presentation of the National Institute of Technology and Evaluation, Japan (NITE) (Hirai, 2012): In the pre-marketing period, chemicals are screened in a hazard-based assessment and persistent and bioaccumulative chemicals, are categorised as class 1 specified chemicals, chemicals manufactured or imported in quantities of more than 1 ton/year are treated as priority assessment chemicals, remaining chemicals are considered as general chemical substances with low risk. Priority assessment chemical substances are evaluated by the government in a step-wise risk assessment, considering persistency, human health (e.g. mutagenicity, carcinogenicity, reproduction toxicity, repeated dose toxicity), environmental health (algae, fish, daphnia), production or import volume and the estimated emission in Japan. The chemicals are categorised in one of five exposure classes and in one out of four hazard classes. A scoring approach combines exposure and hazard classes and allows the classification as high medium or low risk chemical. High risk chemicals are directly designated as priority assessment chemical substances, whereas medium and low risk chemicals are further reviewed. A stepwise risk assessment is conducted for all priority assessment chemical substances. The risk assessment can involve up to four tiers, in each step more toxicity and exposure data of the chemical substance is considered. This leads to a classification as general chemical or

class II specified chemical, causing potential risks to human health and the environment. The Japanese approach allows a risk-based management of chemicals as the government may take measures to control risks associated with the chemical (METI, 2016b). Thus, manufacturing, import or use of class I specified a chemical substance is prohibited and of a class II specified chemical substances is restricted by CSCL (MOE, 2014). According to the English translation of the “Act on the evaluation of chemical substances and regulation of their manufacture, etc.” (METI, 2005), the current Japanese legislation does not require considering mixture toxicity, combined, cumulative or synergistic effects. The Ministry of the Environment clearly states that principally risk assessment is conducted on a substance, but that this might be revised “*on the basis of information obtained through the processes of the risk assessment*” and that risk assessment “*may be implemented comprehensively on multiple chemical substances, where necessary*” (MOE, 2012). However, this might refer more to chemical substances with isomeric mixtures or dissociation than to intentional or environmental mixtures, no further specifications are provided for the assessment of mixtures.

The functionality of CSCL is equivalent to REACH, however, it is a prioritisation led approach which is based on the risk assessment conducted by the government (Hirai, 2012). In contrast, REACH requires that data has to be provided before authorisation for the European market and the risk assessment is prepared by the industry and conducted by the Member States. Both approaches consider the risk towards humans and ecosystems of all produced or imported chemical substances on the market, excluding substances and products being subject to specific regulations (food additives, fertilisers, medicinal products, cosmetics, pesticides). However, only REACH explicitly covers the risk towards workers and consumers, whereas CSCL also covers biocides (Hirai, 2012). Both regulations, REACH and CSCL, focus on chemical substances and do not require the assessment of mixture effects.

Globally harmonised system of classification and labelling of chemicals

Currently, consumer product GHS labelling is not legally required for all chemical substances in Japan, but mandatory for certain specified substances of specific regulations. However, suppliers are free to apply risk based labelling in accordance to GHS and the Japanese Industrial Standards. In this case, the risk assessment is on their own responsibility, using reasonable scientific procedures or their own methods in a transparent manner. The Japanese ministries provide guidance on the GHS classification in general (METI, 2013) and the risk assessment for consumer products for the GHS labelling (NITE, 2008). Both documents provide criteria for the classification of chemical substances as well as mixtures. The classification of consumer products requires the “*classifications and labelling focusing on the intrinsic hazards of individual chemical substances and their mixtures*” and applies to all “*pure chemical substances, and their dilute solutions and mixtures of chemical substances*” (NITE, 2008). For the estimation of the human exposure, the potential exposure by several exposure routes shall be considered by summing up the estimated human exposure of each exposure path. For the estimation of chronic health effects it is recommended to use the hazard information of the product itself or of a similar product, if no product data is available no concrete approach is proposed (NITE, 2008). The document does not mention to consider synergistic, cumulative or combined effects as well as mixture toxicity. It must be noted, that NITE refers to procedures of the US EPA and WHO and therefore, seems to review existing methods at the international level. According to a report available at the United Nations (UN) website a “GHS Classification Guidance for chemical mixtures” will be developed by governmental projects (UN, 2016), however, this was not public available at the time of this report.

Regulation on agricultural chemicals

The Japanese “Agricultural Chemicals Regulation Act” regulates all substances to control diseases or pests that may damage crops. It aims *“to improve the quality of agricultural chemicals and to ensure their safe and proper use [...] as well as the protection of human health and stable agricultural production”* (MOE, 2007). This law sets requirements for the manufacturers and importers to provide information on potential toxic effects to humans or livestock, potential detoxification methods and may limit the use of harmful agricultural substances. However, the approach of the risk assessment is not described in the regulation itself.

Pesticides have to be registered on a formulation basis for sale and import in Japan (FAO, 2015). The system for the pesticide registration has been reformed since 2007. Since then, decision on the registration is based on a full risk assessment of scientific data, considering exposure data and the magnitude of different risks. Within the regulatory framework for pesticides, the toxicological data of the candidate pesticide is evaluated and reference values (ADI, ARfD) and MRLs for the respective pesticide are proposed (Horibe, 2014) So far, risk assessment is conducted on the active substance level and mixtures does not play a role for the registration of pesticides.

Conclusion

Currently, the Japanese regulations dealing with chemical substances and agrochemical chemicals do not mention or require considering mixture toxicity, thus, there are no provisions regarding the risk assessment of mixtures in the Community law. However, Japan improves cooperation with international bodies such as Codex Alimentarius, OECD and accepts OECD style dossiers and study reports in English (FAO, 2015). This international cooperation and harmonisation with international standards, might bring mixtures in the focus of Japanese researchers and politicians. Furthermore, a harmonised approach for risk assessment, supported by many international bodies might set a good example for Japan to follow.

3.2.5. Korea

In Korea, hazardous chemical compounds were registered and controlled under the “Toxic chemical control act” from 1991 to 2015 (CIRS, 2016). Since January 2015, evaluation and registration of chemical substances are regulated under the “Act on the Registration and Evaluation of chemicals”, whereas the “Chemical Control Act” focuses on the control of hazardous substances (CIRS, 2013). Also the Korean government regulates chemical substances for specific uses in separate regulations, such as the “Agrochemicals Control Act”, “Fertilizers Control Act”, “Pharmaceutical Affairs Act”, “Food Sanitization Act” and “Cosmetics Act” (FAOLEX, 2013). The National Institute of Food and Drug Safety Evaluation (NIFDS), develops management methods and gives guidance for the risk assessment of potentially hazardous substances in food, medical products and others. The Institute conducts the risk assessment of the endocrine disrupters, pesticides, raw materials, disinfectants in food, cosmetics, medical devices and pharmaceutical products (NIFDS, 2016). Risk assessment of raw materials in consumer products, such as detergent, bleach, fabric softener, etc. is conducted by the Korean Ministry of Environment.

Registration and evaluation of chemicals

All chemical substances and products have to be registered before being imported to or manufactured in Korea. The evaluation of new chemicals is based on the “Act on the Registration and

Evaluation of chemicals” (Korea REACH), which aims to “*protect people's health and the environment*” (FAOLEX, 2013). The regulation sets requirements for the hazard and risk assessment of chemical substances and products with the objective to identify and restrict the import and production of hazardous chemical substances. The chemical registration process in Korea is organised similarly to the European REACH, the registrant has to provide the hazard data in a dossier. The required data include information on physical and chemical properties, toxicity and ecotoxicological data, guidance for safe use, exposure scenarios as well as classification and labelling of the chemical substance (CIRS, 2016). For the initial assessment of the toxicity, data on genotoxicity, degradability, acute toxicity (fish, water flea and birds), eye irritation, skin irritation and skin sensitivity are required (MoEK, 2013). All new chemicals and existing chemicals imported or produced in volumes higher than 1 ton have to be registered (CIRS, 2016). The Ministry of Environment is responsible for the evaluation of the data, reviews the hazard data and conducts a hazard assessment, if necessary. A risk assessment is conducted, if more than ten tons of the chemical substance is imported or manufactured or if it is considered as necessary after the hazard assessment. The hazard and risk assessment leads to the authorisation or to the prohibition of the chemical substances. Chemical substances designated as hazardous by Minister of Environment are classified as toxic substance, authorisation substance (need permission before import or manufacturing), restricted substance (prohibited for specific purpose) or prohibition substance (banned for any purpose) (FAOLEX, 2013). In contrast to the European REACH, the Korean REACH has special requirements for products, including consumer and biocidal products (CIRS, 2016). In case a product contains an as hazardous designated substance in concentrations higher than 10% or is assumed to be potentially hazardous to human or the environment, a risk assessment is conducted for the product and safety and labelling criteria are set (He, 2016). The Ministry of the Environment can prohibit the sale and use of product. In conclusion, the Korean “Act on the Registration and Evaluation of chemicals” regulates chemical substances and products, being mixture. However, no information was found how the risk assessment is conducted. Further, the regulation itself does not require considering mixture toxicity of different chemical substances in one product or of different substances or products.

Chemical Control Act

The Chemical Control Act regulates the marketing, distribution, handling and disposal of chemicals, which have been evaluated and authorised under the Korea REACH. Thus, no further hazard and risk assessment is conducted, but risk management plans for persons handling the chemical are set (He, 2015)

Globally harmonised system of classification and labelling of chemicals

GHS has been fully implemented for chemical substances and mixtures since July 2013 (ChemSafetyPro, 2015). Beside consumer products and cosmetics, the major regulations on chemical substances and products require the classification according to the GHS criteria (CEFIC, 2014). Thus, effects of mixtures are considered by simplified approaches (see CLP 3.1.1.2).

Agrochemicals Control Act

Fungicides, insecticides, herbicides and other products used to control germs, insects, aphids, mites, viruses, weeds, other animals and plants that may affect the harvest of the main crop, are regulated in the “Agrochemicals Control Act”. This act aims to “*enhance the quality of agrochemicals, establish*

order in their distribution, promote safety in their use, and further contribute to the development of agricultural production and the conservation of the living environment” (WIPO, 2016). The hazard or risk assessment of agrochemicals is not addressed here, because it is regulated under the “Food Sanitization Act”.

Concerning the quality management and risk assessment of agricultural chemicals Korea initiated many research projects to improve the risk assessment system and plans to: i) encourage the registration of environment-friendly safe agrichemicals, ii) establish safety management standards for registered agrichemicals, iii) establish detailed guidelines for the production and examination of agrichemical registration data, iv) determine the status of agrichemical usage for major crops, and v) inspect agrichemical quality standards (UN, 2009).

Food Sanitization Act

The Ministry of Food and Drug Safety (MFDS) established a food safety system and manages all activities ensuring food safety. Among other food laws, the “Food Sanitation Act” builds the legal frame ensuring safe use and controlling risks arising from foods. The Act aims to *“contribute to the improvement of public health by preventing sanitary risk caused by foods, promoting the qualitative improvement of food nutrition and giving accurate information on foods”* (MFDS, 2011). Article 15 requires to assess the risk of foods *“which are likely to cause a risk and have been known to contain harmful materials”* (MFDS, 2011). It further claims to establish a Food Sanitation Deliberation Committee being responsible to propose maximum residue limits of toxic or harmful substances (e.g. agricultural pesticides or heavy metals). Furthermore, the Committee shall study the international standards and specifications of foods, etc. The Food Sanitation Act does not specify how the risk of food is assessed, MRL shall be set and if the assessment of mixture toxicity and combined exposure shall be considered.

Conclusion

The risks assessment of chemicals is conducted according to the “Guidance of chemicals risk assessment” published in 2011 by the NIFDS. This guidance was on the time of the report not available in English. Korea initiated research to develop methods for the evaluation of risks caused by mixtures and cumulative risk assessment, including case studies of pesticides. However, effects of chemical mixtures are not considered in risk assessment so far. Further, the assessment of mixture toxicity, due to combined exposures of different substances or products containing different substances, is not explicitly demanded in the legal acts. The classification and labelling according to the GHS criteria may include a hazard assessment considering mixtures toxicity based on simplified summation methods, but no specific information was found on this. As a result of the recent changes in the regulation related to chemical substances and products, few information was public available in English. Therefore, new developments regarding the risk assessment of chemicals might be not taken into account.

The Korean government seems to consider new developments for risk assessment of chemicals, actively cooperates with international bodies such as OECD and participates in international efforts for the sustainable development and sound control of chemicals to implement Agenda 21 (UN, 2009). Thus, new developments in terms of chemical risk assessment will be recognized and considered and might lead to amendments in the Korean regulation as well.

3.2.6. USA

Pesticides

The US EPA regulates pesticides under broad authority granted by two major statutes, the Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act (FIFRA, 2012) and the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FFDCA, 2016). These Acts have been amended by the Food Quality Protection Act (FQPA, 1996) and the Pesticide Registration Improvement Act (PRIA 1, 2004). PRIA 1 has been reauthorised by the Pesticide Registration Improvement Renewal Act of 2007 (PRIA 2) and the Pesticide Registration Improvement Extension Act of 2012 (PRIA 3). The PRIA 1 (2004) describes a new pesticide registration service fee system in replacement of Section 33 of the FIFRA and it is therefore unrelated to the scope of this report and will not be discussed further.

Within the US EPA, the Office of Pesticide Programs (OPP) *“regulates the use of all pesticides in the United States and establishes maximum levels for pesticide residues in food, thereby safeguarding the nation's food supply”*.

The laws of the United States (US) are organised by subject into the United States Code (USC) which is available online on the Federal Digital System from the US Government Printing Office⁸.

a) Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act (FIFRA)

All pesticides distributed or sold in the US must be registered (licensed) by US EPA under the FIFRA⁹. The latter provides federal regulation on pesticide registration, distribution, sale, and use. The official text of FIFRA (1996) is available in Title 7, Chapters 136 & 136a of the USC (7 USC 136 & 7 USC 136a) and has been revised by the US Senate in 2012 (FIFRA, 2012).

In Section (2)(u) of the revised FIFRA (2012) the term *“pesticide”* is defined as follows:

(1) any substance or mixture of substances intended for preventing, destroying, repelling, or mitigating any pest, (2) any substance or mixture of substances intended for use as a plant regulator, defoliant, or desiccant, and (3) any nitrogen stabilizer, except that the term “pesticide” shall not include any article that is a “new animal drug” [...], or that is an animal feed [...] bearing or containing a new animal drug. The term “pesticide” does not include liquid chemical sterilant products (including any sterilant or subordinate disinfectant claims on such products) for use on a critical or semi-critical device¹⁰ [...].

The requirements, exemptions and procedures for pesticide registration, as well as details on the classification of pesticides are described, among other issues, in Section 3 of the revised FIFRA (2012), however, no specific provisions with regard to assessing mixtures of pesticides are described.

b) Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FFDCA)

The FFDCA is codified into Title 21 Chapter 9 of the USC (21 USC 9). The original FFDCA was amended in December 31, 2004 and has been updated in 2012 and 2016. The following section refers to the most recent revision of the FFDCA, enacted as from September 30, 2016 (FFDCA, 2016).

⁸ <https://www.gpo.gov/fdsys/browse/collectionUScode.action?collectionCode=USCODE>

⁹ <https://www.epa.gov/laws-regulations/summary-federal-insecticide-fungicide-and-rodenticide-act>

¹⁰ For clarification, the term “critical device” [includes any device which is introduced directly into the human body, either into or in contact with the bloodstream or normally sterile areas of the body and the term “semi-critical device” includes any device which contacts intact mucous membranes but which does not ordinarily penetrate the blood barrier or otherwise enter normally sterile areas of the body] (FIFRA, 2012).

Subchapter IV of the FFDCA specifically deals with the aspect of “Food” and Section 408 describes “Tolerances¹¹ and Exemptions for Pesticide Chemical Residues”.

Section 408(b)(2)(D)(v) of the revised FFDCA requires US EPA to take into account *“available evidence concerning the cumulative effects of such [pesticide] residues and other substances that have a common mechanism of toxicity”* in establishing, modifying, leaving in effect, or revoking a tolerance or exemption for a pesticide chemical residue.

Text Box 2.

This piece of legislative requirement has recently been addressed by the OPP through the guidance “Pesticide Cumulative Risk Assessment: Framework for Screening Analysis Purpose” (US EPA, 2016), extensively discussed in this report under Section 3.2.2.(d).

In Section 408(b)(2)(C), it is noted that the risk assessment of a pesticide chemical residue to infants and children should be based, among others, on *“(III) available information concerning the cumulative effects on infants and children of such residues and other substances that have a common mechanism of toxicity”* and, there should be reasonable certainty that *“no harm will result to infants and children from aggregate exposure to the pesticide chemical residue”* and that *“a specific determination regarding the safety of the pesticide chemical residue for infants and children”* should be published. *“Moreover, surveys should be conducted to document dietary exposure to pesticides among infants and children. In the case of threshold effects [...] an additional tenfold margin of safety for the pesticide chemical residue and other sources of exposure shall be applied for infants and children to take into account potential pre- and postnatal toxicity and completeness of the data with respect to exposure and toxicity to infants and children [...]”* provided that these data are reliable.

Text Box 3.

In order to address the legislative requirement as set in Section 408(b)(2)(C) of the FFDCA, regarding the use of an additional safety factor for the protection of infants and children with consideration of potential pre-and post-natal toxicity in the context of cumulative risk¹² assessments (CRA), the OPP published a guidance document on the “Consideration of the FQPA Safety Factor and Other Uncertainty Factors in Cumulative Risk Assessment of Chemicals Sharing a Common Mechanism of Toxicity” (US EPA, 2002b).

According to information presented in this guidance, in cumulative risk assessments it is not appropriate to automatically use chemical-specific reference doses (RfDs) and margins of exposure (MOE¹³), since these values are not necessarily based on common effects among the group of chemicals acting by a common mechanism of toxicity.

¹¹ A pesticide tolerance is the maximum amount of a pesticide allowed to remain in or on a food, as part of the process of regulating pesticides, known in the EU as the MRL.

¹² *“Cumulative Risk is the risk of a common toxic effect associated with concurrent exposure by all relevant pathways and routes of exposure to a group of chemicals that share a common mechanism of toxicity”* (US EPA, 2002a).

¹³ *“The margin of exposure (MOE) is a numerical value providing a measure of how close is the exposure to the NOAEL. It is the ratio of the point of departure (usually a NOAEL) divided by the anticipated or actual measure of human exposure”* (US EPA, 2002a, 2002b).

For the derivation of RfDs or MOE for consideration in cumulative risk assessments, the appropriate point of departure (POD¹⁴), e.g. NOAEL, Benchmark Dose (BMD), is selected based on an index chemical's end-point pertaining to the common mechanism and is representative of the chemical group as a whole.

The first step in the derivation of RfDs or MOEs from the POD selected for consideration in cumulative risk assessment, is to consider the need to apply “traditional uncertainty factors” or FQPA) safety factors to each chemical member of the cumulative assessment group (CAG)¹⁵ to cover for the following potential database deficiencies:

- UFS: uncertainty factor to extrapolate from subchronic to chronic data, when deriving a chronic RfD from a subchronic study;
- UFL: uncertainty factor to extrapolate from the LOAEL to NOAEL, if no appropriate NOAEL can be identified in the toxicology database; and
- UFD_b: database uncertainty factor, intended to account for the absence of key toxicological data).

Additional uncertainty and/or safety factors might be applied to the CAG for consideration in cumulative risk to cover for inter-human (UFH) and experimental animal-to-human (UFA) variation, the completeness of the database with respect to exposure and toxicity to infants and children (UFD_b CAG) and potential pre- and postnatal toxicity (special FQPA safety factor). The uncertainty factors and the special FQPA safety factor are applied to the CAG following the same approach as used for individual chemicals, except that the focus is now confined to the common toxic effect(s) produced by members of the CAG. This is because the common mechanism group of chemicals is considered to be a single unit where the uncertainty is tied to the whole group.

Detailed description of the uncertainty/safety factors considered in cumulative risk assessment is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Incorporation of Uncertainty/Safety Factors in Cumulative Risk Assessment (US EPA, 2002b)

Factors Applied to Specific Chemical Members of the Cumulative Assessment Group (CAG)		
Traditional Uncertainty Factors or FQPA Safety Factors	LOAEL to NOAEL (UFL)	≤ 10-fold factor is used to estimate a NOAEL from a LOAEL for a specific chemical's relative toxic potency factor**.
	Subchronic to Chronic (UFS)	≤ 10-fold factor is used to estimate a chronic point of departure from a study of less than chronic treatment duration for a specific chemical's relative toxic potency factor.
	Deficiencies in the Toxicity Database (UFD_b chemical)	≤ 10-fold factor is used to address database deficiencies, which are not addressed by UFL and UFS factors, in estimating the relative toxic potency of each chemical member of the CAG.
Factors Applied to the Cumulative Assessment Group (CAG) after conducting cumulative risk assessment		

¹⁴ “A **point of departure (POD)** is a dose that can be considered to be in the range of observed responses, without significant extrapolation. A POD can be a data point or an estimated point that is derived from observed dose-response data. A POD is used to mark the beginning of extrapolation to determine risk associated with lower environmentally relevant human exposures” (US EPA, 2002b).

¹⁵ **Cumulative Assessment Group (CAG)** “is a subset of chemicals selected from a **common mechanism** group for inclusion in a refined quantitative estimate of risk.”, where: “Common mechanism of toxicity pertains to two or more pesticide chemicals or other substances that cause a common toxic effect(s) by the same, or essentially the same, sequence of major biochemical events (i.e., interpreted as mode of action)” (US EPA, 2002a).

Standard Uncertainty factors	Human Variation (or intraspecies) (UFH)	≤ 10-fold UF intended to account for potential variation in sensitivity among humans and is considered to include toxicokinetic/dynamic processes.
	Experimental Animal to Human (interspecies) (UFA)	≤ 10-fold UF intended to account for uncertainty in extrapolating data from laboratory animals to project human risk, considered to include toxicokinetic/dynamic processes.
Traditional Uncertainty Factors or FQPA Safety Factors	Deficiencies in the Toxicity Database (UFDb CAG)	≤ 10-fold factor is used to address database deficiencies that are common to the CAG.
	Special FQPA Safety Factor	The reasons for such a factor include: concern about pre- or postnatal toxicity and deficiencies in the exposure database. It is anticipated that most toxicity database issues will be dealt with on the individual chemical members before conducting the cumulative assessment. The risk assessor should not account for the same deficiency twice. Consideration should be given to whether these concerns pertain to the common toxic effect and common mechanism of toxicity.

**** Relative Potency Factor (RPF)** is a ratio of the toxic potency of a given chemical to that of an index chemical in the CAG. The index chemical is a chemical from the CAG used as a point of reference for standardising the common toxicity of the other chemical members of the CAG. Relative potency factors are used to convert exposures of all chemicals in the CAG into their exposure equivalents of the index chemical” (US EPA, 2002a). – Further discussed in Text Box 6, to this report.

The value of the “special FQPA safety factor” could be a “default” 10-fold factor as mandated by the statute, if OPP decides that there are not reliable data to choose a different one. Alternatively, in the presence of reliable existing data, it is possible to decide on the appropriateness, adequacy, need for or size of such a safety factor, on a case-by-case basis.

Section 408(p)(1) of the FFDCA, mandates US EPA to develop the Estrogenic Substances Screening Program to “determine whether certain substances may have an effect in humans that is similar to an effect produced by a naturally occurring estrogen, or such other endocrine effect as the Administrator may designate”. In carrying out this screening program, in Section 408(p)(3)(B) of the FFDCA it is indicated that the US EPA may provide data “for the testing of any other substance that may have an effect that is cumulative to an effect of a pesticide chemical” if they determined that a substantial portion of the population may be exposed to such substance. No particular guidance is published so far to specifically assess cumulative risk from exposure to pesticides and other chemicals with estrogen-like properties.

c) Food Quality Protection Act (FQPA)

The FQPA (1996) was signed into law in 1996 (Public Law 104–170, 104th Congress) and amended both the FIFRA and the FFDCA and thus fundamentally changed US EPA’s regulation of pesticides on certain aspects, including screening of pesticides for disruption of the endocrine system, approving pesticides of low risk, considering minor uses of pesticides, providing a list of pests of significant public health importance, registering antimicrobial pesticide products, periodic review cycle for pesticide registrations in line with scientific developments and so on.

With regard to pesticides registration, the FQPA mandates US EPA to consider among others, in the risk assessment of pesticides, the following points, with special concern on infants' and children susceptibility:

- *cumulative exposure* to pesticides that have common mechanisms of toxicity, and
- *aggregate exposure* to a pesticide from multiple pathways of exposure (food, water, residential and other non-occupational sources).

In order to implement these FQPA requirements, the OPP of the US EPA developed specific methodologies, including:

- "Guidance for Identifying Pesticide Chemicals and Other Substances that have a Common Mechanism of toxicity" (US EPA, 1999a) which describes the process for establishing common mechanism groups (CMGs); and the
- "General Principles for Performing Aggregate Exposure and Risk Assessments" (US EPA, 2001a), which refers to human exposure and risk "*associated with all pathways and routes of exposure to a single chemical*".

Text Box 4.

According to the Guidance for Identifying Pesticide Chemicals and Other Substances that have a Common Mechanism of toxicity (US EPA, 1999a), a CMG is a group of chemicals that share a Common Mechanism of Toxicity¹⁶. A common mechanism of toxicity "*pertains to two or more pesticide chemicals or other substances that cause a common toxic effect to human health by the same, or essentially the same, sequence of major biochemical events*". Further, a common toxic effect among a pesticide and another chemical is a toxic effect¹⁷ that occurs "*in or at the same anatomical or physiological site or locus (e.g. same organ or tissue)*", such that there is concordance between chemicals with both site and nature of the effect. There is a critical difference between a common and a cumulative toxic effect. The cumulative toxic effect is the "*net change in magnitude of a common toxic effect*" resulting from exposure to at least two chemicals causing the same toxic effect by a common mechanism.

In order to describe a common mechanism of toxicity and identify a CMG of chemicals, it is not required to understand all steps leading to the effect, but rather identify the crucial events following the initial chemical interaction that are required to elicit the toxic effect¹⁸. The conceptual framework of the process for identifying CMGs according to US EPA (1999a) guidance, involves the following steps:

¹⁶ The term "**mechanism of toxicity**" is similar to the term MOA considered in recent guidance (US EPA, 2016)

¹⁷ In the frames of the OPP Guidance on the establishment of CMG (US EPA, 1999a) the **toxic effect** is defined as "*an effect known (or can reasonably expected) to occur in humans, that results from exposure to a chemical substance and that will or can reasonably be expected to endanger or adversely affect quality of life, e.g. acute lethality, loss of hearing, renal tubule necrosis, cardiomyopathy etc*". Thus, the 'toxic effect' as defined by US EPA is known as 'adverse effect' under EU legislation.

¹⁸ In recent guidance (US EPA, 2016) the initial chemical interaction is known as the molecular initiating event (MIE) and the sequence of major biochemical events following the initial chemical interaction that are required to elicit the toxic effect constitute the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP).

Step 1. Identify a candidate set of substances that might cause a common toxic effect by a common mechanism of toxicity.

The preliminary grouping of chemicals will be based upon at least one of the following criteria which are presumed to potentially lead to a common toxic effect by a common mechanism:

- *structural similarity;*
- *mechanism of pesticidal action;*
- *general mechanism of mammalian toxicity;*
- *a particular toxic effect.*

Step 2. Definitely identify those substances from Step 1 that cause a common effect.

This step requires that *“a detailed evaluation of available toxicological data for each substance will be undertaken to identify and characterise the toxic effects caused by each substance and to determine which of the substances cause toxic effects that are common with the other substances”*.

Step 3. Determine the toxic mechanism(s) by which each substance causes a common toxic effect.

Step 3 involves understanding of the biochemical events that are most crucial in causing the toxic effect. This process requires detailed evaluation of already available toxicological data on the biochemical mechanism previously determined for (a) each chemical, or (b) analogues of the pesticide (or other chemical), in the absence of already available direct mechanistic data. Primary sources of information should be the Agency’s databases with studies submitted in support of (re)-registration decisions, peer reviewed journals, text books and government reports.

Steps 4 and 5. Comparisons of mechanisms of toxicity (Step 4) and refined grouping of substances (Step 5)

In step 4 of this framework substances with similarities in both the nature and sequence of the major biochemical events that cause the toxic effect, will be considered as having a common mechanism. Substances that cause a common toxic effect by different mechanisms will be excluded from the refined grouping (Step 5).

Overall, evaluating a group of pesticides for potential common mechanism of toxicity begins with several considerations: chemical structural similarity, toxicological profile, and information on mechanism of toxicity/sequence of major biochemical events following the initial chemical interaction that are required to elicit the toxic effect. The identification of a CMG is a pre-requisite for the necessity to perform a CRA.

Text Box 5.

According to the OPP Guidance on General Principles For Performing Aggregate Exposure And Risk Assessments” (US EPA, 2001a), the term ‘Aggregate Exposure’ is defined as *“the amount of a chemical available at the biological exchange boundaries (e.g., respiratory tract, gastrointestinal tract, skin) for all routes of exposure”*; whilst ‘Aggregate Risk’ is *“the likelihood of the occurrence of an adverse health effect resulting from all routes of exposure to a single substance”*.

Briefly, the aggregate exposure assessment *“begins with the identification of the toxicological endpoint(s) of concern for a particular chemical assessment; proceeds toward the identification of possible exposure scenarios (e.g., based upon label use patterns) and assigns certain toxicological endpoints for each route of exposure of concern in the aggregate assessment; and, finally, defines a series of hypothetical, potentially exposed “individuals” by bringing together data sets or a series of professional judgements relating to the aggregate exposure assessment under consideration (toxicological endpoint, duration of exposure, exposure scenario). This is done by appropriately combining information about a potentially exposed “individual’s” demographic (e.g., age, gender, and racial/ethnic background), temporal (season), and spatial (region of the country) characteristics throughout the analysis in a manner which maintains the consistency of the individual”*.

An outline of the framework for performing aggregate exposure and risk assessment is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Framework for performing aggregate exposure and risk assessment (US EPA, 2001a)

The scientific principles and approaches described in the guidance documents on establishing CMGs (US EPA, 1999a) and performing aggregate exposure and risk assessment (US EPA, 2001a) have been incorporated and further developed in revised guidance provided by the OPP:

- “Guidance on Cumulative Risk Assessment of Pesticide Chemicals That Have a Common Mechanism of Toxicity” (US EPA, 2002a)

Text Box 6.

According to the guidance document on CRA, the term CRA refers to “the process of consideration potential human health risks from all pathways of dietary and non-dietary exposures to more than one pesticide acting through a common mechanism of toxicity” (US EPA, 2002a).

A tiered approach for CRA is proposed by US EPA (2002a) and it is summarised in Table 6:

Table 6: The Cumulative Risk Assessment Process (US EPA, 2002a)

Tiered approach in Cumulative Risk Assessment	
Step 1.	Identify Common Mechanism Group (CMG)
Step 2.	Identify potential exposures
Step 3.	Characterise and select common mechanism endpoint(s)
Step 4.	Determine the need for a comprehensive cumulative risk assessment
Step 5.	Determine candidate cumulative assessment group (CAG)
Step 6.	Conduct dose-response analyses and determine relative potencies and points of departure
Step 7.	Develop detailed exposure scenarios for all routes and durations
Step 8.	Establish exposure input parameters
Step 9.	Conduct final cumulative risk assessment
Step 10.	Conduct characterisation of cumulative risk

By definition, the process of CRA involves the establishment of a CMG as previously described (US EPA, 1999a), before conducting a highly refined CRA. The identification of a CMG of chemicals that induce a common toxic effect by a common mechanism of toxicity is the first step (Step 1) in the proposed tiered approach for CRA. Step 1 of the CRA process has so far been applied by OPP on specific chemical groups:

- A Common Mechanism of Toxicity: The Organophosphate Pesticides (Miles et al., 1998);
- A Science Policy on a Common Mechanism of Toxicity: The Carbamate Pesticides and the Grouping of Carbamate Pesticides with Organophosphorus Pesticides (US EPA, 1999b);
- The Grouping of a Series of Chloroacetanilide Pesticides Based on a Common Mechanism of Toxicity;
- The Determination of Whether the Dithiocarbamate Pesticides Share a Common Mechanism

of Toxicity (US EPA, 2001b).

- Thiocarbamates: A Determination of the Existence of a Common Mechanism of Toxicity and a Screening Level Cumulative Dietary (Food) Risk Assessment (US EPA, 2001c);

Further, for each chemical in a CMG the OPP should typically perform an aggregate risk assessment (Step 2) where all pathways of potential human exposure to this chemical will be considered in line with relevant guidance (US EPA, 2001a), and then characterise and select the common toxic effect to be considered in the CRA (Step 3). The next step (Step 4) is to decide if a CRA should be performed and if so to assess whether a comprehensive CRA should be conducted or a screening CRA is sufficient. A comprehensive CRA is required when the CMG *“is composed of a large number of chemicals, has widespread pesticide uses, has high aggregate risks, and has monitoring data showing detectable levels of residues”*.

The CAG to be considered in the CRA may be a subset of the CMG. This is because not all chemicals, pathways of exposure (e.g. residential, drinking water), routes of exposure or uses are risk contributors requiring risk mitigation measures and if they are not they should be removed from the CMG (Step 5). Once the CMG is refined into a CAG, dose-response modelling should be applied to determine relative potencies and POD for the specific CAG to carry out the CRA (Step 6). While data and methods are still improving on the area of mathematical modelling, it is assumed that dose addition is applicable among members of the CAG. Then, the relative potency for the CAG is estimated according to the following steps:

- **Determine Toxic Potency of each chemical member in the CAG by route and duration of interest**

This may be achieved by using a curve fitting model to describe the dose-response relationship for each member of the CAG and another mathematical model to derive the BMD as a measure of each chemical’s toxic potency.

- **Select an Index Chemical as a reference point to put each chemical member on a common scale**

The index chemical is one for which there is high-quality dose-response data available for the common toxic effect/species/sex and for the exposure route/pathways of interest; it is well-characterised for the common mechanism of toxicity, which is its principal toxicity and may therefore be considered to be representative of the other chemical members in the CAG. This is not necessarily the most potent chemical of the group.

- **Calculate Relative Potency Factors (RPF) based on the index chemical’s toxic potency**

Equation 3

$$RPF_n = \text{Toxic Potency}_{[\text{Index Chemical}]} \div \text{Toxic Potency}_{[\text{Chemical } n]}$$

- **Determine the Point of Departure (POD) for the index chemical by routes and durations of interest**

The choice of a POD depends on the quality of the dose-response data available. Traditionally, US EPA uses the NOAEL as a POD, although the goal is to consider the BMD instead.

Once all members of the CAG are identified, the next step (Step 7) is to elaborate the exposure scenarios resulting from the uses of each member compound as previously described by US EPA,

2001a (Text Box 5). An important parameter to assess in this step is whether the exposure scenarios of each CAG member are such that overlapping exposure with another chemical from the same CAG will occur. This might be a difficult process requiring detailed exposure pattern information in cases of acute or short-term toxic effects, or even chronic effects mediated through reversible precursor events, since it is highly likely that the exposures in these cases are sequential instead of concurrent. Whereas, for chronic and carcinogenic effects expressed only after long-term exposure and which are considered to be irreversible, it is assumed that any additional exposure by another chemical will be overlapping in any case. Data for three major sources of pesticide exposure should be considered, i.e. food, drinking water, residential and non-occupational. These data will include combinations of magnitude, frequency, duration and route of exposure data and might be obtained by direct measurements (monitoring data) or model-based estimates (Step 8).

Conduction of the final cumulative risk assessment (Step 9) involves combining all of the dose-response characteristics (RPFs and PODs), exposure data, and exposure scenarios in a manner that will produce a logical outcome consistent with exposures likely to be encountered by the public using probabilistic models¹⁹. In principle, the residues of each member of the CAG will be converted to concentration equivalents of the index chemical using the RPFs previously estimated in Step 6 of the assessment (Equation 4) and will then be summed to give a total cumulative residue value for each sample (Equation 5), as follows:

Equation 4 (US EPA, 2002a)

$$\text{Residue}_{IE} = \text{Residue}_{\text{compound}} \times \text{PF} \times \text{RPF}$$

where:

- *Residue_{IE}* is the compound-specific residue concentration expressed as equivalents of the index compound;
- *Residue_{compound}* is the compound-specific residue concentration;
- *PF* is a compound-specific process factor (for food) or treatment factor (for water); and
- *RPF* is the relative potency factor used to normalize the compound-specific residues to the toxicity of the index compound. This factor converts the compound-specific concentration to an index-compound-equivalent basis.

Equation 5 (US EPA, 2002a)

$$\text{Residue Cumulative} = \sum_{\text{CAG}} \text{Residue}$$

Equation 4 and Equation 5 are applicable for the dietary food and water pathways, whereas for the residential and other non-occupational pathways, the exposure is estimated considering Equation 6:

Equation 6 (US EPA, 2002a)

$$\text{Exposure} = \text{Contact} \times \text{Residue}$$

¹⁹ Examples of probabilistic models that may be considered are the:

- Calendex™ (<http://www.novigen.com/calendex.html>)
- LifeLine™ (<http://www.epa.gov/scipoly/sap/2000/#september>)

Other models such as the Cumulative and Aggregate Risk Exposure Model (CARES) and RExY (Residential Exposure-Year) were still under development at the time this guidance (US EPA, 2002a) was released.

where:

the contact function defines the duration of contact, the portion of the body exposed, how much of the available residue can be transferred to the body for dermal exposure, and the duration of contact and respiratory characteristics of the exposed individual for inhalation exposure.

Then, the point of departure (e.g. a BMD₁₀) for the index chemical is used to calculate route-specific MOEs for the CAG:

Equation 7 (US EPA, 2002a)

$$\text{MOE} = \text{POD}_{\text{index}} \div \sum_{\text{Route}} \text{Exposure}$$

The route-specific MOEs are used and combined to generate a total MOE:

Equation 8 (US EPA, 2002a)

$$\text{MOE}_{\text{total}} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\text{MOE}_{\text{oral}}^*} + \frac{1}{\text{MOE}_{\text{dermal}}} + \frac{1}{\text{MOE}_{\text{inhalation}}}}$$

* Oral is the total oral exposure from food and drinking water plus oral, non-dietary contacts such as hand-to-mouth exposure from residential pesticide uses.

This approach has already been applied by US EPA in “A case study of the cumulative risk of 24 organophosphate pesticides”²⁰.

Description of the results and conclusion of the cumulative risk assessment, the relative confidence in toxicity and exposure data sources and model inputs, identification of major areas of uncertainty and impact of final assessment is performed in Step 10 of this approach. At this step the need to apply uncertainty and safety factors as previously described by US EPA (2002b) (Text Box 3) is considered. Group uncertainty/safety factors should be applied at the MOE_{total}, if necessary.

So far, the OPP has performed CRA for five CMGs: organophosphates, N-methyl carbamates, chloracetanilides, triazines, and naturally occurring pyrethrins and synthetic pyrethroids²¹. Further they examined thiocarbamates²² and dithiocarbamates²³ for potential inclusion into two additional CMGs, but determined they do not share a common mechanism of toxicity, so did not proceed further with an assessment.

d) Recent Scientific Advances in the US

The OPP has recently published a revised guidance for screening available information to identify groups of pesticides that may have a common mechanism of toxicity, i.e. the Pesticide Cumulative Risk Assessment: Framework for Screening Analysis Purpose (US EPA, 2016). In this document, it is recognised that the approach followed so far provides highly sophisticated results, but it is also highly demanding with respect to resources and experimental, modelling and exposure data. Further,

²⁰ <https://archive.epa.gov/scipoly/sap/meetings/web/pdf/finalreport.pdf>

²¹ <https://www.epa.gov/pesticide-science-and-assessing-pesticide-risks/cumulative-assessment-risk-pesticides>

²² <http://epa.gov/pesticides/cumulative/thiocarb.pdf>

²³ <http://epa.gov/oppsrrd1/cumulative/dithiocarb.pdf>

the highly refined CRA, provided with previous guidance, might not even be necessary or feasible for all existing pesticide classes. In an attempt to describe a more pragmatic methodology this guidance is produced based on the 2011 WHO IPCS Guidance on CRA which describes a screening approach involving tiered analysis with increasing levels of refinement (Meek et al., 2011).

In this document (US EPA, 2016) the definitions on key toxicological concepts are used as previously described in the guidance for designating CMGs (US EPA, 1999a) and for developing CRAs (US EPA, 2002a). In addition, the terms mode of action (MOA) and AOP are used. The concept of MOA is similar to the mechanism of toxicity described in the CMG guidance (US EPA, 1999a) and presented in Text Box 4. The term AOP was first introduced by Ankley et al. (2010) and in practice it “links a molecular initiating event (MIE) to progressive levels of biochemical organisation at the individual or population level”. Thus, although the terminology is different to previous guidance the concepts are similar: an AOP is conceptually similar to establishing key event in a MOA or for establishing a CMG under the FFDCA.

The framework for CRA screening as presented in US EPA (2016) guidance is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Framework for CRA screening (US EPA, 2016)

The framework for CRA screening describes three options:

- Option 1, where no CMGs are identified and no CRA is necessary;
- Option 2, where there is evidence to establish a candidate CMG and further screening for toxicology and exposure analysis is required; and
- Option 3, where there is sufficient MOA/AOP information available for establishing key events and CMG and a CRA should be conducted in line with the respective US EPA guideline (US EPA, 2002a) described in Text Box 6.

The OPP provides further guidance on the application of Option 2. The screening process involves toxicology evaluation and risk assessment including exposure and risk potential evaluation.

With regard to toxicology evaluation in CRA screening, the OPP *“assumes dose additivity in CRA unless data are available to support an alternative approach”*. Dose addition assumes by definition that *“chemicals in a mixture are non-interactive and elicit a common response through similar actions on a biological system”*, acting as concentrations or dilutions of each other (US EPA, 2003a). A consequence of this assumption is that the dose-response curves of the individual components of the mixture exhibit similar shapes.

As a first step in the screening analysis approach (Option 2 in the framework for CRA screening, Figure 4), a MOA/AOP hypothesis is set and an index chemical with the most robust toxicological database for the common toxic effect *via* the exposure routes of interest, is selected. In order to assess risks posed by mixtures where their components share a common MOA and have similar-shaped dose-response curves to elicit the same toxic effect, the RPFs and PODs for the common toxic effect (e.g. NOAEL, BMD) could be applied as previously proposed by US EPA (2002a) and described in Text Box 6. RPFs are estimated in relation to the MOA/AOP hypothesis and the common toxic effect for the group of pesticides. Unlike previous guidance (US EPA, 2002a), RPFs and PODs do not have to be accurately assessed. Instead, they may vary in their level of refinement and may be derived from the PODs from single chemical risk assessments, the NOAELs/LOAELs from specific toxicological studies or possibly BMDs.

The second step of the screening process, involves exposure considerations for cumulative risk assessment considering the registered use patterns, level of refinement, and overall risk profiles of the candidate CMG under consideration as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Exposure considerations in CRA screening (US EPA, 2016)

Further, a screening-level analysis of cumulative risks of a candidate CMG is performed following a tiered approach for both dietary exposure analysis (Figure 3.2.1-4) and residential exposure analysis (Figure 3.2.1-5) and stop refinements at the point when risk does not exceed the level of concern as determined by the POD selected. It is noted that depending on resources there might not be a need to follow more refined approaches if the cumulative risks are acceptable based on the minimal resources. In fact, most food exposure assessments that are conducted by OPP for conventional pesticides are unrefined, relying on tolerance level residues and assuming 100% of the crop being treated (US EPA, 2016).

The proposed tiered approach for dietary exposure analysis is presented in Figure 6.

TIER 1

Combined food and water exposures from the most recent single pesticide chemical risk assessment(s) are extracted, RPF scaled, and summed.

TIER 2

Addresses the unlikely co-occurrence of high-end residues in drinking water: drinking water residues are removed from all single pesticide chemical dietary exposure assessments; the single highest RPF-scaled modeled water exposure scenario from among the members of the candidate CMG is identified & combined with the RPF-adjusted combined food exposures.

TIER 3

An attempt is made to refine co-occurrence of food residues. Only the pesticide that has the highest RPF-scaled exposure would be used for a given crop/commodity, since the growers would not use multiple pesticide chemicals from the same pesticide chemical class in the same season.

Figure 6: Tiered approach for dietary exposure analysis (US EPA, 2016)

Both Tiers 1 and 2 assume complete co-occurrence of both food and drinking water residues and may therefore lead to overestimations. Tier 3 incorporates relative toxicities and begins to address the unlikely co-occurrence of candidate CMG pesticide residues in food and/or water. However, it again might provide overestimates of cumulative risk since Tier 3 does not utilise food monitoring data but rather modelling water residue estimates.

The proposed tiered approach for residential exposure analysis is presented in Figure 7.

TIER 1 - Unrefined Assessment

Exposures to surface residues from the most recent chemical risk assessment(s) for each pesticide are extracted, RPF scaled, and summed assuming that all residential exposure for each scenario (e.g., turf, pet, indoor) occurs *via* the chemical with the highest risk.

TIER 2 - Refine Surface Residue Assumptions

In case chemical-specific surface data were not utilized in Tier 1, then the chemical specific data resulting in the highest surface residue for that exposure scenario are used to refine residential exposure estimates.

TIER 3 - Refine Co-occurrence Across Exposure Scenarios.

An attempt is made to refine co-occurrence of exposure scenarios using available survey data, assuming that all residential exposure for each scenario (e.g., turf, pet, and indoor residential exposures) is to the single pesticide with the highest risk (i.e., lowest MOE) for that scenario.

Figure 7: Tiered approach for residential exposure analysis (US EPA, 2016)

Despite potential overestimates and assumptions made in the tiered approaches proposed for food and residential exposure analyses, further refinement beyond Tier 3 is not recommended, since it would require extensive resources beyond the scope of screening-level evaluation.

Overall, this approach entails up to a certain extent the US EPA (1999a) guidance for establishing CMGs and the US EPA (2002a) guidance describing the steps used in conducting CRA (Options 1 and 3 of the framework). Further, it introduces a screening-level approach in case the available toxicological data support a candidate CMG (Option 2). This screening is based on exposure data with increasing level of refinement (tiered approach) and although might be resource intensive it does not need to be performed or at least not all tiers, if the risks identified do not exceed the level of concern.

Other chemicals

a) Environmental Pollutants:

In 1983, the National Academy of Sciences had published the book entitled *“Risk Assessment in the Federal Government: Managing the Process”*, where they recommended that Federal regulatory agencies establish *“inference guidelines to ensure consistency and technical quality in risk assessments and to ensure that the risk assessment process was maintained as a scientific effort separate from risk management. A task force within the US EPA accepted that recommendation and requested that Agency scientists begin to develop such guidelines”*. In 1986, the Office of Health and Environmental Assessment produced the Guidelines for the Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures considering comments from the public and the Science Advisory Board (US EPA, 1986). These *“Guidelines represent the Agency’s science policy and are a procedural guide for evaluating data on the health effects from exposures to chemical mixtures”*. More details on specific principles and procedures, where considered necessary, was provided by the US EPA Risk Assessment Forum through Supplemental Guidance for Conducting Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures as a supplement to the EPA’s Guidelines for the Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures (US EPA, 2000). An overview on the recommended approach to perform environmental pollutant mixture risk assessment is described in Text Box 7.

Text Box 7.

In the frames of the Guidelines for the Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures (US EPA, 1986) and supplemental Guidance thereof (US EPA, 2000), the following key concepts are noted:

- **Mixtures** are defined as *“any combination of two or more chemical substances regardless of source or of spatial or temporal proximity”*. So, the mixtures may include compounds generated simultaneously from a single source of process (e.g. coke oven emissions and diesel exhaust) or produced as commercial products eventually released to the environment (e.g. PCBs, gasoline and pesticide formulations), or even placed in the same area for disposal or storage, eventually coming into contact with each other and released as a mixture in the environment.
- The term **Mode of Action** is defined as *“a series of key events and processes starting with interaction of an agent with a cell, and proceeding through operational and anatomical changes causing disease formation”*. Further, for mixture assessment *“a similar mode of action across mixtures or mixture components is assumed and in some cases this requirement may be relaxed to require that these chemicals act only on the same target organ”*.
- The concept of **additivity** is considered. When mixture components show similar toxicity, **dose addition** is recommended, where the mixture response is estimated for the combined dose expressed as the sum of the relative potencies of its components. A method based on dose addition that has been used most often by US EPA is Hazard Index (HI²⁴), where HI<1 indicates a mixture exposure of no significant concern. For the component chemicals in a mixture that show dissimilar toxicity, **response addition** is recommended instead, where the mixture risk is estimated as the sum of individual risks together. In case there are data

²⁴ *“The Hazard Index (HI) is defined as a weighed sum of the exposure measures for the mixture component chemicals. The “weight” factor according to dose addition should be a measure of the relative toxic strength, sometimes called potency”* (US EPA, 2000)

available indicating interactions between mixture components leading to most commonly greater than additive (i.e. synergistic) or less than additive (i.e. antagonistic) toxic effects, the interaction-based HI is used, where the magnitude of interaction is incorporated in the estimation of HI.

- Chemical mixtures may arise or change as a result of **environmental transformation**, depending on the physicochemical properties of the compound(s) and their susceptibility to photolysis, hydrolysis or biodegradation (aerobic and anaerobic).

The different types of environmental pollutant mixture risk assessment that should be performed according to US EPA (2000) is illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The different types of mixtures assessments based on the availability and quality of the data (US EPA, 2000)

All of the possible assessment paths illustrated in Figure 8 should be performed based on data availability.

When toxicity data are available on the mixture of concern, the quantitative risk assessment is performed using directly these data. When toxicity data are not available for the mixture of concern, then it is recommended to use toxicity data on a “sufficiently similar” mixture instead, to draw conclusions for the mixture of concern. When the mixture of concern is a member of a group of similar mixtures²⁵ then both the comparative potency approach²⁶ should be considered as well as the potential for environmental transformation.

²⁵ “A ‘group of similar mixtures’ refers to chemically related classes of mixtures that act by a similar mode of action, have closely related chemical structures, and occur together routinely in environmental samples, usually because they are generated by the same commercial process” (US EPA, 2000).

²⁶ In the comparative potency approach “a set of mixtures of highly similar composition is used to estimate a scaling factor that relates toxic potency between two different assays of the same toxic endpoint. The mixture

Another approach is to evaluate the mixture through an analysis of its components, e.g. using dose addition for similarly acting chemicals, response addition for independently acting chemicals and interaction-based hazard index for interacting chemicals, as described above.

b) Food additives:

Concerning food additives, (FFDCA - Section 409; 21 U.S.C. 348) in order to determine whether a proposed use of a food additive is safe, the FFDCA mandates US EPA to also consider *“the cumulative effect of such additive in the diet of man or animals, taking into account any chemically or pharmacologically related substance or substances in such diet”* (Section 409(5)(b)).

c) New animal drugs:

[...] In determining whether such [new animal] drug is safe for use under the conditions prescribed, recommended, or suggested in the proposed labelling thereof, the Secretary shall consider, among other relevant factors, [...] the cumulative effect on man or animal of such drug, taking into account any chemically or pharmacologically related substance” (FFDCA - Section 512(d)(2)(B); 21 U.S.C. 360b).

d) Colour additives:

“In determining, for the purposes of this section, whether a proposed use of a color additive is safe, the Secretary shall consider, among other relevant factors [...] the cumulative effect, if any, of such [colour] additive in the diet of man or animals, taking into account the same or any chemically or pharmacologically related substance or substances in such diet” (FFDCA SEC. 721(b)(5)(A); 21 U.S.C. 379e).

Summary and Conclusions

This section is the outcome of the screening on the United States Legislation for mandates placed to assess mixture toxicity of chemicals, including pesticides, environmental pollutants, food additives, new animal drugs and colour additives.

Pesticides are regulated by the US EPA under authority granted by two major statutes, the Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act (FIFRA) and the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FFDCA) as amended by the Food Quality Protection Act (FQPA, 1996) and the Pesticide Registration Improvement Act (PRIA 1, 2004). No specific provisions with regard to assessing the risk to pesticide mixtures are described in the FIFRA and the PRIA. However, the FFDCA and the FQPA mandate US EPA to consider among others, in the risk assessment of pesticides, both cumulative exposure to pesticides that have common mechanisms of toxicity, and aggregate exposure to a pesticide from multiple sources of exposure (food, water, residential and other non-occupational sources), with special concern on infants' and children susceptibility.

The legislative requirements set by FFDCA and FQPA are addressed by several guidance documents currently valid (US EPA, 1999a, 2001a, 2002a, 2002b, 2016). A key assumption in the US EPA approach for pesticide cumulative risk assessment is dose additivity, which means that chemicals act as concentrations or dilutions of each other, they are non-interactive and elicit a common response through similar actions in a biological system (US EPA, 2003a). A consequence of this assumption is that the dose-response curves of the individual components of the mixture exhibit similar shapes.

of concern can then be tested in one of the assays (perhaps a simple assay, e.g., in vitro mutagenicity), and the resulting potency is then adjusted by the scaling factor to estimate the human cancer potency” (US EPA, 2000).

Particular notice should be paid to the fact that although common modes of action might elicit similar dose-response curves, the reverse is not necessarily true and by no means should similar dose response curves be considered to draw conclusions on the potential mode of action leading to the same toxic effect (Slob and Setzer, 2014).

The first step in the Framework for Screening Analysis in pesticide cumulative risk assessment (US EPA, 2016) is an initial review of the chemical structure and the toxicological profile of the pesticide, and the setting of a MOA/AOP hypothesis. Then, it is possible to select one of three options (Figure 5) depending on available resources, including experimental, monitoring/exposure and modelling data. In Option 1, no common mechanism is identified and therefore no further work is necessary. In Option 2, a candidate CMG is established based on some evidence of common toxicological profile and a screening level exposure analysis is recommended for both dietary and residential sources of exposure. Cumulative risks will be compared against the level of concern using appropriate probabilistic models. The level of concern is characterised by the point of departure considered in this assessment and might be the NOAEL/LOAEL or the BMD. The BMD approach is considered to be preferable by the US EPA, however so far the NOAEL/LOAEL approach has been traditionally used. Option 3 of the screening cumulative risk assessment process is considered when there is sufficient toxicological data to prove the MOA/AOP hypothesis and establish a CMG. In this case, a detailed cumulative risk assessment should be performed following a tiered approach (US EPA, 2002a), where the CMG is refined into a CAG based on exposure data as an initial step in the cumulative risk assessment. Cumulative risk assessment involves combining all of the dose-response characteristics (Relative Potency Factors and Points of Departure), exposure data, and exposure scenarios in a manner that will produce a logical outcome consistent with exposures likely to be encountered by the public, using probabilistic models.

This cumulative risk assessment approach (Option 3) has been implemented by US EPA for five CMGs, *i.e.* organophosphates, N-methyl carbamates, chloracetanilides, triazines, and naturally occurring pyrethrins and synthetic pyrethroids. Further, US EPA has examined thiocarbamates and dithiocarbamates for potential inclusion into two additional CMGs, but no common mechanism of toxicity was identified and the assessment did not proceed further (Option 1).

Overall, the approach proposed by US EPA for cumulative risk assessment of pesticides is considered very focused and pragmatic and has proven to be applicable to certain chemical classes for which the mode of action is well established. It remains to observe in practice the applicability of Option 2 of the Framework for Screening Analysis in pesticide cumulative risk assessment (US EPA, 2016), also in line with further development of the relevant probabilistic models for toxicity and exposure analyses.

Besides pesticides, the FFDCa also mandates US EPA to consider cumulative effects in the process of regulating food additives, new animal drugs and colour additives. No specific guidance has been published and adopted by the US EPA for these chemical classes.

In the case of environmental pollutants, the US EPA has produced guidance (US EPA 1986, 2000) in order to assess mixture toxicity when the individual mixture components have similar, dissimilar or interacting (e.g. synergistic, antagonistic) modes of action. The definition of the mode of action is less strict as compared to the pesticides and it may include the series of key events leading to the toxic effect or just the target organ if no further information is available. Since there is often little information on mode of action and/or exposure, US EPA (2000) recommends that risk assessment is performed both on the mixture of concern or similar mixtures as well as the individual mixture components resulting in integrated summary and uncertainty evaluation.

3.3. Conclusions on the analyses of the legal foundations

All considered countries have legal acts to control the production, import and use of chemical substances in order to protect human and animal health as well as the environment. Thus, chemical substances have to be registered before sale and use. For the registration of new chemicals a hazard assessment, based on the toxicological properties of chemical substances, is required. In most cases, the toxicity data has to be provided by the applicant, the risk assessment is conducted or at least proofed by an official authority. The complexity of this assessment varies between the countries and often depends on the produced or imported tonnage per year. A more extensive hazard assessment of chemical substances is usually conducted if chemical substances or products with volumes higher than 1 ton/year are manufactured or imported. The general registration approaches for industrial chemicals are mostly substance oriented and do not require to consider mixture toxicity or effects from combined exposures.

All evaluated countries legally require the classification of chemicals according to GHS, apart from Japan, where it is recommended but not legally binding. GHS provides internationally harmonised safety information and sets up criteria for the classification of substances and mixtures. Chemicals are classified based on the evaluation of the physical, toxicological and environmental hazards to human health and the environment. Mixtures are classified based on the bridging principles, if no toxicity data is available for the complete mixture. The assessment for classification of mixtures shall also consider *“potential occurrence of synergistic effects among the ingredients of the mixture”*, antagonistic effects may lead to a lower classification if evidenced by sufficient data (UN, 2011). In summary, the GHS is a good example that combined efforts of international organisations can lead to globally harmonised approach, which is internationally accepted and applied. Thus, the classification based on GHS provides a first hazard assessment of substances and mixtures, which even requires the consideration of mixture effects.

Products for specific uses such as medicine, cosmetics, food related or pesticidal products are mostly regulated in separate legal acts with specific requirements adapted to the field of use and application. In all considered countries medicine, cosmetics, food additives or pesticidal products have to be evaluated and authorised before being introduced onto the market. The authorisation of a product is usually based on the evaluation of efficiency, usefulness/benefit and a risk assessment to avoid any harm on human, organismal and environmental health and ensure safe use. For the risk assessment intrinsic properties of the chemical products are evaluated and the potential exposure level is assessed. In most cases the risk assessment is based on single chemicals, basic acute tests are conducted with formulated products. Most of the European product regulations (e.g. on plant protection products, biocidal products, general food law) require to consider cumulative or synergistic effects. However, statements such as “if known” or “if relevant” or “If appropriate methods are available” weaken the requirement and create a loophole of not considering it. Furthermore, no guidance exists, except for biocidal products proposing a tiered approach based on the calculation hazard indices for the mixture (ECHA, 2015). If the hazard index indicates a risk ($HI > 1$), the refinement is conducted by grouping the substances with common target organ/mode of action or by considering the mechanisms of action. This is in line with the general support of the European authorities to assess mixtures in CAGs for target organs. Therefore, the EU requires considering mixture toxicity in formulated chemical products, but does not routinely assess mixture toxicity, beyond the basics test required for the whole mixtures. Thus, the evaluation of mixtures is actually required but is not clearly legally binding, because accepted methods and guidelines are missing.

In contrast, USA has a long history of chemical risk assessment and requires a cumulative risk assessment in all legal acts on intentional mixtures (Hartmanns, 2014). Therefore, mixture risk assessment of intentional mixtures is routinely conducted in different regulatory sectors. US EPA developed a tiered system for the evaluation of aggregated exposure on the basis of common mechanism groups. The approach is based on the knowledge of the mode of action of chemicals, however, for many chemicals MoAs are unclear. Therefore, the cumulative risk assessment approach is evaluated for five chemical classes only. Despite this, US EPA seems to be ahead of other countries, in terms of the legal requirements and the implementation of the cumulative risk assessment.

Canada requires assessing the impact of combined exposure to multiple chemicals, but clear guidelines how to do so are lacking. Furthermore, Canada supports the approaches developed by US EPA. In Australia, all agencies consider the synergistic effects of mixtures in their evaluations, only Brasil, Japan and Korea do not have legal requirements to consider mixture toxicity.

In summary, whole-mixture approaches are usually required in all legislations, which allow a realistic evaluation of the toxicity of a product. For unintentional mixtures this is not feasible and due to the high number of formulated products not all intentional mixtures can be tested. Therefore, component-based methods are required to assess the cumulative risks, as chemicals are mostly based on a substance oriented chemical-by-chemical risk assessment. The concept of concentration addition is assumed to provide reliable estimations for the majority of mixtures and is widely accepted as default assumption for the hazard estimation of mixtures. Two main approaches are currently under development to consider cumulative risks, the assessment based on CMGs pursued by US EPA and CAGs supported by EFSA. The main difference of the CMG and the CAG approach is that the grouping of the CMGs is based on a common MoA of chemicals, whereas CAGs are defined based on the target organ, which might be refined based on the mechanism of action. Both approaches have their bottlenecks, for CMGs MoAs have to be known, which is often not the case, and for CAGs the cumulative risk assessment of some target organs (e.g. liver) easily show a high risk and need further refinement based on mechanism of action knowledge. Both approaches are developed for pesticides and one route of exposure only. In general, tiered approaches are supported to avoid unnecessary testing and organise the risk assessment efficiently.

Finally, in all countries risk assessment is conducted in the different regulatory sectors as chemical substances are present in isolation. However, risk profiles of chemicals from different regulatory sectors are overlapping (Evan et al., 2016; Kienzler, et al., 2016), which is currently not considered.

In conclusion, the consideration of combined effects is legally binding in Australia, Canada, EU and USA, whereby the EU has to improve the regulations to avoid loopholes that make it possible to avoid the consideration of synergistic and cumulative effects. Furthermore, there is a general lack of common terminology, accepted methods, clear guidance and harmonised methods for cumulative risk assessment. It seems that the development of approaches for cumulative risk assessment is much more advanced for pesticides than for products of other regulatory sectors. Leading countries and international organisations have to generate synergies and bundle forces to develop a harmonised approach for the evaluation of mixtures. This would enable other countries with less experience in the risk assessment of chemicals to follow this good example.

4. Current approaches for health risk assessment of chemical mixtures

4.1. Current approaches

Several authorities and organisations have proposed approaches for health risk assessment of chemical mixtures that commonly take the form of decision trees or tiered frameworks. These are sometimes general in their intended application and sometimes proposed for assessment of specific exposure scenarios or groups of chemicals. Some of these approaches have been reviewed in a previous report by EFSA (2013a). This review specifically summarises the terminology, methodologies and frameworks developed by national and international agencies for the human risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals and provides recommendations for future activities at EFSA in this area (EFSA, 2013a). Since the EFSA review was conducted some additional approaches have been presented (i.e. ECHA, 2015; Price et al., 2012; Stein et al., 2014). In addition, EFSA has published guidance on the use of probabilistic methodology for modelling dietary exposure to pesticide residues (EFSA, 2012), as well as separate opinions on the identification of pesticides to be included in cumulative assessment groups (CAGs) on the basis of their toxicological profile (EFSA, 2013b) and on the relevance of dissimilar MoA and its appropriate application for cumulative risk assessment of pesticides residues in food (EFSA, 2013e). EFSA and its different European partners have made considerable progress in the development of methodologies for cumulative risk assessment of pesticides, e.g. the development of the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) tool together with the Dutch national institute for public health and the environment (RIVM). These initiatives are ongoing and more information will become available later in 2016 and during 2017 (see EFSA webpage²⁷). Recently, the EFSA has drafted the terms of Reference for a working group of the Scientific Committee on “Harmonisation of risk assessment methodologies for human health and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals” (EFSA, 2016). The working group shall develop a guidance document for human and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals, using existing frameworks and tiered approaches for each step of the risk assessment (problem formulation, hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment, risk characterisation).

The purpose of this chapter is not to conduct thorough reviews of all available approaches and methodologies, but to provide a structured overview and comparisons of the general principles applied with the aim to provide the basis for a proposal of an approach suitable for the purposes of EuroMix. For details about specific methodologies applied within the reviewed approaches the reader is referred to the original documents. The following eleven approaches were identified from literature searches as well as previous reports and are presented in chronological order:

1. **US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA):** "Supplementary Guidance for Conducting Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures" (US EPA, 2000). The purpose of this guidance is to provide a consistent US EPA approach for assessing health risks from exposures to multiple chemicals. Additional guidance and practical examples, extending the scope to cumulative risk assessment, are provided in US EPA reports "Framework for cumulative risk assessment" (US EPA, 2003b) and "Concepts, methods and data sources for cumulative health risk assessment of multiple chemicals, exposures and effects: A resource document" (US EPA, 2007).

²⁷ www.efsa.europa.eu

2. **US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA): "Guidance on Cumulative Risk Assessment of Pesticide Chemicals That Have a Common Mechanism of Toxicity"** (US EPA, 2002b). This guidance establishes a stepwise procedure intended for US EPA Office of Pesticide Programs (OPP) scientists when performing cumulative risk assessments (multiple chemicals by multiple pathways) of pesticides that act by a common mechanism of toxicity. This is a highly refined process and it was acknowledged by the US EPA that it may not be warranted to conduct such a process in all cases. Therefore, this guidance was recently supplemented by additional guidance presenting a tiered framework for the purpose of screening groups of pesticides for cumulative evaluation of dietary as well as resident exposure to pesticides (US EPA, 2016).
3. **US Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR): "Guidance Manual for the Assessment of Joint Toxic Action of Chemical Mixtures"** (ATSDR, 2004). The ATSDR provides a review of approaches existing at the time and presents a stepwise procedure intended as guidance for environmental health scientists and toxicologists of ATSDR's Division of Toxicology assessing health risks of chemical mixtures at waste sites, specifically.
4. **Scientific Steering Committee of the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety (VKM): "Combined toxic effects of multiple chemical exposures"** (VKM, 2008). This rather general report reviews approaches existing at the time and describes a step-by-step approach intended to secure that the Scientific Panels in VKM pay appropriate attention to the possibility of combined toxic effects when assessing health effects of multiple chemicals.
5. **European Food Safety Authority Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues (EFSA PPR): "Scientific Opinion on a request from the EFSA evaluate the suitability of existing methodologies and, if appropriate, the identification of new approaches to assess cumulative and synergistic risks from pesticides to human health with a view to set MRLs for those pesticides in the frame of Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005"** (EFSA, 2008). This regulation-specific EFSA opinion proposes a tiered framework for assessing health risks from pesticide residues for the purpose of setting MRLs. In addition, EFSA has more recently published additional opinions promoting the EFSA tiered approach and discussing, specifically, the relevance of dissimilar MoA (EFSA, 2013e) and grouping pesticide residues into CAGs (EFSA, 2013b) for application in cumulative risk assessment of pesticides residues in food. In this context, EFSA has also published a "Guidance on the use of probabilistic methodology for modelling dietary exposure to pesticide residues" (EFSA, 2012).
6. **UK Interdepartmental Group on Health Risks from Chemicals (IGHRC): "Chemical Mixtures: A framework for assessing risks to human health"** (IGHRC, 2009). This report addresses health risks of chemicals at levels of exposure that may be encountered by people in their daily activities. The approach is based on both a decision tree and tiered approach for addressing mixture issues.
7. **World Health Organization/International Programme on Chemical Safety (WHO/IPCS): "Framework for the risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals"** (Meek et al., 2011). This published article describes a general tiered framework intended to aid risk assessors in identifying priorities for risk management for a wide range of applications where co-exposures to multiple chemicals are expected. The framework was developed subsequent to the WHO/IPCS Workshop on Aggregate/Cumulative Risk Assessment (Combined Exposures to Multiple Chemicals) held in 2007.
8. **European Commission Scientific Committees on Health and Environmental Risks (SCHER), Emerging and Newly Identified Health Risks (SCENIHR) and Consumer Safety (SCCS):**

"Toxicity and assessment of chemical mixtures" (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). The three scientific committees refer to the WHO/IPCS framework (Meek et al., 2011) and promote a general decision tree for the assessment of both health and environmental risks from chemical mixtures.

9. **The European Chemical Industry Council (CEFIC): "A decision tree for assessing effects from exposures to multiple substances" (Price et al., 2012).** This published article presents a decision tree and tiered approach developed by CEFIC with the aim to guide the assessment of both health and environmental risks from chemical mixtures. It combines the WHO/IPCS framework with the SCHER, SCENIHR, SCCS decision tree and adds the extra step of calculating a Maximum Cumulative Ratio (MCR) as one risk characterisation step between Tier 1 and 2.
10. **The German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR): "Human health risk assessment from combined exposure in the framework of plant protection products and biocidal products" (Stein et al., 2014).** This published article describes a regulation-specific tiered approach proposed by the BfR. The purpose is to provide guidance for taking cumulative aspects into account when assessing health risks from plant protection products and biocides under their respective EU regulations. Different methodologies for cumulative risk assessment with respect to worker/application safety and pesticide residues in food, respectively, are proposed. However, the aspects specific to assessment of application safety were not included in this review since that is outside the scope of EuroMix.
11. **The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA): "Guidance on the Biocidal Products Regulation. Volume III Human Health - Part B Risk Assessment" (ECHA, 2015).** This guidance document from ECHA aims to assist users in complying with their obligations under the Biocidal Products Regulation. It includes guidance for risk characterisation for combined exposures and proposes a tiered approach. Tier 1 precedes assessment of potential risks from combined exposure, and is an intermediary step to verify risk acceptability for each substance used in the product.

4.2. Summary and comparisons of key principles and strategies applied

The different approaches to risk assessment of chemical mixtures reviewed here have been developed over time, by different organisations under different jurisdictions and regulatory settings. Hence, the purpose and scope, primarily, but also to some extent the principles applied, vary between them. To enable structured identification and comparisons of key principles, details about the different approaches were extracted and collected in a database constructed in Microsoft Excel. The points of comparison were chosen specifically based on aspects relevant for the work in EuroMix and with the aim to identify information gaps and needs for further development. The scope, purpose and principles applied in the nine approaches have been summarised in Table 7. The commonalities and differences are further discussed in the following sections.

Table 7: Overview of the scope and risk assessment strategies of nine different approaches to risk assessment of chemical mixtures. (ADI = Acceptable Daily Intake; BBDR = biologically-based dose-response; BMD = Benchmark Dose; HI = Hazard Index; HQ = Hazard Quotients; LOAEL = Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level; MCR = Maximum Cumulative Ratio; MOET = Combined Margin of Exposure; MRL = Maximum Residue Levels; NOAEL = No Observed Adverse Effect Level; OEL = Occupational Exposure Limit, PBPK = Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic; PoD = Point of departure; RA = Risk Assessment; RfC = Reference Concentration; RfD = Reference Dose; RfPI = Reference Point Index; RPF = Relative Potency Factors; TDI = Tolerable Daily Intake; TEF = Toxicity Equivalence Factors; TTC = Target organ Toxicity Concentration; TTD = Target organ Toxicity Dose; TMOE/S = Combined Margin of Exposure/Safety)

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
"Supplementary Guidance for Conducting Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures" US EPA, 2000	A consistent US EPA approach for assessing health risks from exposures to multiple chemicals <u>Grouping based on:</u> 1) Co-exposure 2) Toxicological similarity <i>Further guidance and examples provided in US EPA 2003 and 2007</i>	Refers to traditional exposure assessment methods	A whole mixture approach is preferred. <u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> RfD/RfC TTD/TTC BMD	Yes, when the dose for each individual component is at a level at which effects are not expected to occur, be observable, or be of concern	HI refined using RPF/TEF-based if possible	Response addition, add individual risks together	Interaction-Based HI/BINWOE-method PBPK models useful to investigate the potential for interactions

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
<p>“Guidance on Cumulative Risk Assessment of Pesticide Chemicals That Have a Common Mechanism of Toxicity”</p> <p>US EPA, 2002b</p> <p><i>Supplemented by US EPA 2016.</i></p>	<p>A stepwise procedure for performing cumulative risk assessments (multiple chemicals by multiple pathways) of pesticides with a common mechanism of toxicity.</p> <p>US EPA, 2016 supplements this guidance by proposing a tiered screening approach.</p> <p><u>Grouping based on:</u> Toxicological similarity</p>	<p>Stepwise approach (steps 2, 7 and 8 of the overall procedure): First identify potential exposure pathways and routes for all compounds in the common mechanism group (CMG). Then establish detailed exposure scenarios for all compounds in CAGs²⁸ and determine the magnitude, frequency, and duration for all pertinent exposure pathway/route combinations.</p> <p>Should reflect “real-world exposure” with the aim to identify the main drivers of toxicity in the CAG.</p>	<p>Stepwise approach (steps 3 and 6 of the overall procedure): First characterise and select common mechanism endpoints for all compounds in the common mechanism group (CMG). Then conduct dose-response analyses, determine relative potencies and points of departure for all compounds in CAGs¹.</p> <p><u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> BMD NOAEL if BMD is not possible Refinement using PBPK modelling</p>	Yes	RPF-based (ideally based on PBPK-data)	Not within the scope of this approach.	Refers to US EPA, 2000

²⁸ In US EPA 2002b a CAG represents a subset of the chemicals in a CMG that contribute most to the toxicity of the CMG.

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
<p>"Guidance manual for the assessment of joint toxic action of chemical mixtures"</p> <p>ATSDR, 2004</p>	<p>A stepwise procedure intended as guidance for environmental health scientists and toxicologists of ATSDR's Division of Toxicology assessing health risks of chemical mixtures at waste sites</p> <p><u>Grouping based on:</u> Co-exposure</p>	<p>Not addressed specifically, refers to other ATSDR and EPA guidance</p>	<p>A whole mixture approach is preferred. Describes separate stepwise procedures for non-carcinogens and carcinogens.</p> <p><u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> MRL (<i>NOTE: =Minimal Risk Level</i>) TTD</p>	<p>Yes, for chemicals with similar effects or the same target organ in the low dose range</p>	<p>HI (TTD-modified if justified) RPF/TEF-based</p>	<p>Response addition, add individual risks together</p>	<p>BINWOE-method</p> <p>PBPK models useful to investigate the potential for interactions</p>
<p>"Combined toxic effects of multiple chemical exposures"</p> <p>VKM, 2008</p>	<p>A step-by-step approach intended to guide VKM panels in health risk assessment of multiple chemicals</p> <p><u>Grouping based on:</u> Toxicological similarity</p>	<p>Not addressed specifically</p>	<p>Provides stepwise guidance for component-based approach.</p> <p><u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> ADI NOAEL/LOAEL</p>	<p>Not clearly stated</p>	<p>HI PoDI TMoE/S RPF/TEF-based</p>	<p>Not addressed</p>	<p>Not addressed</p>

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
<p>"Scientific Opinion on a request from the EFSA evaluate the suitability of existing methodologies and, if appropriate, the identification of new approaches to assess cumulative and synergistic risks from pesticides to human health with a view to set MRLs for those pesticides in the frame of Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005." EFSA, 2008</p>	<p>A tiered framework for assessing health risks from pesticide residues for the purpose of setting MRLs</p> <p><u>Grouping based on:</u> Toxicological similarity (CAGs)</p> <p><i>Further guidance on exposure assessment and grouping provided in EFSA 2012 and 2013b and e.</i></p>	<p>Different tiered approaches for assessment of actual exposure and MRL-setting.</p> <p><u>Tier 1:</u> deterministic, MRL or field data, EFSA consumption model data <u>Tier 2:</u> deterministic, higher and mean residues from monitoring programmes, EFSA consumption model data <u>Tier 3:</u> deterministic refined, using processing data <u>Tier 4:</u> probabilistic, distribution of monitoring data, distribution of national FCS data <u>Tier 5:</u> probabilistic, assess fraction of population instead of fraction of person-days</p>	<p>A component-based tiered approach</p> <p><u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> <u>Tier 1:</u> deterministic, ADI or NOAEL/BMD <u>Tier 2:</u> deterministic or probabilistic, use RPF based on NOAEL or BMD <u>Tier 3:</u> RPF, further refinements using PBTK-BBDR</p>	Yes	HI RfPI RPF/TEF-based	Not within the scope of the report	Not within the scope of the report

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
"Chemical Mixtures: A framework for assessing risks to human health" IGHRC, 2009	A decision tree and tiered approach for addressing mixture issues when assessing health risks of chemicals at levels of exposure that may be encountered by people in their daily activities. <u>Grouping based on:</u> 1) Co-exposure 2) Toxicological similarity	The approach taken will depend on the circumstances	A step-wise approach to component-based assessment. <u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> no specific reference point promoted, refers to approaches set up by other agencies, e.g. US EPA and ATSDR	Yes	HI (TTD-modified if possible) RPF/TEF-based	Response addition (refers to US EPA)	HI-approach with extra uncertainty factor BINWOE-method PBPK models useful to investigate the potential for interactions
"Risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals: A WHO/IPCS framework" Meek et al., 2011	A tiered framework to aid risk assessors in identifying priorities for riskmanagement for a wide range of applications where co-exposures to multiple chemicals are expected. <u>Grouping based on:</u> 1) Co-exposure 2) Toxicological similarity or interactions	Tiered approach <u>Tier 0:</u> simple semiquantitative estimates of summed exposure for the various components <u>Tier 1:</u> "summation of deterministic estimates of exposure for all components of the assessment group based on measured or modeled data" <u>Tier 2:</u> refined deterministic assessment, more data and more realistic but still conservative estimates <u>Tier 3:</u> Probabilistic exposure estimates	Component-based, tiered approach. <u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> <u>Tier 0:</u> ADI, TDI, RfD, OEL (for the most toxic component, i.e. all components are assumed to have the same potency as the most toxic component) <u>Tier 1:</u> NOAEL, LOAEL, BMD/C <u>Tier 2-3:</u> RPF, PBPK modeling	Yes	HI (using ref value for the most toxic component at Tier 0 and individual ref values at higher tiers) PoDI RPF/TEF-based	Not addressed	Not addressed

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
<p>"Toxicity and assessment of chemical mixtures" SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012</p>	<p>A decision tree for the assessment of health and environmental risks from chemical mixtures.</p> <p><u>Grouping based on:</u> Toxicological similarity</p>	<p>Supports the IPCS/WHO Tiered approach.</p>	<p>Supports the IPCS/WHO tiered approach. Includes the use of TTC at the first step. Promotes a component-based approach; whole mixture approaches are explicitly not recommended.</p> <p>Does not propose any specific guidance value/PoD</p> <p>PBPK modeling may be useful for a higher-tier assessment</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>HI (based on reference value for the most toxic component at Tier 0 and individual reference values at higher tiers) PoDI RPF/TEF-based</p>	<p>Response addition (add probabilistic risks together) Effects addition (add biological responses together)</p>	<p>Case-by-case RA</p>
<p>"A decision tree for assessing effects from exposures to multiple substances" Price et al., 2012 (CEFIC)</p>	<p>A decision tree and tiered approach to guide the assessment of health and environmental risks from chemical mixtures.</p> <p><u>Grouping based on:</u> Not addressed.</p>	<p>Supports the IPCS/WHO Tiered approach.</p>	<p>States that a whole mixture approach may be applied when such data is available but discusses the specific limitations and data requirements for such an approach.</p> <p>Does not propose any specific guidance value/PoD but refers to the WHO/IPCS approach.</p> <p>Uses the concept of MCR</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>HI/HQ</p>	<p>Not addressed</p>	<p>Not addressed</p>

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
"Human health risk assessment from combined exposure in the framework of plant protection products and biocidal products" Stein et al., 2014	A tiered approach taking cumulative aspects into account when assessing health risks from plant protection products and biocides under their respective EU regulations <u>Grouping based on:</u> Toxicological similarity (EFSA CAGs)	<u>Acute CRA:</u> Use deterministic international estimated short-term intake (IESTI). <u>Chronic CRA:</u> Can be conducted in principle but resource demanding. Should then use STMR values for the product/mixture considered and background levels for all other pesticide residues in the same CAG, as well as simulations (e.g. Monte Carlo) to estimate exposure.	Promotes a component-based approach. Only provides guidance for acute risk assessment for pesticide residues as chronic risk assessment is very resource demanding and "not expected to reveal risks that have been overlooked in the past" <u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> ARfD	Yes	HI/HQ RfPI RPF-based	Not addressed ²⁹	Case-by-case

²⁹ Stein et al. (2014) use the term "independent action" to mean the opposite of interaction. I.e. per that definition independent action can apply both to components with similar AND with dissimilar MoA.

Reference	Scope and purpose, strategy for grouping	Exposure assessment approach	Hazard assessment approach	Dose addition as default assumption?	recommended RA strategy when assuming dose addition	recommended RA strategy when assuming independent action	recommended RA strategy when assuming interaction
<p>“Guidance on the Biocidal Products Regulation. Volume III Human Health - Part B Risk Assessment” ECHA, 2015</p>	<p>This guidance aims to assist users in complying with their obligations under the Biocidal Products Regulation. It includes guidance for risk characterisation for combined exposures and proposes a tiered approach as well as a decision tree.</p> <p><u>Grouping based on:</u> Toxicological similarity</p>	<p>Provides guidance for combined exposure to multiple substances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • from one source/use • from different sources/uses <p>Internal exposure levels are used, thus exposure from different sources is taken into account.</p> <p>Refers to the IPCS/WHO Tiered approach</p>	<p>Component-based, tiered approach (same as Stein et al. 2014). The first tier is to verify risk acceptability for single components of the mixture/product. Refers to IPCS/WHO.</p> <p><u>Recommended guidance value/PoD:</u> AEL or another European validated value, e.g. a DNEL.</p> <p>PBPK modeling may be useful at higher tiers.</p>	<p>Yes, but if independent action is shown to be the appropriate assumption it is already covered in Tier 1 (assessment made substance by substance)</p>	<p>HI/HQ PoDI MOET RPF/TEF-based</p>	<p>Response addition</p>	<p>Interaction-based HI</p>

4.3. Commonalities and differences

4.3.1. Structure of the approach

The earlier reports from the US EPA (2000), ATSDR (2004), VKM (2008) and IGHRC (2009) describe step-by-step approaches, or decision trees, which provide guidance for how to progress through the mixture risk assessment based on the type of data available. In contrast, the approaches presented by the EFSA PPR (EFSA, 2008), the WHO/IPCS (Meek et al., 2011) and the BfR (Stein et al., 2014) are tiered frameworks, with simple deterministic (conservative/worst-case) assessments at lower tiers and more complex and quantitative probabilistic (and realistic) assessments at higher tiers. In the approaches presented by CEFIC (Price et al., 2012) and SCHER, SCENIHR, SCCS (2012) the tiered framework proposed by WHO/IPCS is combined with a stepwise decision tree. The updated guidance from US EPA (2016) presents a tiered approach intended for screening common mechanism groups (CMG) to determine if cumulative assessment should be applied. The tiering in this approach is thus a bit different from the others in that it does not propose very refined risk assessment at higher tiers, which is only done if the CMG is carried forward to cumulative assessment in accordance with US EPA approach (US EPA, 2002b).

While it may be useful to compare the overall structures of the different approaches this is not easily summarised in text and the reader is referred to descriptive figures in the respective original reports (specified in Table 8). Specific aspects of the approaches are summarised in Table 7 and in the sections below.

Table 8: References to figures showing the structure of the reviewed approaches.

Reference	Structure of approach depicted
US EPA, 2000	Figure 2-1, page 8
US EPA, 2002	Figure 1, page 11
ATSDR, 2004	Figure 2, page 32 and figure 3, page 45
VKM, 2008	Figure 7, page 83
EFSA, 2008	Figures 1-4, pages 61-64
IGHRC, 2009	Figure 1, page 50
Meek et al., 2011	Figure 1
SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012	Figure, page 38
Price et al., 2012	Figure 3
Stein et al., 2014	Figure 1
ECHA, 2015	Figure 13, page 265

4.3.2. Guidance for grouping

Although not very explicitly stated in most of the reports, some comparisons of guidance or discussion provided for how chemicals are grouped into relevant assessment groups can be made. There are primarily two main themes for grouping; i) the potential for the components to co-occur, and ii) similarity in toxicity, or the potential for interactions, between components.

Grouping should primarily be based on co-exposure according to the approaches presented by the US EPA (2000), the ATSDR (2004), the IGHRC (2009), and the WHO/IPCS (Meek et al. ,2011), followed by grouping based on toxicological similarity (except in the ATSDR-approach, which seems to only

consider co-exposure). Other approaches do not specifically discuss co-exposure as a grouping factor but focus on grouping components based on similar target organs and/or MoA, e.g. EFSA's CAGs (EFSA, 2013b) and the US EPA CMGs (US EPA, 2002b).

4.3.3. Exposure assessment

The approaches presented by US EPA (2002b) EFSA (2009 and 2012), WHO/IPCS (Meek et al., 2011) and, to some extent, BfR (Stein et al., 2014) and ECHA (2015) give guidance on a specific exposure assessment methodology for chemical mixtures. SCHER, SCENIHR, SCCS (2012) and CEFIC (Price et al., 2012) promote the WHO/IPCS approach, and the early reports from US EPA (2000) and ATSDR (2004) refer to traditional exposure assessment methods. It should be noted that in the approaches proposed by the US EPA (2002) and ATSDR a whole-mixture approach to risk assessment is stated as the preferred option (given that data for the whole mixture, or a sufficiently similar mixture, is available), which would mean conducting exposure assessment according to the same principles as for single chemical exposure. The reports from VKM (2008) and IGHR (2009) do not address exposure assessment, specifically.

The IPCS/WHO and EFSA approaches both incorporate tiered exposure assessment. At the lowest tier simple deterministic or semiquantitative estimates of exposure are conducted, representing conservative worst-case assessments. At higher tiers the assessment gets increasingly complex and approaching more realistic estimates, as more data is available. If available data allows, probabilistic estimations can be conducted at higher tiers. However, while the WHO/IPCS framework is intended to be generally applicable and modifiable to different types of chemical exposures, the EFSA framework is specific for estimating actual exposure to pesticide residues in food and for setting MRLs. EFSA has provided detailed guidance on the methodology for probabilistic modelling of acute and chronic dietary exposures to pesticide residues (EFSA, 2012). This guidance is not specific for exposure assessment of chemical mixtures but includes a separate section on approaches required for modelling exposure to multiple substances.

The BfR approach relating to the health risk assessment of pesticide residues in food provides guidance for assessing acute exposure only. The justification is that "*chronic [cumulative risk assessment] is not expected to reveal risks which have been overlooked in the past and is expected to be dispensable in the context of a PPP or BP evaluation*" (Stein et al., 2014). Further, Stein et al. (2014) state that chronic cumulative risk assessment can be conducted in principle, and should then use Supervised Trial Median Residue (STMR) values for the product/mixture considered and background levels for all other pesticide residues in the same CAG to estimate exposure.

4.3.4. Hazard assessment

The US EPA (2000) and ATSDR (2004) approaches specifically state that a whole-mixture approach to risk assessment is preferred, if data on an identical or sufficiently similar mixture is available. However, more recently it has been commonly discussed that this is not the preferable approach for most mixture risk assessments, as it is only applicable when exposure is from a single source and for mixtures that do not change significantly in their composition (CEFIC, 2012; SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). Further, whole mixture data can only be used for assessment of the endpoints that are measured in the study of the mixture (CEFIC, 2012). Consequently, the majority of the methodologies reviewed here promote the use of component-based approach to hazard and risk assessment of chemical mixtures.

An important difference from single chemical risk assessment, explicitly pointed out by the US EPA (2007), is that *“the health effects observed as a result of combined chemical exposures may differ in phenotype and/or magnitude from the critical effects caused by the individual chemical exposures. Thus, it is important to evaluate secondary effects for those chemicals to which humans may be exposed in combination.”*

One outcome of the hazard assessment is the identification of a value representing a “no effect” or “safe” dose/concentration to be used as basis for the risk characterisation. Depending on data availability and the methodology used to estimate risk (see sections 4.3.5 - 4.3.7), this can e.g. be a health-based guidance value, such as an ADI or Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) or a reference dose (RfD), or a point of departure (PoD), such as a no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL) or benchmark dose (BMD). The BMD approach is often preferred as it enables better use of available dose-response datasets compared to the NOAEL approach (EFSA, 2009b; Slob, 2014). As a PoD, the BMD lower confidence bound (BMDL), is more explicitly defined and provides more information and statistical precision than the NOAEL. As such, the BMD approach may also result in more precise estimates for relative potency factors (RPFs). Another advantage over the NOAEL approach is that the BMD approach allows for quantification of uncertainties in the dose-response data and the precision in the BMD estimate.

Ideally, the components of the mixture in question are known and there is sufficient data to identify individual guidance values or NOAELs/BMDs for all components. However, in many cases the components may not be known, or data may be lacking for a component or for the specific effect that is being assessed. In these cases, default assumptions and/or modifications based on scientific judgment have to be made (e.g. US EPA, 2000).

One generally acknowledged challenge is that guidance values or PoDs may not be available for the specific effect that is being assessed. E.g. an ADI is based on the critical effect of a compound but this may not be the effect that is relevant for the risk assessment in question. If the assessment is conducted for another, less sensitive effect, the hazard of the mixture may thus be overestimated. To address this potential limitation, the US EPA (2000) and ASTDR (2004) propose the use of a Target organ Toxicity Dose (TTD) for oral exposures or Target organ Toxicity Concentration (TTC) for exposure via inhalation. The TTD and TTC are toxicity-based exposure levels that are specific to the target organ of interest. They are derived in the same way as an RfD, ADI or TDI, i.e. by dividing a NOAEL or BMD by assessment (uncertainty) factors. The US EPA acknowledges that the use of TTD and TTC as basis for risk assessment is not common practice and that this approach should only be used when there is sufficient reason to believe that using a guidance value, such as an RfD, ADI or TDI, will lead to overestimations of the hazard that are significant for the risk assessment conclusions. Further, the use of the abbreviation “TTC” may be confusing as it currently has established use as the abbreviation for Threshold of Toxicological Concern. Similarly, it should be noted that the ATSDR uses the abbreviation “MRL” for the term Minimal Risk Level (used by the ATSDR as a guidance value), easily confused with the more general meaning of Maximum Residue Levels for pesticides.

The use of the Threshold for Toxicological Concern concept is suggested as a first-tier approach by the SCHER, SCENIHR and SCCS committees (2012) but is not mentioned in any of the other reports.

CEFIC (Price et al., 2012) introduces the concept of a Maximum Cumulative Ratio (MCR), which is included in their approach as a specific component of the decision tree. The MCR describes the contribution of the different components to the total toxicity of the mixture and is used “to identify

the optimum approaches for assessing and managing risks from combined exposures”. The MCR is calculated by dividing the total toxicity of the mixture by the largest toxicity contributed by any single chemical. If the MCR value is close to 1 it means that one of the components is the main driver of the toxicity. Conversely, if the value is close to the total number of components, then components contribute equally to the toxicity of the mixture.

A note can also be made for the BfR-approach, which states that there is no need for a specific cumulative risk assessment approach for chronic exposure to pesticide residues in food, since *“the use of the PPP or BP under consideration normally provides only a minor contribution to the overall chronic exposure of consumers to residues of the respective active substances and of substances belonging to the concerned CAGs. Summing up hazard quotients (on basis of the individual ADI values) for the active substances contained in the PPP or BP as for the acute cumulative assessment is therefore not recommended”* (Stein et al., 2014). The conservative calculations for single substances are considered protective enough and to include possible cumulative effects.

4.3.5. Risk assessment strategies when applying dose addition

The eleven approaches are in general agreement that dose addition can be applied when all components of a mixture cause the same effects in the same target organ or have a similar MoA. Strictly speaking, components should have similar MoA for dose addition to be applicable but, since mechanistic data commonly is limited, evidence of common effect and target organ is often considered sufficient (US EPA, 2000). Dose addition entails estimating the effect and cumulative risks of the mixture from the sum of the doses/concentrations, scaled for relative toxicity.

Notably, there is general agreement between reports that dose addition can be used as a default assumption, unless there is sufficient evidence to show that components act independently or that there are interactions causing synergisms or antagonism between components. There is little empirical evidence of interactions occurring between mixture components at (low) dose levels relevant for exposure scenarios in the general population (e.g. EFSA, 2008; EFSA, 2013e; EFSA, 2015b; SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). Dose addition is the most precautionary no-interaction model and is considered likely to produce human health risk estimates that are appropriate or somewhat conservative (US EPA, 2002b; ATSDR, 2004; EFSA, 2008; IGHR, 2009; Meek et al., 2011; SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). The US EPA states that additivity (i.e. either dose or response addition) should be default rather than assuming interactions and further specifies that dose addition should be used as default *“when the dose for each individual component is at a level at which effects are not expected to occur, be observable, or be of concern”* (US EPA, 2000).

The most common strategy for applying dose addition, promoted by all nine approaches, is the hazard index (HI) methodology. The HI is calculated by summing up the individual Hazard Quotients (HQ) for all components of the mixture. The HQ is calculated by dividing the estimated exposure of the component by its health-based guidance value (GV), e.g. an ADI or TDI:

Equation 9

$$\text{HQ} = \frac{\text{Exp}}{\text{GV}}$$

Thus, the HI is calculated as:

Equation 10

$$HI = \frac{Exp_1}{GV_1} + \frac{Exp_2}{GV_2} + \frac{Exp_3}{GV_3} + \frac{Exp_4}{GV_4} + \dots$$

When the HI is less than 1, the combined risk of the mixture is considered acceptable (EFSA, 2008).

A number of the reports also presents the Point of Departure Index (PoDI), also known as a Reference Point Index (RfPI), as an alternative to the HI-methodology. The PoDI/RfPI is calculated in a similar fashion as the HI but by dividing the exposure for each component by the NOAEL or BMD for the organ/effect in question. The combined risk of the mixture is considered acceptable if the PoDI/RfPI multiplied by a group assessment/uncertainty factor is lower than 1 (EFSA, 2008).

There is in general large agreement between the approaches that the most conservative (first tier) approach is to calculate a HI using the ADI/TDI/RfD for the most toxic component of the mixture. As refinement is increased (e.g. at higher tiers) individual health-based guidance values or NOAELs/BMDs, if available, are used as basis for HI- or PoDI/RfPI calculations.

The EFSA PPR (2008) and the VKM (2008) also discuss the Combined Margin of Exposure/Safety (MOET or TMOE/S) and Cumulative Risk Index (CRI). However, the EFSA PPR panel explicitly discourages the use of these methodologies since they are more complex mathematically than the HI and RfPI/PoDI (EFSA, 2008).

The majority of the approaches (except CEFIC) also discuss refined risk assessment strategies based on the use of component- and exposure route-specific relative potency factors (RPF). This method entails scaling the toxicity of each individual component in the mixture to the toxicity of an index substance. The health effect of the mixture is then assessed by using the dose-response curve of the index substance. According to the SCHER, SCENIHR and SCCS committees, *“The RPF method is transparent, and easy to understand, particularly because it separates potency correction from exposure considerations. Thus, it provides a better basis for standardising toxic dose metrics for the various chemicals. However, it should be noted that determination of the risk posed by the combined exposure places great emphasis on the quality of the toxicology database of the index compound”* (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). An example of the RPF-method is the application of toxicity equivalence factors (TEF) for dioxins and dioxin-like compounds (reviewed in US EPA, 2000). Many of the reviewed reports mention the application of the TEF-method for components with “very similar” MoA. The US EPA (2000) and the three scientific committees (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012), for example, provide detailed guidance and considerations for calculating and applying the RPF/TEF-method.

4.3.6. Risk assessment strategies when assuming independent action

In general, the definition for independent action applied in most of the reports reviewed is that mixture components have dissimilar MoA. However, in the publication from BfR (Stein et al., 2014) the wording is a bit unclear and seems to imply that independent action is the opposite of interaction. According to this definition, independent action could apply to components with dissimilar AND similar MoA, as long as there are no interactions. It is however assumed that this may be a case of unclear terminology, and that the definition expressed in the other reports can be believed to be generally accepted.

As mentioned previously, all of the reports reviewed express the opinion that even though components of a mixture can be assumed to show independent action it may still be valid to apply dose addition as default, as this generates protective risk estimates. However, the reports by US EPA (2000), ATSDR (2004), IGHR (2009), the three scientific committees (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012) and ECHA (2015) also discuss the use of effect or response addition methodologies to estimate effects and cumulative risk of chemical mixtures with independently acting components. Effects addition entails adding biological responses together, while response addition means adding (probabilistic) risks together (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012).

4.3.7. Risk assessment strategies when assuming interactions

Only four of the reviewed approaches address risk assessment strategies for mixtures with interactions between components (ATSDR, 2004; ECHA, 2015; IGHR, 2009; US EPA, 2000). The US EPA introduces the concept of a weight-of-evidence procedure that uses binary interaction data to modify the HI, the so called BINWOE method. This modification of the HI-approach is also discussed by the ATSDR and IGHR as a possible method to account for any interactions occurring between components. The IGHR also proposes an additional strategy that entails using the common HI-approach and applying an extra uncertainty factor for possible interactions.

4.3.8. Use of PBPK models to refine risk assessment

Since alterations in kinetic processes are an important mode of toxicological interactions between mixture components (e.g. US EPA, 2000) some of the approaches discuss the use of physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) data and models in the context of evaluating possible interactions, specifically. I.e. PBPK models can be used to estimate internal doses of mixture components and examine the potential for toxicological interactions between them. However, the US EPA (2002b), the PPR panel of EFSA (2008), the WHO/IPCS (Meek et al., 2011), the SCHER, SCENIHR and SCCS committees (2012) and the ECHA (2015) generally discuss the use of PBPK models to refine risk assessment at higher tiers of the assessment, without any specific description of their application or reference to the investigation of potential interactions.

4.3.9. Uncertainty analysis

Uncertainty analysis as part of the risk assessment of chemical mixtures is specifically discussed in the reports by the US EPA (2000; 2002b; 2003; 2007), the PPR Panel of EFSA (2008), the SCHER, SCENIHR and SCCS committees (2012) and ECHA (2015) (not shown in table). It is also specifically addressed in the review conducted by EFSA (2013a).

These reports do not provide detailed guidance for uncertainty analysis but discuss potential sources of uncertainty and some general principles. One main conclusion is that uncertainty analysis in risk assessment of chemical mixtures is a field where more research and development is needed. EFSA has provided detailed guidance on methodology for probabilistic modelling of acute and chronic exposures and, specifically, for quantifying variability and uncertainty in food consumption and residues (EFSA, 2012).

Many sources of uncertainty, e.g. uncertainties in model estimations, analytical methods, measurements, application of default assessment factors, etc. are the same in risk assessment of chemical mixtures and single chemicals. However, some additional variables and sources of

uncertainty may be introduced when conducting mixture risk assessment and include, but are not limited to (ECHA, 2015; EFSA, 2008; SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012; US EPA, 2000; 2002b, 2003; 2007):

- Uncertainties associated with grouping mixture components, both concerning the identity of relevant mixture components and assumptions regarding similar MoA or independent action. Especially information on secondary effects may be inadequate.
- Omissions from assessment groups due to lack of exposure data, e.g. uncertainties in dynamic fate models used to analyse co-exposures (US EPA, 2007), also, monitoring programmes do not include all pesticides present in the worldwide market and therefore compounds that should be included in a CAG may be left out (EFSA, 2007).
- The level of accuracy with which (co-)exposure to mixtures has been characterised, keeping in mind that exposure estimates may be based on several sources/uses and a number of events at several locations over broad and varied time periods.
- Assumptions of similar or dissimilar MoA used to support the choice of dose addition or response addition methodologies.
- Uncertainties concerning any interactions between mixture components, as well as uncertainties concerning interactions or additivity with other (unknown) chemicals.
- Potential overestimation of risk when applying response addition.
- Assumptions regarding similarity in the shape of the dose response curves and uncertainties in estimations of RPFs when applying dose addition
- Uncertainties in default assessment factors and resulting reference values (e.g. ADI, TDI) when calculating HI.
- Dose and response addition methods are simplistic mathematical models and are generally associated with greater uncertainty than dose-response assessments developed when the toxicity of the whole mixture is evaluated.
- Assumptions that the period during which effects will become manifest is similar for all components of the mixture, i.e. that latency and duration of effects is similar for all components.

The EFSA PPR panel notes that risk assessment of mixtures is affected by more potential sources of uncertainty than risk assessment of individual pesticides (EFSA, 2008).

The US EPA points out that uncertainty analysis in mixture risk assessment “*might be predominantly qualitative because of the use of numerous defaults (e.g., for addressing interactions and multiple effects)*” (US EPA, 2007). A challenge is also that it may be possible to quantify some aspects/sources of uncertainty for some of the mixture compounds, but not for others. Consequently, the uncertainty analysis method applied should allow for combining quantitative and qualitative uncertainty analyses in a structured and transparent way.

4.3.10. Further research and development needs

The purpose of this section is to identify if there are any aspects related to the development or practical application of risk assessment methodology for chemical mixtures that has not been covered, or covered to a limited degree, in previously proposed approaches, and that would need to be developed for the purposes of the work within EuroMix. While the approaches reviewed here

represent a vast expanse of knowledge and integrated methods to address the challenges of mixture risk assessment, some issues were identified where additional guidance or method development could increase transparency and structure, as well as improve confidence in risk assessment conclusions. These are especially:

Considerations for prioritisation and grouping

The fundamental problem that it is not possible to identify and assess all potential chemical mixtures makes the issue of how to prioritise chemicals for mixture risk assessment, as well as how to organise them into relevant assessment groups, central to the development and refinement of methodologies in this area. Prioritisation and grouping are generally addressed in several of the approaches reviewed here, and have been specifically discussed by EFSA (2013b) and US EPA (2002b; 2016).. There seems, for example, to be some agreement that the potential for exposure and similar effects/MoA are main factors that should drive prioritisation, as well as grouping. However, there is need for development of approaches to further refine groupings, e.g. EFSA CAGs, into narrower/smaller groups.

Problem formulation

Somewhat related to prioritisation and grouping is the concept of problem formulation, i.e. a specific and clear definition of the population group(s), chemicals, sources and routes of exposure, and health effects included in the assessment. Problem formulation is an initial step, conducted prior to risk assessment and few of the available approaches explicitly include this issue. However, problem formulation contributes to the transparency and structure of the assessment by providing the basis for the literature search strategy, criteria for the inclusion/exclusion of studies, type of data extracted from studies, and strategy for synthesis and reporting of results. In the EU, and especially in the context of EFSA, the problem formulation is usually embedded in the terms of reference and not as a defined step of the assessment process (EFSA, 2013a). The US EPA provides somewhat more detailed considerations for problem formulation (US EPA, 2003b; US EPA, 2007). Future activities for problem formulation are addressed in the review conducted by EFSA (2013a).

Criteria for dissimilar MoA

In general, the approaches and reports reviewed here promote using the assumption of similar MoA and applying dose addition as a default strategy. That means that clear criteria are needed for when to deviate from this assumption and apply the principle of independent action and effect/response addition. However, such criteria for determining when MoAs of different chemicals are sufficiently dissimilar to indicate independent action are currently lacking.

Non-animal toxicity data

The use of non-animal data, e.g. *in vitro* and *in silico* data, in risk assessment of chemicals is becoming increasingly more important with new advancements in such technologies and a general movement towards replacing, reducing and refining animal studies in toxicity testing. The SCHER, SCENIHR, SCCS committees briefly mention the use of *in vitro* and *in silico* methods in the context of enabling “pathway-based toxicity evaluations” but conclude that such an approach is not yet sufficiently robust or informative (SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012). The use of non-animal data in the context of risk assessment of chemical mixtures, e.g. for strategies for refined grouping or distinguishing between similar and dissimilar MoAs, remains to be further explored.

Methods and guidance for uncertainty analysis in mixture risk assessment

The complexity of chemical mixtures results in additional potential sources of uncertainty in the exposure and hazard assessments, as well as risk characterisation phase, compared to single chemical risk assessment. Although methods for uncertainty analysis in risk assessment of chemicals exist from different organisations (e.g. EFSA and US EPA) it is acknowledged in several of the reports reviewed here that more research and development of guidance for uncertainty analysis when conducting risk assessment for chemical mixtures is needed (e.g. US EPA, 2000; US EPA, 2003b; US EPA, 2007; EFSA, 2008; EFSA, 2013a; SCHER/SCENIHR/SCCS, 2012).

In 2014 EFSA held a Scientific Colloquium on “Harmonisation of human and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals” (EFSA, 2015b). In this colloquium four general topics were explored and discussed: 1) mechanistic models for hazard assessment, 2) harmonisation of methods for combined exposure assessment, 3) the use of OMICs and *in silico* methods for risk assessment, and 4) application of science-based uncertainty factors and approaches for risk characterisation using mechanistic approaches. Although focus was primarily on the harmonisation of human and ecological risk assessment, data gaps and future research needs similar or related to the ones listed above were identified and are further discussed in the summary report (EFSA, 2015b). Specifically, there were discussions on methods to deal with mixture components with dissimilar MoA, how to improve the use of non-animal data in risk assessment of mixtures, and on the development of methods to handle uncertainty in the risk assessment.

4.3.11. Summary and conclusions

In this review of current approaches for risk assessment of chemical mixtures, eleven frameworks and decision trees from ten different organisations were scrutinised and compared. The points of comparison were chosen specifically based on aspects relevant for the work in EuroMix and with the aim to provide the basis for a proposal of an approach suitable for that work. Thus, focus was on the overall structure of the different methodologies as well as on specific strategies proposed for exposure assessment, hazard assessment and risk characterisation, such as methods for grouping, choice of hazard and risk estimates and default assumptions.

While some of the approaches reviewed are meant to be general frameworks applicable for different purposes others were developed with a specific exposure source (e.g. ATSDR, 2009) or group of chemicals (e.g. ECHA, 2015; EFSA, 2008; Stein et al., 2014; US EPA, 2002b; US EPA 2016) in mind. Nevertheless, the approaches show many similarities in their general structures, as well as in the principles applied. A tiered approach is generally recommended, especially in more recent reports, and the tiered IPCS/WHO tiered framework is endorsed by several organisations, with certain modifications for specific purposes. Further, there is general agreement that dose addition generates sufficiently protective health risk measures, also when mixture components show independent action, and may therefore be used as the default assumption when estimating health risks of chemical mixtures. In terms of specific risk assessment methodologies, the HI-approach is generally promoted. If a lower tier approach indicates a risk, refinements in the next higher tier, using component- and exposure route specific RPFs as well as PBPK-modelling, is considered necessary in many of the available approaches.

Some areas in need of further research and development were identified and include strategies for prioritisation and grouping of chemicals, problem formulation, criteria for determining when MoAs are sufficiently dissimilar to assume independent action, and guidance for conducting uncertainty

analysis in this context. Several of these aspects, or related issues, were also identified at the EFSA 2014 Scientific Colloquium on the harmonisation of human and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals, and are further discussed in that context in the summary report (EFSA, 2015b).

Recently the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) paradigm has been promoted for application in risk assessment of chemicals. The AOP methodology is an approach which provides a framework to collect, organise and evaluate relevant information concerning the effect cascade caused by chemicals linking a molecular initiating event (MIE), to key events (KE) and an adverse outcome (AO). As such, this approach supports the use of a mode (and/or mechanism) of action basis for understanding adverse effects of chemical mixtures. In addition to providing a structured approach for summarising current knowledge and identifying data gaps, the AOP methodology could prove to be a useful tool for the risk assessment of mixtures. For example, the AOP approach provides a framework within which it is possible to theoretically explore the assumptions of similar and dissimilar MoA, and potential interactions between mixture components. Similarly, it can be used as an approach for refined grouping of chemicals into relevant assessment groups. AOPs also provide a basis for predicting adverse effects in individuals or populations based on mechanistic non-animal data. In general, AOPs can contribute significantly to the development of integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATA) of chemicals (e.g. Edwards et al., 2016; US EPA, 2015; US EPA 2016).

The AOP knowledge base (AOP KB³⁰) was initiated by the OECD and is executed in close collaboration with the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC), the US EPA, and the US Army Engineer Research & Development Center. The AOP KB is intended as a resource for sharing, developing and discussing AOP related knowledge in the scientific community. One part of the AOP KB is the AOP Wiki, the central repository for all AOPs developed as part of the OECD AOP Development Effort by the Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics. The AOP Wiki is managed jointly by the JRC and the US EPA. The OECD has published a guidance document (OECD, 2013) as well as a User's Handbook (OECD, 2016), providing an overview which kind of information is necessary to identify and document an AOP and how to structure the data. The User's Handbook is intended as a living document; it provides the most updated guidance, and should primarily be consulted when developing AOPs. The Handbook also provides instructions on how to undertake the assessment of an AOP in terms of its relevance and adequacy. It includes templates and guidance intended to improve consistency in AOPs developed by different stakeholders.

In summary, structured, tiered frameworks, as well as basic methodologies, have been developed, proposed and thoroughly discussed by several organisations. The development of an approach for use in EuroMix entails identifying and incorporating the aspects considered most appropriate for the purposes of the project, considering both the research and regulatory goals. In addition, further development may be needed to address the current knowledge gaps and research needs identified here. Incorporation of the AOP paradigm into the EuroMix approach is recommended as it provides a structured and transparent approach to organising current knowledge, as well as meeting those needs.

³⁰ <http://aopkb.org/>

5. Conclusion

5.1. Summary

Factual basis

For a reliable chemical risk assessment reliable data and sound knowledge on the potential exposure and toxic properties of chemical substances is required. For the effect evaluation of chemicals, knowledge of the uptake and mode of action is crucial. Furthermore, interactions between components of formulated products or unintentional mixtures may have an influence on the overall toxicity. For the exposure assessment the exposure through different sources and routes of one or more chemicals should be taken into consideration for a more realistic assessment.

Legal basis in the EU

Most reviewed regulations stipulate to consider mixture toxicity or cumulative and synergistic effects. If the assessment of mixture toxicity is required, statements like “if appropriate methods are available”, “where relevant” or “known and expected cumulative and synergistic effects shall be considered”, weaken the requirement and create a loophole of not considering it. The CLP Regulation is one of the few regulations providing guidance on how the hazard of mixtures shall be assessed. However, the intention of CLP is a hazard-based classification and no complete risk assessment and therefore exposure information is not considered. A guidance document for a risk assessment accounting for mixture toxicity only exists for biocidal products. However, EFSA is currently developing a guidance document for human and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals using existing frameworks as a starting point.

Legal basis in non-EU countries

All considered countries have legal acts to control the production, import and use of chemical substances in order to protect human and animal health as well as the environment and legally require the classification of chemicals according to GHS, apart from Japan. In general, chemical substances have to be registered before sale and use. Products for specific uses such as medicine, cosmetics, and food related or pesticidal products are mostly regulated in separate legal acts with specific requirements adapted to the field of use and application. A risk assessment based on effect and exposure data has to be conducted before products can be placed onto the market. The consideration of combined effects is legally binding in Australia, Canada and USA, whereas Brasil, Japan and Korea do not have legal requirements to consider mixture toxicity. US EPA has a long history of chemical risk assessment and seems to be ahead of other countries, in terms of the legal requirements and the implementation of the cumulative risk assessment

5.2. Challenges

Effect site

- Detailed information on the mode of action of most chemicals is currently lacking. In this context, AOPs are considered as an alternative approach, but have to be developed and validated.
- Interactions of chemicals in mixtures are difficult to predict, particularly for chronic exposure.
- Animal tests enable the most realistic effect estimation, but shall be reduced. Alternative methods have to be developed and validated.
- There is a need to base effect evaluation on *in vitro* and *in silico* methods, however, the extrapolation to effects on animals, humans and the environment is challenging.
- Few chronic whole-mixture tests are available for estimation of human health, more mixture testing is performed in the environmental area..
- For a risk assessment of mixtures, chemical substances shall be grouped in common assessment groups, however, two different approaches for grouping of pesticidal substances exist currently. An international harmonisation of these approaches is considered necessary.
- No general approach for the effect estimation of mixtures available.

Exposure site

- The assessment of a realistic exposure of humans and the environment to certain chemicals is a major challenge as different exposure routes have to be considered and the total exposure has to be assessed.
- Data on chemical residues is rare.
- Large-scale monitoring programs are required to provide realistic exposure data for risk assessment, also with regard to multiple residues from different products.
- Important information on realistic chemical exposures of the human population is lacking
- Existing data need is not summarised; well organised, public available databases are required to support science and decision making of risk assessors and risk managers.

Risk assessment

- Criteria for the prioritisation of chemical mixtures considered for a risk assessment are unclear.
- Risk assessment is conducted in different regulatory sectors as chemical substances are present in isolation. The chemical-by-chemical risk assessment within one legal sector cannot fully assess the risk of chemical substances, as risk profiles are overlapping
- There is no general framework for a systematic, comprehensive and integrated assessment of chemicals and mixture effects, which considers different routes of exposure and different product types.
- There are many parallel activities of research, authorities and international organisations regarding the development of approaches for cumulative risk assessment, which might lead to different risk assessment approaches and results in different countries.
- No cumulative risk assessment for non-intentional mixtures.
- No general approach for the cumulative risk assessment of chemical mixtures.
- Broad cumulative assessment groups lead to high risks, refinement of groups might

5.3. Recommendations

EU wide

- Implement a clear legal mandate in each regulation, to consider mixture toxicity for the authorisation of chemical substances/products.
- Avoid loopholes and provide clear guidance how to assess mixture toxicity in the respective regulation.
- Avoid different approaches for the risk assessment in different regulations. Risk assessment conducted under different regulations shall come to similar results for chemical substances and products.
- Consider an approach which allows a comprehensive evaluation of hazardous chemical products that are regulated in various regulations and widely used.
- Develop a guidance document for human and ecological risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals using existing frameworks as starting points and tiered approaches for each step including problem formulation, hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment and risk characterisation.

Globally

- Harmonise terminology in the field of cumulative risk assessment.
- Establish criteria for the prioritisation of chemical mixtures considered for a risk assessment.
- Obtain an overview on all on-going actions and discussions regarding legal requirements, current implementation and mixture approaches.
- Set up a network involving European and Non-European authorities and international organisations such as EFSA and WHO, US-EPA to generate synergies and bundle forces to develop a harmonised approach for the evaluation of mixtures. The network should:
 - Compile available data on mixture toxicity and case studies in public available databases to support science and decision of risk assessors
 - Develop appropriate methods for exposure assessment and risk characterisation.
 - Verify *in silico* methods and *in vitro* bioassays and the extrapolation from these results to humans.
 - Improve toxicological testing strategies for the assessment of mixture toxicity for all relevant groups of chemicals.
 - Develop harmonised criteria and strategies for refinement for cumulative assessment groups.
 - Develop a tiered approach to evaluate the risk of chemical mixtures.
 - Develop an applicable guideline for the effect evaluation of mixtures and a tiered approach for risk assessment of mixtures
 - Clarify if a general, systematic and comprehensive framework is feasible for both the protection of human and environmental health.
- At present JRC, EFSA and OECD develop guidance documents in the field of cumulative risk assessment. An effort should be made to harmonise approaches and use similar strategies.

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List of Abbreviations

ABNT	Brasilian Association of Technical Ruling
ADI	Acceptable daily intake
AICS	Australian Inventory of Chemical Substances
ANVISA	Brasilian Ministry of Health
AO	Adverse Outcome
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
AOP KB	Adverse Outcome Pathway Knowledge Base
APVMA	Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority
ATE	acute toxicity estimates
BBDR	Biologically-Based Dose-Response
BfR	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower confidence bound
BP	Bridging Principles
CA	Concentration Addition
CAG	Cumulative Assessment Group
CARES	Cumulative and Aggregate Risk Exposure Model
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
CEFIC	European Chemical Industry Council
CEPA	Canadian Environmental Protection Act
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging of substances
CMG	Common Mechanism Group
CRA	Cumulative Risk Assessment
CRI	Cumulative Risk Index
CSCL	Chemical Substances Control Law (Japan)
DEQ	Department of Environmental Quality (Canada)
DNEL	Derived No-effect-Levels
DQRA _{Chem}	Detailed Quantitative Risk Assessment for Chemicals
DSL	Domestic Substances List (Canada)
EC	European Community
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EEC	European Economic Community

EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMA	European Medicine Agency
EU	European Union
EuroMix	European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures
FCSAP	Federal Contaminated Sites Action Plan (Canada)
FFDCA	Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (USA)
FIFRA	Federal Insecticide, Fungicide, and Rodenticide Act (USA)
FQPA	Food Quality Protection Act (USA)
FSANZ	Food Standards Australia New Zealand
GerES	German Environmental Survey
GHS	Globally Harmonised System
GPE	Greatest Potential Exposure
GV	Guidance Value
HBGV	Health-Based Guidance Value (Australia)
HI	Hazard Index
HQ	Hazard Quotient
IATA	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment
IBAMA	Brasilian Ministry of the Environment
ILCR	Incremental Lifetime Cancer Risk
IPCS	International Programme on Chemical Safety
IPE	Intermediate Potential Exposure
JRC	Joint Research Centre of the European Commission
KE	Key Event
KER	Key Event Relationship
LOAEL	Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level
LPE	Lowest Potential Exposure
MAPA	Brasilian Ministry of Agriculture
MCR	Maximum Cumulative Ratio
MCRA	Monte Carlo Risk Assessment
MCS	Multi-Constituent Substances
M-factor	Multiplying factors
MFDS	Ministry of Food and Drug Safety (Korea)
MIE	Molecular Initiating Event

MoA	Mode of Action
MOE	Margin Of Exposure
MOET	Combined Margin of Exposure (also abbreviated as TMOE)
MoS	Margin of Safety
MRL	Maximum Residue Levels
NHANES	National Report on Human Exposure to Environmental Chemicals
NIFDS	National Institute of Food and Drug Safety Evaluation, Korea
NITE	National Institute of Technology and Evaluation, Japan
NICNAS	National Industrial Chemicals Notification and Assessment Scheme (Australia)
NOAEL	No Observed Adverse Effect Level
OAR	Oregon Administrative Rule (Canada)
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
OPP	Office of Pesticide Programs (USA)
PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons
PBTK	Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic,
PCBs	Poly-Chlorinated Biphenyls
PCDDs	Poly-Chlorinated Dibenzo Dioxins
PCDFs	Poly-Chlorinated Dibenzo Furans
PCPA	Pest Control Products Act (Canada)
PF	Process Factor
PMRA	Pest Management Regulatory Agency (Canada)
PoD	Point of Departure
PoDI	Point of Departure Index
PQRA	Preliminary Quantitative Risk Assessment
PRIA	Pesticide Registration Improvement Act (USA)
RA	Risk Assessment
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of chemicals
RExY	Residential Exposure-Year
RfC	Reference Concentration
RfD	Reference dose
RfPI	Reference Point Index
RIVM	Dutch national institute for public health and the environment

RPF	Relative Potency Factors
RPF _n	Relative Potency Factors of chemical n
SCHER	Scientific Committee on Health and Environmental Risks
SCENIHR	Scientific Committee on Emerging and Newly Identified Health Risks
SCCS	Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety
SED	Systemic Exposure Dose
SM	Summation Method
STM _R	Supervised Trial Median Residue
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
TEF	Toxicity Equivalence Factor
TGA	Therapeutics Goods Administration (Australia)
TMoE/S	Combined Margin of Exposure/Safety
TRV	Toxicological Reference Values
TTC	Target organ Toxicity Concentration (not Threshold of Toxicological Concern)
TTD	Target organ Toxicity Dose
UFA	Uncertainty Factor due to Animal-to-human variation
UFD _b	Database Uncertainty Factor
UFH	Uncertainty Factor due to inter-Human variability
UFL	Uncertainty Factor to extrapolate from the LOAEL to NOAEL
UFS	Uncertainty Factor to extrapolate from Subchronic to chronic data
US	United States of America
USC	United States Code
US EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
WHO	World Health Organisation